

The Physical Evolution of Galaxies

Jarle Brinchmann

Clare Hall

A thesis submitted to the University of Cambridge
for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy

September 1999

Declaration

I hereby declare that this thesis is not substantially the same as any that I have submitted for a degree or diploma or other qualification at any other University. I further state that no part of my thesis has already been or is being concurrently submitted for any such degree, diploma or other qualification.

This thesis is based on my own work, except where explicit reference has been made. The length of this thesis does not exceed the limit of sixty thousands words set by the Degree Committee for Physics and Chemistry.

Acknowledgements

Since I as a nine-year old turned away from the animal kingdom as my main interest to astronomy, my family has always supported me, showed interest in my field and let me troddle on without questions about the use and utility of my education. I owe them a huge gratitude, mum, dad, brother, aunts, uncles, cousins, all of you, thanks!

My time in Cambridge has been a good time. And much gratitude must go to Richard Ellis for his role in supervising this thesis, his constant interest in the topic and his ability to become exasperated with my time-wasting at the right moments. Thanks Richard. For being a good supervisor and even more importantly, a great person. And when Richard was not there (which sometimes happened), Bob Abraham would always be there for my questions and ideas. Always friendly and helpful, Bob, you are great for talking to when everything seems dull and dreary, thanks! Thanks also to Per Lilje, without him I probably would not be here writing this thesis, Simon Lilly for being an interesting and interested discussion partner, Masataka Fukugita for suggestions and constructive critique, and to the friendly gang in Durham, Carlos, Shaun, Cedric and Carlton for interesting discussions.

My gratitude also goes out to all the good friends I have. To my office mates, Manuela for always being happy and stressed and being a good friend, and Vernon for introducing me to squash and the quirks of English humour. To Jon for writing up at the same time as me and for his friendly ways, to Steve for the late games of snooker, to Jarrod for the equally late games of darts. To Felipe for always being in a good mood. To Matthew, Marcus, Tiziana, Stefano, Margarida, Clovis and the others from my year. To Mike, Meghan, Celine, Alwyn, Julia, Sara, Andrea, Andrew, Raquel and everyone else!

Thanks also to the computer staff who allowed me into the sacred helpdesk for three months, it was a good time, thanks Pete, Andy, Hardip and Sue and Paul for offering me the opportunity. And thanks to the staff for making this a good place to work, to Paul, Jane, Elsie, Margaret, Pamela, Judith, Sofia, Eileen, Brian, Peter, David and John.

Thanks also to everyone else at the institute that I have enjoyed talking to or going to the pub with, in particular Ian² and Aylwyn for arranging the pub-nights, and to Priya, Marie, Laurence, Ed, Bianca, Liliya, Steve², Sverre, Matthew, Melvyn, Sylvie, Annette, George, Vince, Gerry, Oleg, Rachel, Ofer, Ilidio, Claudia, Piero, Francine, Richard, Max, Alex, David and Nicole. I have had a great time.

My friends outside the IoA have helped save my sanity, special thanks go to my long-time housemates in Norway, Torgeir, Espen and Bernard. Det var en bra tid, skulle ønske dere var her! Varme hilsner går også til Tale, Kristine, Ingebjørg og alle andre jeg hang sammen med på den tiden. Thanks Darrin for teaching me the Queens(land) English, and to Nick, Tooraj, Gerald, Christian and Shane for great companionship and fun house-sharing. You were always a haven of sanity when days had been too long at the IoA. Thanks also to the other masticators, Britta, Warren, Jackie, Jörg, Carol, Warren, Lisa, Mira and Sally. And to Teca for arranging a very particular party. I have had a great time and you are all part of the reason for that.

Finally, I want to express my gratitude to Anabela. Your support and love has been a ray of light when the going was tough and nothing seemed to work. Thank you so much.

Summary

This thesis presents the study of a large sample of galaxies with redshifts and Hubble Space Telescope imaging. This sample is used to study the morphological and physical evolution of galaxies between $z = 1$ and the present.

Chapter 1 gives an introduction to the field and an historical context for the present work. The general topic of galaxy formation is reviewed here and relevant observational results are summarised.

Chapter 2 constructs the samples used in the thesis. The alignment and unification of these samples is described in detail. In addition, a Monte Carlo method for estimating errors in k -corrections is outlined and used to determine the accuracy of the absolute magnitude determinations. We conclude the chapter with a summary of the HST observations performed and their connection with ground-based spectroscopy.

The morphological characteristics of the sample are presented in Chapter 3. Both visual and automated classifications are used and the robustness of the latter as a function of redshift is quantified using simulations.

The morphologies and redshifts for the sample allow us to study morphologically segregated redshift distributions and luminosity functions in Chapter 4. We will here see that a class of “peculiar” galaxies makes an increasingly important contribution to the overall population of galaxies at higher redshifts, implying substantial evolution. Less dramatic evolution is found for spiral and elliptical galaxies and we contrast the evolution of these classes by calculating their contributions to the overall luminosity density and star formation.

Chapter 5 describes our efforts to obtain near infrared observations for the sample. These data are used in Chapter 6 to constrain the luminous masses of the galaxies in the sample. We use these estimates to study the distribution of luminous mass for the sample and calculate the integrated mass density of the universe as a function of redshift, showing clearly that peculiar galaxies at high redshift are physically different from their low redshift counterparts and that the mass density of elliptical galaxies is increasing from $z = 1$ to the present. To constrain the evolution of spiral galaxies we examine these in more detail before finishing with a study of the star formation characteristics of the sample galaxies as a function of stellar mass.

To my family
Past
Present
and Future

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Early studies	2
1.2	Determining cosmological parameters	2
1.3	Formation of structure in the universe	4
1.4	Formation and evolution of galaxies	6
1.4.1	The IMF	6
1.4.2	Evolutionary models	7
1.4.3	Modelling galaxy formation	8
1.5	Constraining models — the quest for $N(z)$	9
1.6	An outline of the thesis	12
2	The ground based catalogues and HST observations	15
2.1	The LDSS/Autofib redshift surveys	16
2.1.1	The LDSS-1 survey	17
2.1.2	The LDSS-2 redshift survey	18
2.1.3	The Autofib redshift survey	18
2.2	The Canada-France Redshift Survey	19
2.2.1	Magnitude measurements	19
2.3	HST observations and image analysis	20
2.3.1	Identification and extraction of objects	20
2.3.2	Photometry of objects	24
2.4	Estimates of colours and SEDs for galaxies	26
2.4.1	The Monte Carlo method	30
2.4.2	Examples of use	31
2.4.3	Summary	34
2.5	Joining the surveys	34
2.5.1	Alignment of the magnitude systems	35
2.5.2	Quality indicators and naming scheme	38
2.6	Consistency checks	38
2.7	Summary	40

3	Measures of morphologies	43
3.1	Introduction	43
3.2	An overview of classification procedures	44
3.2.1	Expert systems	48
3.2.2	The “light distribution” methods	49
3.2.3	Spectral classifications	50
3.3	Visual classifications used in this work	50
3.3.1	The peculiar class	55
3.4	Automated classifications	56
3.4.1	Central concentration	57
3.4.2	Asymmetry	60
3.4.3	The Frei et al. Calibration Sample	60
3.5	Redshift dependent biases	63
3.5.1	Wavelength-dependent Trends	64
3.5.2	Results from Detailed Simulations	64
3.6	Sample properties	69
3.6.1	Contrasting the eyeball and automated classifications	73
3.7	The Yerkes classification revisited	74
4	Evolution of the sample	77
4.1	Methodological considerations	77
4.2	The local census of galaxies	78
4.2.1	Type dependent luminosity functions	80
4.3	The present sample	85
4.3.1	Classification based on B/T and colours	85
4.4	Theoretical predictions for the morphologically split redshift distributions	87
4.4.1	Dependence of $N(z)$ on cosmology and LF	88
4.5	The observed redshift distribution of different morphological types	90
4.6	Luminosity functions	91
4.6.1	Luminosity densities	100
4.7	Spectroscopic properties	103
4.8	Discussion	108
4.8.1	Spirals	108
4.8.2	Ellipticals	108
4.8.3	Peculiars	109
4.9	The road forwards	110
5	Infrared observations and data assembly	111
5.1	The IRCAM3 observations	112
5.1.1	Reduction	114
5.1.2	Analysis and photometry	116
5.1.3	Completeness and non-detections	117
5.2	From the literature	119

5.2.1	CFRS and Groth strip fields	120
5.3	Further HST data	121
5.3.1	The Hubble Deep Field North and flanking fields	122
5.3.2	The Hawaii Deep Field	123
5.4	Consistency checks	124
5.5	Photometric properties	126
6	Evolution revisited	129
6.1	Prediction of luminous masses from K -magnitudes	130
6.1.1	A comparison with dynamical mass estimates	136
6.1.2	Selection criteria	138
6.2	The mass distribution of the sample	138
6.3	Properties of spiral galaxies	150
6.3.1	The mass-luminosity relation	153
6.3.2	The concentration of spirals	155
6.4	Star formation characteristics	160
6.5	Summary	164
6.6	Future prospects	166
A	An astrophysical reference	185
A.1	An astronomical glossary	185
A.2	Cosmology	187

Chapter 1

Introduction

The question whether nebulae are external galaxies hardly any longer needs discussion. It has been answered by the progress of discovery. No competent thinker, with the whole of the available evidence before him, can now, it is safe to say, maintain any single nebula to be a star system of co-ordinate rank with the Milky Way.

AGNES C. CLARKE (1890)

This thesis is concerned with the physical evolution of galaxies from about half the age of the universe till the present. To set the scene for the subsequent chapters, this introduction will review and introduce many of the concepts used in this thesis. It is primarily intended to give an overview, and topics important for the discussion are reviewed in more detail in the relevant chapters. In the introduction I¹ therefore wish to put more emphasis on the evolution of the subject rather than the actual prevailing theoretical paradigm, parts of which are always up for revision and possible falsification. The structure follows roughly the historical evolution of the subject of galaxy evolution, but with excursions up to the present interposed. This will lead up to a short overview of the thesis, showing how it fits into the recent work on galaxy evolution.

No introduction can sample all aspects of galaxy evolution and formation; this is no exception. I have chosen to focus on the historical development of the subject and primarily on observations at low redshifts. Some omissions are more important than others, some might miss a discussion of observations of high-redshift galaxies (Steidel et al. 1999; Madau 1999), others a review of the determinations of the optical, infrared and microwave background radiation (Madau & Pozzetti 1999; Partridge 1995) or the evolution of clusters (Van Dokkum et al. 1998; Barger et al. 1998). All of these are important issues in their own right, but I have decided here to concentrate on issues that directly lead up to the subject of the thesis.

¹In the introduction I have chosen to use 'I' as the pronoun, but in the rest of the thesis I follow the astronomical convention of using 'we'.

1.1 Early studies

Theorising about other galaxies outside our own started early, even before there was a clear notion of a “galaxy” as a separate entity. This early history is retold with great enthusiasm in [Hoskin \(1998\)](#). The discussions about the nature of the “nebulæ” culminated in the famous Shapley-Curtis debate in 1920, before the extragalactic nature of some galaxies was firmly established by Edwin Hubble ([1926](#)). The details of this fascinating period in the history of astronomy are well summarised in “The Hubble Atlas of Galaxies” ([Sandage 1961](#)), and as Sandage strongly emphasises, this controversy teaches us many lessons about the way science progresses and the supposed “objectivity” of science.

The outcome of all this was that a whole new field of astronomy was born — the study of the universe of galaxies. Advances came quickly, and already in 1929 Hubble announced that the universe was expanding; this work was expanded in collaboration with Humason and published in [Hubble & Humason \(1931\)](#). This was complemented with a study of the distribution of galaxies, counting galaxies at different limiting magnitudes. This enabled [Hubble \(1934\)](#) to show that the distribution of galaxies at least was reasonably homogeneous, which greatly simplified the analysis of cosmological models.

Parallel to this exciting observational work, major advances in theory helped shape the world-picture. Based on Einstein’s general theory of relativity (GR), several people constructed cosmological models. Of particular interest here are the Friedman² models which are solutions of the GR field equations for an isotropic and homogeneous universe with zero pressure. I will adopt this model for the universe in this thesis and the basic results are summarised in [Appendix A](#). It turns out that these models primarily depend on three basic parameters, the density of matter Ω_0 , the cosmological constant, Λ and Hubble’s constant, H_0 . These parameters govern the overall evolution of the universe and a great deal of work has gone into determining these.

1.2 Determining cosmological parameters

It was early realised that observations of galaxies could be used to constrain the cosmological parameters, and Hubble reviewed this in “The Realms of the Nebulæ”, concluding that the data were insufficient to make any strong statements. Indeed his early estimate of the Hubble constant was about a factor of 5–10 too large, implying an age of the universe well shorter than the geological age of the Earth for the simplest cosmological models, leading some researchers to postulate alternative coasting models of the universe (see the discussion in [Felten & Isaacman 1986](#), and references therein). The value of H_0 was adjusted down by Baade (recounted in [Baade 1956](#)) and subsequently [Sandage \(1958\)](#) to $0.5 < h < 1$, where $h = H_0/100$ km/s/Mpc. Later determinations of H_0 have mainly stayed within these limits, but the scatter between different determinations has generally been substantially larger than

²The naming of cosmological models is inconsistent; a clear exposition of the historically correct naming is given by [Felten & Isaacman \(1986\)](#).

the intrinsic error quoted by any one group. The upshot has been that the age of the universe has been unknown to within a factor 2.

Most methods used to estimate H_0 depend on local calibration samples (see [Rowan-Robinson 1985](#)), the classical approach is to use the period-luminosity relation for Cepheids to determine absolute luminosities and through Equation (A.4) the value of H_0 . This approach has benefited greatly from the refurbished Hubble Space Telescope (HST) and the “ H_0 key project” (e.g. [Freedman 1999](#)) has measured distances to a large set of galaxies (at least 25 papers at the time of writing), and the determinations of H_0 are now starting to converge on $H_0 = 71 \pm 7$ km/s/Mpc ([Freedman 1999](#)), which gives an age of the universe $\gtrsim 13$ Gyr consistent with the ages of the oldest stars in globular clusters ([Chaboyer et al. 1998](#)). Other determinations of H_0 using a similar distance ladder approach are given by nearby supernovae ([Branch 1998](#), and references therein), surface brightness fluctuations ([Jensen et al. 1998](#)) and various luminosity function arguments (see [Freedman 1999](#) for a review). These all give results in roughly the same range, and I will adopt

$$H_0 = 65 \pm 10 \text{ km/s/Mpc}, \quad (1.1)$$

which encompasses most recent values and is consistent with the determinations of Ω_0 and λ_0 reviewed below. An alternative route to H_0 is provided by gravitational lensing ([Refsdal 1964](#); [Blandford & Narayan 1992](#)) which does not rely on local distance calibrations, instead the main uncertainty is in the modelling of the lens ([Grogin & Narayan 1996a,b](#)). The results show a larger scatter than the distance-ladder methods, but in general agreement with these.

The Hubble constant alone is not sufficient to determine the age of the universe. For a model with non-zero λ_0 and Ω_0 , the present age of the universe, t_0 , can be approximated by ([Peacock 1999](#), see also [Carroll et al. 1992](#))

$$t_0 = \frac{2}{3} H_0^{-1} (0.7\Omega_0 + 0.3(1 - \lambda_0))^{-0.3}. \quad (1.2)$$

Similarly the overall geometry of the universe is determined by Ω_0 and λ_0 (Equation (A.11)) so the determination of these constants has been a major area of research for many years. Much of the research was pursued using the 200 inch telescope on Mt. Palomar, and the now classical four tests of world-models were set out by [Sandage \(1961a\)](#). These were the redshift-magnitude relation, the number-magnitude relation, the angular-diameter-redshift relation and the time scale of the universe. All of these have been of major importance in later observational work and were reviewed by [Sandage \(1988\)](#), see also [Sandage 1995](#)). The most promising path seemed to be the magnitude-redshift relation and substantial effort went into obtaining redshifts of cluster galaxies to determine Ω_0 and λ_0 from this relation (see [Sandage 1995](#) for an historical account). I will return to the observational results below, suffice to say that evolutionary effects in galaxies turn out to dominate the uncertainties in the determinations of Ω_0 and λ_0 so accurate values have been hard to find.

It was however clear that the density of the universe was in the vicinity of the critical value $\Omega_0 = 1$. As shown in Appendix A this is an unstable solution in the sense that if Ω was

slightly less than zero at high redshift one would find $\Omega_0 \ll 1$ today. Thus the theoretical prejudice is for $\Omega_0 = 1$ exactly and to explain this the theory of inflation was introduced (Narlikar & Padmanabhan 1991). This theory postulates that the universe went through a phase of exponential expansion at a very early epoch causing the universe to be spatially flat, $\Omega_0 + \lambda_0 = 1$, today.

The determination of Ω_0 in the last twenty years has followed several paths such as abundance of galaxy clusters, large-scale velocity flows and the properties of the cosmic microwave background. Although the latter might give the best estimates of cosmological parameters in the long run (Efstathiou & Bond 1999), the most exciting recent developments have however come by adopting one of the classical tests — the redshift-magnitude diagram. But instead of applying this to galaxies with their unknown evolutionary behaviour, the recent attempts have used the light-curves of supernovae type Ia. It turns out that it is possible to calibrate their peak luminosities (Riess et al. 1996) and assuming these are invariant one gets a strong constraint on Ω_0 and λ_0 (Perlmutter et al. 1999)

$$0.8\Omega_0 - 0.5\lambda_0 \approx -0.2 \pm 0.1, \quad (1.3)$$

which for a flat universe gives $\Omega_0 \approx 0.3$ and $\lambda_0 \approx 0.7$. A comparison of these results with other determinations of Ω_0 and λ_0 is presented by Perlmutter et al. (1999) and also in the review by Bahcall et al. (1999). Following the latter authors I will adopt a $\Omega_0 = 0.35$, $\lambda_0 = 0.65$ and $h = 0.65$ as the fiducial cosmological model in the following.

1.3 Formation of structure in the universe

The most successful methods for estimating cosmological parameters mentioned above all originated with the early pioneers of cosmological observations in the 1930s. The study of structure formation in these universes also started during this time (e.g. Tolman 1934) and the general solution for the gravitational collapse of perturbations in an expanding universe was derived by Lifshitz (1946). The main characteristic of this solution compared to static media was that the growth of structure was only algebraic as compared to exponential for the Jeans solution. The Lifshitz solution therefore requires finite initial perturbations to reach a given size today.

Parallel to this, Gamow (1948) showed that the universe would have been extremely hot and dense in its early phases, the “Big Bang”, and predicted a relic radiation field, the cosmic microwave background, shown to have a temperature $T = 5$ K by Alpher & Herman (1948). Gamow’s emphasis was however on element production in this hot phase, a process which subsequently was shown not to produce the required amounts of heavy elements. Instead, Burbidge et al. (1957) showed that heavy elements primarily were synthesised inside massive stars and subsequently ejected into the interstellar medium through supernova explosions and stellar winds. The interest in element production in a hot Big Bang was however rekindled by the discovery of the background radiation by Penzias & Wilson (1965), and led several groups to calculate the expected amount of helium and deuterium formed in the early universe (Peebles 1966; Wagoner et al. 1967); later refined to give a fairly strict

limit of the density of baryons relative to the critical density, $0.010 \gtrsim \Omega_B h^2 \gtrsim 0.015$ (e.g. Walker et al. 1991). Coupled to the present estimates of Ω_0 this implies that a majority of the universe consists of non-baryonic matter; in our fiducial model there is about ten times as much matter as there are baryons, the rest must be some sort of exotic form of matter (e.g. Trimble 1987; Kolb & Turner 1990).

With these ingredients it became possible to construct a thermal history of the universe. For the purposes of evolution of gravitational perturbations this can be divided into three (e.g. Padmanabhan 1993)

The radiation dominated era. During this era the radiation dominates the dynamics of the expansion and both baryonic and non-baryonic matter follow the evolution of the radiation field. Perturbations in the radiation field are oscillatory and perturbations in matter do not grow during this epoch.

Matter domination At $z = z_{\text{eq}} \approx 2.4 \times 10^4 \Omega_0 h^2$ the energy density in matter equals that of the radiation signalling the start of the matter dominated era. Baryonic matter will however remain coupled to the radiation as long as the cosmic plasma is ionised. As I mentioned above the majority of matter is however of a non-baryonic form and can start to collapse at z_{eq} .

Recombination The final stage is when baryonic matter recombines and finally decouples from the radiation field. This actually happens at a fairly well-defined redshift; regardless of cosmological model the optical depth of the universe is unity at $z \approx 1065$ (Jones & Wyse 1985). This is the surface of last scattering and is where the microwave background radiation originates. After this epoch the baryons will fall into the dark matter perturbations and galaxy formation can ensue.

The exact evolution depends on the type of (non-baryonic) dark matter assumed. If the dark matter was highly relativistic when it decoupled from the radiation field (Hot Dark Matter, HDM), it will stream out of small perturbations and all structure on small scales will be erased. The opposite extreme is Cold Dark Matter (CDM) where there is structure on all scales. The pure HDM models were appealing because they postulated a non-zero mass for a known particle, the neutrino, but numerical simulations in the early 1980s showed that the HDM model has too little power³ on small scales to reproduce the observed galaxy distribution. Emphasis therefore turned to simulations of CDM models and the early success of these simulations (performed for $\Omega_0 = 1$) in describing the overall features of the galaxy distribution (e.g. Blumenthal et al. 1984; Davis et al. 1985; Frenk et al. 1985) helped make the $\Omega_0 = 1$, $h = 0.5$ CDM model dominate theoretical work for nearly a decade. With the current data against $\Omega_0 = 1$ this has been replaced with models close to our fiducial models (see Bertschinger 1998 for a review).

³I here use power in the Fourier sense, if one transforms the density contrast, δ , into its Fourier components, δ_k , the power spectrum is given by

$$P(k) = \langle |\delta_k|^2 \rangle, \quad (1.4)$$

and where as usual $k = 2\pi/\lambda$, where λ is the real-space wavelength.

1.4 Formation and evolution of galaxies

The numerical simulations described above primarily studied non-baryonic dark matter, but galaxies consist of stars, and the formation and evolution of galaxies are closely connected to that of their constituent stars. The theory of stellar evolution developed in the 1950s (see [Kippenhahn & Weigert 1990](#); [Tayler 1994](#)) allowed cosmologists to make quantitative statements about the importance of evolution on cosmological observations (see below), but the formation of stars is a difficult subject and even today the formation of stars on galactic scales is poorly understood (e.g. [Silk 1997](#)). The details of formation can be ignored however, if one has a reasonably robust recipe for specifying the birthrate and mass distribution of stars.

1.4.1 The IMF

[Salpeter \(1955\)](#) introduced the concept of the “original” mass function, which today is known as the initial mass function (IMF), and showed that the available data in the solar neighbourhood were well fit by

$$\frac{dN}{dM} = aM^{-1.35}, \quad (1.5)$$

where M is the mass of the star and dN/dM give the number of stars born with a given mass M . It is to be interpreted in a probabilistic way, and a lower and upper mass cut-off have to be adopted. More recent determinations of the IMF favours a change in slope at the low-mass end and differ somewhat from the Salpeter function. [Scalo \(1986\)](#) reviewed the determinations of the IMF in the solar neighbourhood and presented the so-called Scalo-IMF as a best fit model to the data. The very existence of a universal IMF has however been cast into doubt by recent diversity in the determination of the IMF in different environments and [Scalo \(1998\)](#) argues for a variation in IMFs, but presents an alternative “best” IMF, in good agreement with the determination of the IMF from M dwarfs with HST ([Gould et al. 1996](#)). [Figure 1.1](#) shows the difference between four different determinations of the solar-neighbourhood IMF, the three mentioned above and the [Miller & Scalo \(1979\)](#) IMF.

All the IMFs in the figure are normalised to $1M_{\odot}$ total mass, so two points worthy of note from the plot are that: a) the *number* of stars per solar mass is higher for the Salpeter function than for any other IMF since it rises steeply down to $0.1M_{\odot}$; and b) the “new” Scalo IMF and the Salpeter IMF have the largest number of high mass stars. Since different IMFs give different calibrations of star formation rates and different mass estimates, the choice of IMF is important. Unfortunately there is no good understanding of the IMF outside the solar neighbourhood and in this work I will use a Salpeter IMF since it seems to fit the data as well as anything ([Kennicutt 1998b](#)).

FIGURE 1.1: A comparison of four different determinations of the solar-neighbourhood IMF. The quantity plotted is $dN/d\log M$ and all functions are normalised to $1M_{\odot}$ between $M = 0.1M_{\odot}$ and $M = 125M_{\odot}$.

1.4.2 Evolutionary models

The early attempts at using the results of stellar evolution on galactic scales focussed on estimating the effect of evolution on the determination of cosmological parameters, in particular the deceleration parameter, q_0 , (Humason et al. 1956; Sandage 1961b), the effect of evolution was therefore regarded as a mere correction factor and not interesting in its own right. Some of the reason for this was no doubt the crude models existing in the end of the 1950s and early 1960s. This changed during the 1960s when population synthesis models were developed (e.g. Partridge & Peebles 1967; Tinsley 1968). These models took observed spectral energy distributions for stars and combined them with evolutionary tracks for stars, an IMF and a star formation history to provide estimates of the evolving spectra of galaxies (Tinsley 1972b; Bruzual 1983). The incorporation of these evolutionary models into cosmological calculations made it possible to give more robust estimates of the effect of evolution on the estimation of cosmological parameters (Tinsley 1972a; Solheim & Tinsley 1972; Tinsley 1980), but they were also used to study the properties of young galaxies (e.g. Partridge & Peebles 1967) and to understand the colours of peculiar and merging galaxies (Larson & Tinsley 1978).

An important recent development has been the isochrone synthesis approach (Charlot & Bruzual 1991) which calculates evolutionary tracks for a population of stars with zero age-spread, a single stellar population (SSP). The properties of an object with a given star formation rate can then be calculated with a convolution integral (e.g. Bruzual & Charlot 1993; Worthey

1994; Poggianti 1997; Jimenez et al. 1998). Charlot et al. (1996) show that these models agree fairly well and in Chapter 6 I will adopt the models of Bruzual & Charlot (BC96, in preparation 1999⁴).

1.4.3 Modelling galaxy formation

Already before evolutionary models had been developed in detail, an influential study of the formation of our own galaxy was published by Eggen et al. (1962, ELS). These authors had a sample of stars with kinematic information and “ultraviolet excesses” — closely correlated with metallicity, and used this to argue that the galaxy had formed during a rapid collapse of a protogalactic cloud. This view of the formation of the Milky Way has proved very influential and surprisingly long-lived (see Gilmore 1989; Sandage & Bedke 1994).

Going into the 1970s most work on galaxy formation assumed that galaxies formed through the collapse of large protogalactic clouds and much effort went into understanding the cooling and fragmentation of such clouds (Silk 1977; Rees & Ostriker 1977; Binney 1977). There was one missing piece to the puzzle left to discover however — the existence of large amounts of “dark matter” in spiral galaxies. Although one had long known that clusters of galaxies have large mass-to-light ratios (Zwicky 1937), the majority of the work on spiral galaxies assumed that the mass was tracing light so a steep drop in light density implied a similar drop in mass density. The evidence against this mounted throughout the early 1970s (Rubin & Ford 1970; Freeman 1970) and in 1973 Ostriker & Peebles provided theoretical support for the dark matter argument by showing that a massive unseen halo was required to keep a cold disk stable. This was followed by two studies of the mass distribution of spiral galaxies, showing clear indications of a flat rotation curve at large radii (Ostriker et al. 1974; Einasto et al. 1974), but the strongest evidence came from HI, and Roberts (1975, his Figure 1) presented a striking illustration of the powers of HI compared to optical rotation curves. The discussion related to this paper also showed that many were ready to accept the data, and by the time of the review by Faber & Gallagher (1979), the existence of massive dark halos was generally accepted.

The theorists embraced the idea rather quickly, although it did not get a lot of emphasis in Gott’s (1977) early review, but in a classical paper White & Rees (1978) showed how dissipational collapse of gas in a massive dark halo could explain a number of properties of galaxies, notably their maximum luminosity and the shape of the luminosity function. The descendants of this work are of importance for this work and I will return to review the work on analytic models of spiral formation in Chapter 6.

One of the most influential aspects of the White & Rees model was perhaps the use of the Press-Schechter (PS, Press & Schechter 1974) formalism for gravitational collapse. The PS formula is a prescription for the number of halos of a given mass in an expanding universe evolving under the effect of gravity, and was justified partially by comparisons with numerical N -body simulations. The PS formula was extensively used in work on galaxy formation, but in the late 1980s and early 1990s a more refined semi-analytic technique

⁴This follows standard notation although some authors use BC99 for the same package

combining numerical simulations and analytical prescriptions for cooling and star formation was developed (Cole & Kaiser 1988; Cole 1991; White & Frenk 1991; Lacey & Silk 1991). These early studies were exploratory in nature, but were able to reproduce an encouraging number of features of the galaxy population, although they all found a faint-end slope of the luminosity function that was too steep compared with the observed value (reviewed in Chapter 4).

Cole (1991) used a Monte-Carlo technique to construct merger histories for halos, and this approach was extended by several authors (Lacey & Cole 1993, 1994; Kauffmann & White 1993) and used to construct extensive models of galaxy formation and evolution by Kauffmann et al. (1993) and Cole et al. (1994a). These models are all similar in that they use some sort of Monte-Carlo method to construct merger histories of dark halos. The dark halos are assigned spins consistent with numerical simulations and inside these dark halos baryonic matter is supposed to collapse and form galaxies with some ad hoc prescription for star formation and feedback. The resulting star formation history is fed into a spectral synthesis code, similar to those described above, giving observed properties of galaxies. Recent models of this type have been used to discuss the properties of high-redshift Lyman break galaxies (Baugh et al. 1998; Somerville et al. 1998), the properties of galaxies with different morphology (Baugh et al. 1996; Kauffmann 1996b) and the clustering properties of galaxies (Kauffmann et al. 1999; Baugh et al. 1999; Benson et al. 1999).

The semi-analytic models are appealing since they have the ability to identify the physical processes responsible for specific trends in the galaxy population. In the view of the complexities of observational studies, another, perhaps even more salient property of these models is their ability to treat selection criteria in a rigorous manner when comparing to observations. The main disadvantage of these models is their complexity and consequent opaqueness for outsiders. It is therefore difficult to decide to what degree how falsifiable they are. I will return to this topic in Chapter 4.

1.5 Constraining models — the quest for $N(z)$

The early observations of galaxies were, as mentioned earlier, mostly aimed at determining the overall structure of the universe. Early on, however, it was clear that classical tests such as the number-magnitude relation and number-redshift relation were fairly insensitive to the values of Ω_0 and λ_0 (Sandage 1961a) and it became clear that these instead provided promising probes into the evolutionary properties of the galaxies (e.g. Tinsley 1972a). This change in emphasis from determining cosmological parameters to understanding galaxy evolution is illustrated in Figure 1.2 which shows the fractional number of papers in ApJ and AJ that contains the words “galaxy evolution” in the abstract and/or keywords versus the year of publication. The figure is based on data from ADS, and is not complete before 1975; hence there is no rapid early rise. The dotted line in the figure is the same for “cosmological parameter”, and the relative importance of the two is shown in the inset diagram. This dramatically illustrates the relative importance of these two research areas in the early '70s. But it is evident that by the middle of the decade, the emphasis was firmly on the evolution

of galaxies.

Disentangling the evolutionary and cosmological effects proved difficult and better and larger and deeper datasets were sought. A major advance was the introduction of plate-measuring machines in the mid-1970s (e.g. [Kron 1980](#); [Ellis 1980](#)). This allowed number counts of galaxies to be carried out much more efficiently than before. The most notable finding was perhaps the discovery that at faint B -magnitudes, galaxies tended to be very blue and present in larger numbers than expected from the local data ([Kron 1980](#)). This was early interpreted to be a signal of evolution in the galaxy population ([Kron 1980](#); [Bruzual & Kron 1980](#); [Tinsley 1980](#)), but the nature of these “faint blue galaxies” was the centre of much speculation throughout the next decade.

The next major advance in the observational field was the advent of Charged Coupled Devices (CCDs). Much more sensitive than photographic plates, they also have the advantage of being linear in their response to incoming photons over a large dynamical range. The first faint galaxy counts were reported by [Hall & Mackay \(1984\)](#) and CCDs gradually started replacing photographic plates for faint work ([Tyson 1988](#); [Lilly et al. 1991](#)). For bright galaxies most of the work continued to be done using photographic plates and plate measuring machines. The largest of these surveys, the APM survey ([Maddox et al. 1990a](#)), produced galaxy counts to $B \sim 16$ and found indications of a remarkably strong evolution at low redshift ([Maddox et al. 1990b](#)). It became clear that by $B \sim 24$, the counts were in excess of the no-evolution predictions by a factor of at least 3–5, or more if the predictions were normalised to the bright end of the APM counts, but the K -band counts were fairly well described by a no-evolution model ([Lilly et al. 1991](#)). With no knowledge of the redshifts of these faint galaxies, the simplest assumption was to assume that the excess blue counts were caused by luminosity evolution of galaxies, i.e. that present day galaxies were significantly brighter in the past. This would imply that a high redshift tail would be found in the redshift distribution of faint galaxies.

The development of new multi-object spectrographs on 4m class telescopes made it possible to undertake the large, systematic redshift surveys that were required to test such predictions. [Broadhurst et al. \(1988\)](#) were the first to present the results of such a survey and surprisingly enough they did *not* find the tail of high redshift galaxies predicted by the pure luminosity evolution models. Instead, the redshift distribution was quite close to the no-evolution prediction, and this led [Broadhurst et al. \(1988\)](#) to postulate luminosity dependent luminosity evolution. This was followed by a series of three papers by [Colless et al. \(1990, 1991, 1993\)](#), who extended the work of [Broadhurst et al.](#) to $B = 22.5$ and $z < 0.7$. They confirmed the findings of the latter, and in [Colless et al. \(1993\)](#) they showed that redshift incompleteness was not the reason for the lack of a high redshift tail.

Several theoretical models were invented to explain these results. [Broadhurst et al.](#) explained their results in terms of a large population of star-bursting dwarf galaxies at higher redshift. The additional blue luminosity caused by the star-burst would bring them inside the selection criterion at high redshift, but they would fade rapidly and be too faint at low redshift, hence the steep number counts in the B -band. These or similar bursting-dwarf models were pursued further by several authors ([Lacey & Silk 1991](#); [Cole et al. 1992](#); [Babul & Rees 1992](#); [Babul & Ferguson 1996](#); [Phillipps & Driver 1995](#)) and gave a good fit

FIGURE 1.2: The fraction of papers in *ApJ* and *AJ* containing the words "galaxy evolution" or a synonym of this, as a function of time. Various historical events are indicated on the figure, note in particular the rapid rise after the HDF was released. The dotted line shows the same, but for the words "cosmological parameters", and the inset diagram shows the two relative to each other. This figure was made using the Astrophysics Data System (ADS), and the drop around 1975 is because not all abstracts are searchable before this time.

to number counts and redshift distributions, but I will show that they predict too low redshifts for the blue galaxies in Chapter 4.

An alternative explanation invoked substantial merging of galaxies, first modelled by Rocca-Volmerange & Guiderdoni (1990). The large amount of merging was later postulated by Cowie et al. (1991) to explain the combination of an overabundance of blue galaxies at faint blue magnitudes, no sign of such overabundance in the K -band and redshift distributions consistent with no-evolution predictions and a refined model was presented by Broadhurst et al. (1992). This was the state of the field at the time of the review by Koo & Kron (1992), who examined all the evidence and concluded that both models and observations were too uncertain to justify any strong claims about the evolution of these galaxies.

Since then the increased sensitivity of CCDs has allowed number counts to be made to increasingly faint limits, $B \approx 27.5$ (Metcalf et al. 1995), $R \sim 27$, (Smail et al. 1995), $K > 22$ (Gardner et al. 1993; Djorgovski et al. 1995; Moustakas et al. 1997), and improved spectrographs such as LDSS-2 on the WHT and LRIS on Keck have allowed redshift surveys to extend to fainter limits such as those published by Lilly et al. (1995a) ($I_{AB} < 22.5$), Ellis et al. (1996) ($b_J < 24.0$), Cowie et al. (1996) ($K < 20$), Cowie et al. (1997) ($B < 24.5$) and Cohen et al. (1999b) ($K < 20$) among others.

These surveys did however mix up different types of galaxies and it became very interesting to see if there were any differences in the morphological properties of galaxies at high redshift. The refurbishment of the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) in 1993 made this possible. Several groups obtained deep exposures of field galaxies and performed number-magnitude counts. The most striking result of these observations was that there was a large number of peculiar/irregular galaxies at faint magnitudes (Driver et al. 1995; Driver et al. 1995; Glazebrook et al. 1995; Driver et al. 1996a). This trend was found to be even more striking in the Hubble Deep Field images (Williams et al. 1996; Abraham et al. 1996a), and it was tempting to identify these galaxies with the excess of blue galaxies, but this required the combination of spectroscopic information with HST images.

1.6 An outline of the thesis

The main reason for the slow progress in combining HST imaging and spectroscopic observations is that a typical multi-object spectrograph on a 4m class telescope has about 8 arcmin field of view, in other words about 10 times the area of a HST pointing. This mismatch has meant that substantial observational effort has been needed to combine HST imaging and spectroscopic data. The best way to proceed is to obtain HST exposures of areas coincident with redshift surveys, but this requires large amounts of observing time. In this thesis I try to put constraints on the evolution of galaxies from $z = 1$ to $z = 0$ using such an approach. The primary basis for this study is a large sample of galaxies with known redshifts and HST images. This dataset will be introduced and calibrated in detail in Chapter 2.

One of the aims with this dataset is to look at morphological changes in the galaxy

population and at the properties of different morphological types. This leads one to consider the question of how to obtain secure and robust measurements of the morphology of a galaxy. This is a topic which will be dealt with in detail in Chapter 3 and it will be shown there that galaxy classifications made by eye or by a computer algorithm are both reasonably robust.

After the morphological classifications have been assembled, I turn to the question of the evolution of the different morphological types in Chapter 4. The aim of this chapter is to determine the evolutionary properties of different morphological types to see if there is clear evidence for morphological transformations between different classes of galaxies. To do this I will pay particular attention to the redshift distributions, luminosity functions and star formation characteristics of the different morphological types and I will try to constrain their evolution. In particular I try to determine how “peculiar” galaxies fit into the puzzle, whether they are indeed bursting dwarfs and what their physical nature is, but it turns out that the data I have are insufficient to say what the nature of these galaxies is.

To answer this I will use near infra-red data, and the observations are described in Chapter 5. It also proves convenient to extend the sample to improve statistics. This extended sample is analysed in Chapter 6. The main development here is that with the near-IR data it is possible to constrain the masses of the galaxies, something which simplifies the interpretation of the data greatly. It will therefore be possible to ask what the evolution of galaxies of different mass is, whether all galaxies form a similar fraction of their stars between $z = 1$ and the present, and whether there are signs of mass-dependent luminosity evolution?

These questions will be addressed using the mass-function, the mass-density function and the overall mass-distribution in the universe as a function of redshift. This turns out to indicate that spiral galaxies possibly are transformed to elliptical galaxies and I therefore discuss the properties of the spiral galaxies in some detail before returning to the star formation characteristics of the sample — now armed with a knowledge of the masses of the galaxies. Finally I will summarise the results of the thesis and indicate possible future directions of research.

Chapter 2

The ground based catalogues and HST observations

We saw in the introduction that adding the spatial information from HST to the spectral information from a redshift survey is a very promising direction of research. This chapter will introduce the dataset used throughout this thesis to follow such a path of investigation.

The chapter is divided into three parts. The first part is concerned with a review of the relevant ground based data, which is taken from a set of different ground-based surveys: The LDSS-1 (Colless et al. 1990, 1991, 1993), LDSS-2 (Glazebrook et al. 1995), Autofib (Ellis et al. 1996; Heyl et al. 1997) and CFRS (Lilly et al. 1995a; Crampton et al. 1995) redshift surveys. The LDSS-1, LDSS-2 and Autofib surveys, all selected in the *B*-band, will be discussed separately from the the CFRS, selected in the *I*-band. The surveys and various basic quantities associated with them are summarised in Table 2.1.

The second part of the chapter describes the HST observations performed, the identification and extraction of images, and the photometry done on the relevant objects. The degree to which a survey is well-suited for HST follow-up depends on the selection criteria and exposure time required. This varies considerably between the surveys considered here, and to illustrate this the last column in Table 2.1 shows the number of objects one would expect to find in one HST frame with the given selection criteria. The numbers are calculated using the number counts from Metcalfe et al. (1995) for the *B*-selected surveys and Tyson (1988) for the CFRS. These calculations assume a one-in-one sampling i.e. that all galaxies within the selection criteria are targeted spectroscopically; for the CFRS this is more like 1 in 5 on larger scales, thus the numbers for the CFRS are over-estimated in the mean. Regardless of the details, this shows that LDSS-2 and CFRS are the most suited for HST follow-up. And if the quoted CFRS sampling of 22.4% (Le Fèvre et al. 1995) is used the CFRS and LDSS-2 are expected to give very similar numbers of galaxies per HST frame.

The last part of this chapter details how the data from the first two parts are combined to form a final well-defined sample of galaxies with HST imaging and spectroscopic information. This involves combining the *I* and *B* selected surveys, their notation and their magni-

TABLE 2.1: *Basic information about the ground based surveys used in this thesis.*

Survey	Selection	N_{gal}	Med(z)	Completeness	Expected per HST field ^a
LDSS-1a	$21 \leq b_J \leq 22.5$	105	0.317	81%	2.1 ^b
LDSS-1b	$22.5 \leq b_J \leq 23.5^c$	6	0.267	57%	2.1 ^b
LDSS-1c	$21 \leq b_J \leq 22.5^d$	51	0.339	63% ^e	2.1 ^b
LDSS-2	$22.5 \leq B \leq 24$	96	0.454	73%	9.7
Autofib-bright	$17.0 \leq b_J \leq 20.0$	546	0.208	71%	0.18
Autofib-faint	$19.5 \leq b_J \leq 22.0$	479	0.110	81%	1.4
CFRS	$17.5 \leq I(AB) \leq 22.5$	741 ^f	0.564	85%	43

^a Based on the magnitude limits for the survey.

^b This number is based on the selection criteria for LDSS-1a

^c In addition the objects were selected to be compact, and finally some objects were re-observations of targets in LDSS-1a.

^d This survey was really composed of two separate surveys, an extension to the LDSS-1a survey and a survey of faint blue objects selected to have $22 < R < 23$, following a set of priorities detailed in the paper.

^e The extension to the LDSS-1a survey has a completeness of 72.5%, and the survey of faint blue objects has a completeness of 57.9%.

^f This includes the Groth strip extension (see text).

tude measurements, as well as comparing the properties of this subsample with the parent catalogue to ascertain whether or not the sample of galaxies with HST imaging form a fair subsample of their parent populations. This has to be done carefully to determine whether the selection of fields to target with HST has lead to any additional selection biases. In what follows, such selection of subsets of a sample will be referred to as a secondary selection criterion.

2.1 The LDSS/Autofib redshift surveys

The LDSS and Autofib redshift surveys are a collection of essentially three b_J selected redshift surveys. They have earlier been combined in the Autofib survey (Ellis et al. 1996), which despite its name does include both the Autofib redshift survey and the LDSS-1 and LDSS-2 redshift survey, as well as the DARS (Peterson et al. 1986) and BES (Broadhurst et al. 1988) redshift surveys. Since there are no BES or DARS objects with HST imaging, we will however not discuss these further. The work described in this section is an independent assembly of these results, together with some additional LDSS-1 objects.

The goal of this section is to review the different methods for measuring magnitudes used in these papers, and align the various notations used in the surveys. Throughout this thesis these surveys will be referred to collectively as the LDSS surveys. The choice to use a different name for the collected data from Ellis et al. (1996) was based on the fact that

TABLE 2.2: *Objects observed more than once in the LDSS redshift surveys.*

First occurrence	Other	Comments
LDSS-1b — 10.2.09	LDSS-2 — 10.23.222	$z = 1.999$ in LDSS-2, $z = 2.014$ in LDSS-1. The (α, δ) for the two objects are slightly different, and no overlap is noted in the papers. There are no other compact objects nearby.
LDSS-1b — 10.4.01	LDSS-1c — 10.4.26	Not noted as a re-observation in Colless et al. 1993, and the redshifts are slightly different with $z = 0.320$ in LDSS-1b and $z = 0.323$ in LDSS-1c.
LDSS-1a — 10.2.6	LDSS-1b — 10.2.03	
LDSS-1a — 10.2.8	LDSS-1b — 10.2.04	
LDSS-1b — 10.2.15	LDSS-2 — 10.23.332	Published (α, δ) slightly different.
LDSS-1a — 10.4.2	LDSS-1b — 10.4.03	
LDSS-1b — 10.4.05	LDSS-1c — 10.4.6	
LDSS-1a — 10.4.7	LDSS-1b — 10.4.06	
LDSS-1a — 10.4.8	LDSS-1b — 10.4.07	
LDSS-1b — 13.2.05	LDSS-1c — 13.2.25	
LDSS-1a — 13.2.6	LDSS-1b — 13.2.06	

the dataset used herein is somewhat different from the dataset discussed there, and the most dominant survey in the data presented here is the LDSS-2 survey rather than the Autofib redshift survey.

2.1.1 The LDSS-1 survey

The original LDSS-1 survey (Colless et al. 1990) was carried out using the Low Dispersion Survey Spectrograph (LDSS) on the Anglo Australian Telescope (AAT). This was later extended in a survey mainly targeting compact objects (Colless et al. 1991) and finally the original survey was re-observed and made more complete, along with further observations of blue galaxies with $22 < R < 23$, in Colless et al. (1993). In the following we will mostly refer to these collectively as LDSS-1, but when necessary we will refer to the individual surveys as LDSS-1a, LDSS-1b, LDSS-1c. The three surveys have somewhat different selection criteria and some objects overlap between the surveys. The overlap between the different surveys is summarised in Table 2.2 for reference. This information is otherwise only available through detailed comparison of the papers.

LDSS-1 magnitudes were measured from photographic plates, calibrated with CCD data (Colless et al. 1990). “Total” magnitudes (following Kron 1980, see Appendix A) were measured in b_J and r_F ; the calibration procedure is detailed in Jones et al. (1991). Three points had to be dealt with in order to join this survey with the CFRS and LDSS-2 surveys described below. Firstly, the magnitude measurements and systems had to be

aligned; this is detailed later in Section 2.5. Secondly, the notation for the quality of the redshift determination had to be standardised. We use the notation from LDSS-1a and LDSS-1c practically unchanged, so that

- Q=1 — Reliable identification, based on more than one feature
- Q=2 — Redshift based on one spectral feature
- Q=3 — No identification possible
- Q=4/5 — No spectrum/failure
- Q=-1 — No quality indication given in paper

For LDSS-1b a different notation was used. This has been translated so that spectral ids that are given as *M-star*, *qso*, *elg* or *gal* in the paper are assigned a quality of Q=1, spectral ids of *star* or *em?* are given quality Q=2, spectral ids *???* are given Q=3 and missing spectra are given Q=5.

The third transformation that had to be done was to transform magnitudes in LDSS-1c back to b_J and r_F , this is done using the inverse of the transforms given in the paper:

$$\begin{aligned} b_J &= B - 0.147(B - R) \\ r_F &= R - 0.064(B - R) \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

2.1.2 The LDSS-2 redshift survey

The LDSS-2 survey is the b_J -selected survey that is best matched to the HST area as can be seen from Table 2.1. It is therefore reasonable to use this survey as the reference survey for the LDSS surveys and align the others to this.

The LDSS-2 study suffered from poor weather on one run which meant that their spectroscopy was less deep for the fields targeted on that run. They subsequently determined that a selection criterion of $22.5 \leq B \leq 23.3$ for the 13hr objects gave a uniform 70% completeness limit for the survey (Glazebrook et al. 1995, see also Table 2.5)

As described in Glazebrook et al. (1995), R and B magnitudes were obtained from CCD images using 4-arcsec diameter apertures corrected to total magnitudes using an aperture correction of ~ -0.3 . The magnitude system is close to b_J and r_F , and was kept in the CCD system (Glazebrook, private communication). The quality indicators used in the LDSS-2 paper were more or less identical to the ones used in the LDSS-1 survey described above.

2.1.3 The Autofib redshift survey

The Autofib redshift survey is detailed in the first Autofib paper (Ellis et al. 1996, see also the description in Cole et al. 1994b). It is a b_J selected survey, based on COSMOS measuring-machine scans of UK Schmidt plates. The spectroscopic work was carried out using the Autofib multi-object fibre-spectrograph on the AAT (Parry & Sharples 1988).

A notable feature of this survey is that the k -corrections were determined by cross-correlating the spectra with a set of template spectra (Heyl et al. 1997; Ellis et al. 1996,

see also below). The magnitude system is the colour-corrected photographic b_J , and the magnitudes are effectively total magnitudes, similar to LDSS-1. There is in general no colour information available for the galaxies in this survey from ground-based photometry.

2.2 The Canada-France Redshift Survey

The Canada-France Redshift Survey (CFRS) consists of what was at the time of publication an unprecedentedly large sample of faint galaxies, selected according to isophotal I magnitude, $17.5 \leq I_{AB} \leq 22.5$. In total 1010 such objects were selected for spectroscopic follow-up using MARLIN and later the MOS-SIS spectrographs on the CFHT. After a careful re-measurement of the photometry, 67 of these were later found to have magnitudes fainter than $I_{AB} = 22.5$, these were placed in a supplementary catalogue. In total this gives 943 objects in the full catalogue, 591 of which have secure redshifts (Crampton et al. 1995). After the allocation of HST time, the LDSS and CFRS groups decided to extend this survey in the Groth strip (see below), for which supplementary spectroscopy of 59 objects was obtained to a magnitude limit identical to that adopted for the main CFRS survey, using LDSS-2 on the 4.2m William Herschel Telescope (Tresse & Glazebrook unpublished).

The CFRS group adopted the following system to indicate the quality of the redshift determination (Le Fèvre et al. 1995, see also Crampton et al. 1995):

- Class 0 — Redshift completely unknown.
- Class 1 — Tentative redshift determined, with an estimated confidence of $\sim 50\%$.
- Class 2 — Good redshift determined with an estimated confidence of $\sim 80\%$
- Class 3 — Very good redshift determination with a confidence level $> 95\%$.
- Class 4 — 100% certain redshift supported by many features.
- Class 8 — Redshift based on one emission line identified as $[\text{OII}](\lambda 3727)$
based on the shape of the continuum
- Class 9 — Redshift based on one emission line tentatively identified with $[\text{OII}]$.
- Class $1n$ — Similar to n , but for quasars
- Class $9n$ — Similar to n but for objects in the supplementary catalogue

2.2.1 Magnitude measurements

The CFRS group measured I -band isophotal and $3''$ aperture magnitudes for all the galaxies in their survey and selected objects based on their I -band isophotal magnitudes. In addition all objects have $3''$ aperture photometry in V and a subset also in B and/or K . The CFRS group quote their results in the AB magnitude system (see Appendix A), and we will convert all our magnitudes to AB in what follows. For reference the following transformations were

adopted by [Lilly et al. \(1995a\)](#)

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{AB} &= B - 0.17 \\
 V_{AB} &= V \\
 I_{AB} &= I + 0.48 \\
 K'_{AB} &= K' + 1.78
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.2}$$

In general the shift is given by (eg. [Fukugita et al. 1995](#))

$$AB = 2.5 \log \frac{\int R(\nu) f_{\nu} d\nu / \nu}{\int R(\nu) d\nu}
 \tag{2.3}$$

2.3 HST observations and image analysis

Upon completion of the CFRS and LDSS redshift surveys, both the CFRS and LDSS teams independently sought HST WFPC2 time in Cycle 4. Early results of these efforts were described by [Schade et al. \(1995\)](#) and [Ellis \(1995\)](#). From 1994 the two teams agreed to merge their efforts, and further allocation of HST time to the combined team were made in Cycle 5 and Cycle 6.

In Cycle 4, prior to the merged effort, the strategy adopted by the two teams was somewhat different. Although both teams sought F814W imaging for morphological classifications, the CFRS team chose to supplement these images with ones in F450W whereas the LDSS team explored the visibility of their b_J -selected samples in F336W and F218W. Only in Cycle 5 and 6 did a common strategy emerge based on F814W images augmented by F450W images for a subset of the targets.

Table 2.3 summaries the HST survey data obtained for this analysis. The total dataset consists 25 WFPC-2 HST frames. Six fields are drawn from the contiguous ‘Groth strip’ ([Groth et al. 1994](#)) imaged by WFPC-2, in addition we have used the much deeper Westphal field image to check our photometry (see below), this field is completely covered by other images and is not used for anything else in this thesis. Galaxies have only been included in the final catalogue if they have been spectroscopically targeted in either the LDSS or CFRS/Groth strip surveys.

2.3.1 Identification and extraction of objects

The identification of the ground based targets was simplified by the existence of World Coordinate System (WCS, see [Greisen & Calabretta 1995, 1993](#)) header information in the HST images. This WCS information was utilised to transform lists of RA and Dec for all potential galaxies to pixel coordinates for the given image using the `iraf`-routine `wcsctran`. This gave a list of estimated pixel coordinates for each object. This list could be compared with the image and the match could be assessed by eye. It was generally found that the HST coordinate system agreed well with the ground based system, but there was a shift between the astrometric system defined in the HST headers and the system used by

TABLE 2.3: *HST* Imaging Survey

Field ^a	Red filter	Integration time (s)	NCOMB ^b	Blue filter	Integration time (s)	NCOMB ^b	N_{targets}^c	N_z^d	N_{star}^e
cfrs_03_1	F814W	6700	5	14	13	0
cfrs_03_2	F814W	6700	5	15	14	0
cfrs_03_3	F814W	6700	5	13	10	0
cfrs_03_4	F814W	6400	6	F450W	6600	6	11	11	0
cfrs_03_5	F814W	6400	6	F450W	6600	6	5	5	0
cfrs_10_1	F814W	6700	5	17	16	1
cfrs_10_2	F814W	6700	5	12	11	1
cfrs_10_3	F814W	5303	4	24	20	2
cfrs_14_1	F814W	7400	6	F450W	7800	6	21	21	0
cfrs_14_2	F814W	7400	6	F450W	7800	6	13	10	3
cfrs_22_1	F814W	6700	5	8	7	0
cfrs_22_2	F814W	6700	5	14	12	0
cfrs_22_3	F814W	6700	5	15	13	1
grth_14_1	F814W	4400	4	F606W	2800	4	36	31	4
grth_14_2	F814W	4400	4	F606W	2800	4	16	12	4
grth_14_3	F814W	4400	4	F606W	2800	4	21	17	1
grth_14_4	F814W	7400	6	F450W	7800	6	20	20	0
grth_14_5	F814W	4400	4	F606W	2800	4	18	14	3
grth_14_6	F814W	4400	4	F606W	2800	4	11	10	1
ldss_10a	F814W	5800	5	F380W	6000	6	13	10	1
ldss_10b	F814W	5800	5	F380W	6000	6	18	13	2
ldss_10c	F814W	5800	5	F218W	6000	6	10	7	2
ldss_13a	F814W	5800	5	F380W	6000	6	13	6	2
ldss_13b	F814W	5800	5	F380W	6000	6	21	15	1
ldss_13c	F814W	5800	5	F380W	6000	6	15	8	2
Total ^f						341	269	44	28

^a cfrs_03=CFRS 3^h field, grth_14=Groth 14^h field, ldss_10a=LDSS-2 10^h.

^b The number of individual exposures combined to form the final image

^c The number of spectroscopic targets in the field

^d The number of objects with reliable redshift measurement (note > 1)

^e The number of stars

^f There is some overlap between the different frames so the total is not the sum of the columns

FIGURE 2.1: *The identification of LDSS1, LDSS2 and Autofib objects in the 10A field. Left: The ground based coordinates transformed to HST pixel coordinates. Right: The matching achieved after applying a simple pixel shift on the positions in the left frame (still shown as unlabelled circles)*

the CFRS that typically amounted to ~ 20 pixels for the WFC chips. This shift presented no problem, and could be determined by inspection. A typical example of the process is shown in Figure 2.1, where the top figure shows the calculated positions of objects based on the ground based RA & Dec, and the bottom shows the results after applying suitable shifts. The CFRS objects were independently identified and extracted by David Schade and myself, the LDSS objects only by myself.

After all CFRS/LDSS/Groth strip objects were successfully identified on the HST images, postage-stamp images of the objects were extracted. It was decided to extract 101×101 pixel stamps for objects on a WFC chip, and 201×201 stamps for objects on the PC. Some nearby objects were too large to be fully contained within these stamps; for these larger stamps were extracted manually. Each stamp was finally given a FITS header with the most important information about each object, such as redshift, absolute magnitude, origin and the apparent magnitude of the object.

This process resulted in a catalogue of 378 objects for which there had been ground based spectroscopic observations and HST imaging. Finally, every image was inspected by eye to weed out any objects for which cosmic defects rendered the images useless for accurate morphological analysis. It was also necessary to remove objects that were partially or completely obscured by the edges of the WFPC chip. This removed 37 objects in total.

The effective area of the HST sample is not equal to the sum of the areas of the HST fields because of overlaps between images. A careful calculation of overlaps and completeness yields the numbers given in Table 2.4. The geometric completeness for each field, defined as the number of objects targeted spectroscopically divided by the number of objects within the photometric selection criteria is shown in Figure 2.2. This figure shows that the HST fields with CFRS galaxies have much higher geometric completeness than the one

TABLE 2.4: *HST Survey Completeness*

Survey	Survey limits	Completeness		Effective area ^a deg ²
		Geometric	Spectroscopic	
CFRS	$17.5 < I_{AB} < 22.5$	0.5477	90.44%	0.01377
LDSS-2 (10hr)	$22.5 < b_J < 24.0$	0.7941	85.19%	0.002513
LDSS-2 (13hr) ^b	$22.5 < b_J < 23.3$	0.4516	85.71%	0.001576

^a Defined as surveyed area times the geometric completeness

^b The LDSS-2 13hr field have less deep spectroscopy, we have adopted the completeness limits as discussed in Glazebrook et al. (1995b)

TABLE 2.5: *Statistics of the final survey*

Survey	Total number	Number with z^a	Number of stars	Unknown z
CFRS ^b	223	192	16	15
GRTH	28	25	...	3
LDSS1	22	12	3	7
LDSS2	61	43	7	11
Autofib	7	4	...	3

^a Including objects with uncertain redshifts

^b This includes objects in the supplementary catalogue — in total 10 objects

FIGURE 2.2: *The geometric completeness from field to field. The CFRS fields are shown as filled circles and the LDSS fields as open squares. For the LDSS fields, only LDSS-2 objects have been counted.*

FIGURE 2.3: *The consistency between repeat measurements of objects. The open circles refers to objects from the Westphal strip (see text). The strongly discrepant point at $F814W \sim 22.5$ is 14.0620*

quoted for the CFRS as a whole (22.4%). This is understandable since the CFRS group observed galaxies in three strips of $30'' \times 9'$ separated by $210'$, defined by the geometry of their instruments, and the HST fields are obviously chosen to intersect such strips primarily. Taking into account the size of the HST field this will roughly double the geometric completeness, consistent with Figure 2.2.

The final catalogue is summarised in Table 2.5, and combined with the effective areas in Table 2.4 this shows good agreement with the expected numbers from Table 2.1, except for LDSS-1. The LDSS-1 numbers in Table 2.1 were computed on the basis of the selection criteria in LDSS-1a, whereas both LDSS-1b and LDSS-1c have additional or wider selection criteria for subsets of their samples; if we only count the LDSS-1a objects we get 12 objects which is in excellent agreement with Table 2.1.

2.3.2 Photometry of objects

The existence of HST imaging for all galaxies in the survey, offers the possibility of obtaining a uniform photometric base for further studies. To take advantage of this, $3''$ aperture magnitudes were measured for all objects in the final catalogue, using the `phot` routine in `IraF`. In addition SExtractor (Bertin & Arnouts 1996) was used to measure “auto” magnitudes, which are similar to Kron magnitudes with the modification that an elliptical aperture is used. It is worth noting that for very nearby, large objects, the relatively small size of the

(a) The difference between ground based isophotal magnitudes and SExtractor “best” HST magnitudes for all CFRS galaxies with known redshift and HST imaging. The small dots are objects which were flagged to have uncertain photometry by SExtractor. The top panel shows the median and mean absolute deviation in bins of 25 galaxies compared to a simple estimate of the error expected from the quoted errors on the magnitudes

(b) The difference between 3'' HST magnitudes and ground based isophotal magnitudes for CFRS galaxies with $I_{AB} \geq 20.5$

FIGURE 2.4: The difference between HST and ground based magnitudes as a function of the ground based magnitude

HST fields might lead to less accurate photometry than what is achievable from the ground. This translates into a larger scatter in photometry for the brightest objects than one would naïvely expect.

The overlap between some of the fields made it possible to check the consistency of the photometric measurements. The difference between repeat observations of objects is shown in Figure 2.3. The open circles are from the Westphal field which has a total exposure time of 25200s, *i.e.* almost four times the typical exposure time for the images listed in Table 2.3. The average offset for the solid circles is < 0.01 magnitudes, whereas that for the open circles is -0.03 magnitudes. The latter gives us confidence that the total magnitudes measured this way are rather good estimates of the total magnitudes. The one large discrepancy is 14.0620, and it is not easy to see why it is so discrepant. It is classified as a star in the CFRS survey, and a change of 0.3 magnitudes over 4.6 days, which is the time between the observations, is consistent with it being a variable M star.

The photometry was subsequently compared with ground based magnitudes for the CFRS objects for which homogeneous *I*-band photometry exists. To carry out this comparison the HST magnitudes had to be transformed to the ground based system. This was achieved using the formalism in Section 2.4. The difference between the ground based isophotal magnitude and the HST magnitude so transformed is shown in Figure 2.4(a). The objects that are close to edges or which SExtractor has flagged for close neighbours are plotted as small solid circles. The agreement is good with a small shift of only 0.07 magnitudes, and a scatter slightly larger than the expected intrinsic error in the magnitudes, cf. the upper panel. The increased scatter around the mean for this difference is probably partly caused by a combination of the uncertainty in the transformation equations (typically of the order of 0.03–0.05 magnitudes), smearing of objects by seeing in the ground based magnitudes, and for the brightest objects, problems with the sky background estimation due to the small size of the HST fields.

The relation between the ground based isophotal magnitudes and the 3" aperture HST magnitudes is shown in Figure 2.4(b). This comparison is restricted to the faintest objects, since aperture magnitudes underestimate magnitudes at the bright end. It is worth noting that the correlation is very good, this will be used Chapter 6 to select objects from HST frames with similar selection criteria to the CFRS survey.

For the LDSS objects only limited ground-based *I*-band photometry exist, and only a handful of the b_J selected galaxies in the survey have existing ground-based *I*-band photometry, so no comparison is plotted here, it is only noted that the agreement is similar to the one for the CFRS galaxies.

2.4 Estimates of colours and SEDs for galaxies

We often want to convert from observed flux to rest-frame flux, corrected for universe expansion, since this simplifies subsequent analysis. If we write the flux of a galaxy between λ and $\lambda + d\lambda$ as $f(\lambda)d\lambda$ and the response function of the system as $R(\lambda)$, the observed flux

of a galaxy at $z = z_{\text{em}}$ will be

$$f_{\text{obs}} \propto \int R(\lambda) f\left(\frac{\lambda}{1+z_{\text{em}}}\right) \frac{d\lambda}{1+z_{\text{em}}}, \quad (2.4)$$

due to universe expansion assuming no intergalactic attenuation¹, whereas we are interested in the quantity

$$f_{\text{wanted}} \propto \int R(\lambda) f(\lambda) d\lambda, \quad (2.5)$$

which is the flux of the same galaxy observed through the same filter at $z = 0$, so to correct our estimates of the flux we multiply the observed flux with the ratio

$$K'(z) = \frac{f_{\text{wanted}}}{f_{\text{obs}}}. \quad (2.6)$$

The above discussion applies even if the galaxy's spectrum evolves with time (as it is expected to do), but it is customary to rewrite this equation to split it into a term independent of evolution called the k -correction, $k(z)$ and a term dependent on the evolution of the spectrum called the evolutionary correction, $E(z)$, and express the final result in magnitudes:

$$k(z) = 2.5 \log \frac{\int R(\lambda) f(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int R(\lambda) f(\lambda/(1+z_{\text{em}})) d\lambda / (1+z_{\text{em}})} \quad (2.7)$$

$$E(z) = 2.5 \log \frac{\int R(\lambda) f(\lambda/(1+z_{\text{em}}), t = t_0) d\lambda}{\int R(\lambda) f(\lambda/(1+z_{\text{em}}), t = t_{z_{\text{em}}}) d\lambda}, \quad (2.8)$$

where t_0 is the age of the galaxy at $z = 0$ and $t_{z_{\text{em}}}$ is the age of the galaxy at $z = z_{\text{em}}$ (e.g. [Yoshii & Takahara 1988](#)). These corrections go into the calculation of absolute magnitudes through

$$M = m - k(z) - 5 \log d_L(z) / 10 \text{pc} - E(z). \quad (2.9)$$

In the present discussion we will ignore the evolutionary correction, but it will be of importance later. The present discussion will concentrate on the k -correction and the estimation of it. This is plotted as a function of redshift and wavelength in Figures [2.5\(a\)](#) and [2.5\(b\)](#) respectively, where the strong dependence on galaxy type is evident. Galaxies with a strong 4000Å break in their spectrum, such as ellipticals, have larger k -corrections than flat spectrum objects.

It is clear from equation (2.7) that a good estimate of the spectral energy distributions (SEDs) of a galaxy is necessary to estimate k -corrections. This section will look at this task, and finally return to the subject of estimation of k -corrections at the end of the section.

¹For galaxies at $z < 1$, the intergalactic attenuation due to neutral hydrogen is negligible for photometry in wavebands redwards of $\lambda > Ly\alpha(1+z) > 2432\text{\AA}$ ([Madau 1995](#)), which is the case in this thesis.

(a) The k -correction as a function of redshift for the B -band (top) and the I -band (bottom)

(b) The k -correction is shown as a function of wavelength at $z = 1.0$ with the b_J and I_{CFRS} filter transmission curves overlaid

FIGURE 2.5: The k -correction as a function of wavelength and redshift.

In the coming discussion we will repeatedly have to estimate a galaxy's colours at a given redshift, using the notation above the colour of the galaxy can be written as

$$C(X, Y; z) = m_X - m_Y, \quad (2.10)$$

with

$$m_X = -2.5 \log \frac{\int X(\lambda) f(\lambda(1+z)) d\lambda / (1+z)}{\int X(\lambda) F_\lambda(\alpha \text{Lyr}) d\lambda}, \quad (2.11)$$

where $F_\lambda(\alpha \text{Lyr})$ is the SED for Vega, assuming that the normalisation chosen is Vega based (see for instance [Fukugita et al. 1995](#)).

Application of equation (2.10) again requires knowledge of a galaxy's SED. This can in theory be taken from the observed spectra, but this requires relatively high-S/N and well calibrated spectra which often render the practical use limited (see however [Crampton et al. \(1995\)](#) and [Hammer et al. \(1997\)](#) for an application of this for the CFRS survey). Another limiting factor is of course the wavelength coverage of the spectrum.

Alternatively equation (2.10) can be viewed as a constraint on $f(\lambda)$. It is therefore possible to take a set of known high-S/N spectra that cover the observed range of spectral properties of galaxies, and use equation (2.10) to fit an optimal linear combination of these spectra.

The basic idea of fitting SEDs to aperture colours for faint field galaxies of known redshift has often been used as a step to estimate k -corrections. A typical example is [Eales \(1993\)](#) who uses the $b_J - r_F$ colours for the LDSS-1 to choose between a set of template SEDs. Similarly, the CFRS group interpolated a set of SEDs to their $(V - I)_{\text{AB}}$ colours and chose the best-fitting combination. An interesting variation to this approach was used by [Gardner \(1996\)](#). He used $b_J - r_F$ and $r_F - K$ colours for his galaxies to select a best-fit SED from a set of GISSEL models from [Bruzual & Charlot \(1993\)](#), including the effects of passive evolution. An interesting additional feature was the independent weighting of $b_J - r_F$ and $r_F - K$ in the fitting procedure.

An alternative approach is to correlate the observed spectrum with a set of template spectra, either using cross-correlation techniques (e.g. [Heyl et al. 1997](#); [Zaritsky et al. 1995](#); [Connolly et al. 1995](#)), or principal component analysis ([Folkes et al. 1996](#); [Connolly et al. 1995](#); [Folkes et al. 1999](#)). This is a potentially very powerful technique, but it works well only for fairly good S/N spectra, whereas photometric methods can be used with fainter, and therefore on average more distant, galaxies in a sample.

However, all these approaches have the disadvantage that errors are difficult to assess in a rigorous way (see for instance the discussion in [Heyl et al. 1997](#)). For some it is also a problem that the final SED will be taken from a discrete set of SEDs, which will lead to quantisation of the k -corrections, an effect that can be quite large at high- z where the spacing between the k -corrections for the different classes is not uniform (see eg. [Figure 2.5\(a\)](#)). Lastly, the methods that depend on aperture colours have an added uncertainty in the common case of using only one colour to estimate the SED. This might be acceptable in the case of high precision photometry, but this is not always available for the faintest galaxies. The

advantage of several photometric bands is illustrated by [Bershady \(1995\)](#) who shows that they make it possible to estimate galaxy colours and k -corrections accurately out to $z = 0.3$.

To address these issues in reverse order, we will adopt a method here where we fit independently to each available aperture colour for a given galaxy. These fits are then combined by weighting the fits inversely by the variance of the colours used for the given fit. Note that this does only constitute a maximum-likelihood method in the case of Gaussian errors in the distribution of the fits, and this might not be a reasonable approximation. An alternative method is discussed in Chapter 6. The advantage of the present approach is that one can interpolate between SEDs from our adopted set to obtain a best-fit SED for each colour. Finally, the errors in this process can be estimated using a Monte Carlo method (eg. [Press et al. 1992](#)) described below.

The choice of SED set is important, one has to have a set of SEDs that span the spectral properties of the galaxies in question. One option is to use model spectra from a spectral synthesis code ([Bruzual & Charlot 1993](#); [Jimenez et al. 1998](#); [Poggianti 1997](#)), and we will take this approach in Chapter 6. The disadvantage of the synthetic spectra is that one needs to incorporate a realistic model for internal extinction to be comparable to observed spectra. A more empirical approach is to use observed spectra of galaxies, and we will follow that approach here. Specifically we will adopt the [Coleman et al. \(1980, CWW\)](#) spectral energy distributions in the following.

2.4.1 The Monte Carlo method

For a given galaxy g , we have a collection of colours $\{C(A_i, B_i)\}$ where A_i and B_i are magnitudes with associated a standard deviation of $\{\sigma_i^A, \sigma_i^B\}$, and we will assume that the errors on the magnitudes are Gaussian. In addition we have a set of average spectra for E/S0, Sab, Sbc, Scd, Sdm and Irregular galaxies, $\{S_i(\lambda)\}$. The aim of our exercise is to get a good estimate of the SED of our galaxy g performing accurate error propagation, and to do so we adopt the following scheme:

1. For each magnitude we draw a random realization, according to the intrinsic error given with standard deviation σ_i . We then form the set of colours for the galaxy defined as $C_i = m_{i+1} - m_i$ where m_i is magnitude i .
2. We then calculate the colour of all the template spectra redshifted to the galaxy's redshift z_{gal} . This gives a set of template colours T_j .
3. We then determine i so that $T_j \leq C_i \leq T_{j+1}$, and assign an SED to the objects as

$$f(\lambda) = \frac{C_i - T_{j+1}}{T_j - T_{j+1}} S_j(\lambda) + \frac{T_i - C_i}{T_j - T_{j+1}} S_{j+1}(\lambda), \quad (2.12)$$

assuming that the T_j are increasing, in reality the T_j are sorted which introduces a permutation of the indices for S_j , but this is merely a book-keeping issue. The galaxy

is then assigned a spectral class c_i

$$c_i(C_i) = j + \frac{T_j - C_i}{T_j - T_{j+1}}, \quad (2.13)$$

where C_i has been left in to emphasise the dependence of the class on the colour used for the fit².

4. The c_i 's are finally combined for all colours in a maximum likelihood way³, using inverse variance weighting

$$\bar{c} = \frac{\sum_i \frac{c_i(C_i)}{\sigma_i^2}}{\sum_i \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2}}. \quad (2.14)$$

This \bar{c} defines the optimal SED, $\overline{S(\lambda)}$ for this galaxy given the colours by inverting equation (2.13), and inserting into (2.12).

5. Any quantities that are a function of the assumed SED are calculated using $\overline{S(\lambda)}$. Examples of such quantities are colour shifts, k -corrections, z_{\min} , z_{\max} and V_{\max} values.

For every galaxy we wish to estimate the SED for this process is repeated typically 1000 times. For each repetition relevant quantities, such as the k -correction, colour transformation or absolute magnitudes are calculated and tabulated, examples are given below. This could also be combined with a bootstrap technique (see e.g. the discussion on luminosity functions in Chapter 4)

2.4.2 Examples of use

The Monte Carlo method can be used to get realistic errors on the k -correction and hence the absolute magnitude of any galaxy. Inserting the best-fit SED, $\overline{S(\lambda)}$ in equation (2.7), results in a prediction of the k -correction and through equation (2.9) the absolute magnitude. In the next section we show that to get a uniform estimate of absolute magnitudes for the galaxies in the survey, we need to calculate absolute B -band magnitudes from I -band photometry. In the top panel of Figure 2.6 we plot the intrinsic error in the k -correction as a function of redshift for the CFRS galaxies. Note in particular that the error in the k -correction goes to zero around $z \sim 0.9$ where the observed I -band samples the rest B -band.

It is also evident in the figure that the estimation of k -correction depends heavily on the estimated SED at low redshift, and as pointed out by [Bershady \(1995\)](#), there are better ways to estimate the k -correction. One possibility for the CFRS galaxies is to use the V -band at redshifts less than $z = (\lambda_I + \lambda_V)/2\lambda_B \approx 0.58$ where observed V is closer to rest B

²For accurate photometry and typical SEDs every colour should of course lead to the same SED, but in reality there is always some scatter between the predictions for each colour.

³This is a maximum likelihood statistic only if errors are Gaussian, which is likely to be the case as long as the photometric errors are small

FIGURE 2.6: The intrinsic error in the k -correction derived using the Monte Carlo method described in the text. Top: The error on the k -corrections when calculating absolute B magnitudes from I -band photometry. The dashed line indicates where the I -band samples the rest B -band. Bottom: Similar to above, but using V -band photometry for $z < 0.58$ where V is closer to rest B than I .

FIGURE 2.7: The distribution of absolute magnitudes for eight galaxies from the CFRS survey. The solid line shows the best fit Gaussian, and the dashed line shows the Gaussian expected if the intrinsic error in the I-band magnitude dominated the error-budget. All plots have a width of 1.5 magnitudes and are centred on the median absolute magnitude.

than observed I . The error in the k -correction so obtained is shown in Figure 2.6, where the advantage of using multi-band photometry to estimate accurate k -corrections is explicitly shown.

After the full Monte Carlo simulation these realizations can be analysed to give a mean absolute magnitude and a 1σ deviation appropriate for this. The results of such an analysis for eight CFRS galaxies, randomly selected, can be seen in Figure 2.7. What is evident from these plots is that the error distribution of absolute magnitudes is not necessarily Gaussian. To indicate the difference from the errors due to the intrinsic error in the I magnitude used to calculate the absolute magnitudes, the dashed line in the plot show a Gaussian with FWHM equal to σ_I .

It should be remarked that the errors obtained using the methods here are intrinsic to the given procedure for fitting SEDs, and in particular on the set of SEDs used for the fitting procedure. This should not be a major issue in the work described here as we allow for linear combination of SEDs to approximate the variation of SEDs observed in nature, and the k -correction calculations only depend on the properties of the SEDs in the optical. In particular, the uncertainty in SEDs in the ultraviolet (eg. Ellis 1997) is not a major concern for this particular application as the observed I -band does not sample the rest-frame UV until $z \sim 2$.

2.4.3 Summary

This has been a fairly detailed technical discussion, so it is useful to step back and summarise what the practical use of this methodology is. The most important aspect is that it provides a method to quantify the uncertainty in the estimation of k -corrections and hence absolute magnitudes for high- z galaxies. The intrinsic uncertainty in absolute magnitudes is about a factor of 2 larger than the uncertainty in the I magnitudes alone for galaxies between $z = 0.2$ and $z = 0.4$, from an average of $\sigma = 0.06$ to $\sigma = 0.12$ whereas the increase is much less close to $z = 0.9$ where observed I -band samples rest B .

In addition this methodology enables us to calculate colour transformations for any given galaxy and assign an uncertainty to it. This is useful when magnitudes are given in slightly different passbands.

2.5 Joining the surveys

In rough order of decreasing importance the main steps needed to join the LDSS/Autofib and CFRS surveys are:

1. The magnitudes must be aligned so that they are measured in a comparable way.
2. A uniform method for calculation of k -corrections must be used and compared to published k -corrections to relate the results to the parent populations.
3. Various secondary measured quantities and data quality indicators should ideally be aligned. It is also convenient to introduce a common naming scheme.

FIGURE 2.8: *The shift between published magnitudes and re-observations of LDSS-1, LDSS-2 and Autofib objects as described in the text. The re-observations are all on a uniform photometric system, whereas LDSS-1, LDSS-2 and Autofib all were zeropointed independently.*

2.5.1 Alignment of the magnitude systems

The best way to align magnitude systems is of course to obtain uniform photometry of the entire sample, but this can be prohibitive in terms of observing time. In the present work, however, the situation is rather better, as we already have uniform photometry for the entire sample in the form of HST imaging. As we will see below it is possible to use HST photometry to align the B-band selected LDSS surveys and the I-band selected CFRS survey.

Given the different detection criteria and methodology used in the various LDSS surveys and the Autofib survey, there is no simple way to align the B -magnitudes without any independent calibration. One way would be to use the HST I -band magnitudes as calibration, but the significant difference in wavelength introduces additional uncertainties. Instead we have used CCD observations of some LDSS fields from the WHT to calibrate of the magnitude systems for the LDSS1, LDSS2 and Autofib surveys. The CCD images were analysed with SExtractor and the difference between SExtractor’s total magnitudes and the published B magnitudes for the objects is plotted in Figure 2.8. The WHT data uses a slightly different filter system, and the SExtractor magnitudes were transformed to the LDSS1 filter system using either the published $b_J - r_F$ magnitudes or when they were missing, $b_J - I$ magnitudes where I is the SExtractor I -band magnitude, using the formalism in Section 2.4.

As mentioned earlier, we want to normalise to LDSS-2, and using the relations in Figure 2.8, the conclusion is that the LDSS-1 and Autofib magnitudes must be made fainter by 0.15 and 0.14 magnitudes respectively for their magnitude measurements to be aligned with the LDSS-2. There is no indication of a magnitude or redshift dependent term in this

conversion. The close agreement between LDSS-1 and Autofib is not very surprising as the underlying photometry is based on the same scanned plates.

The ultimate goal with our alignment here is to be able to give absolute magnitudes for CFRS and LDSS objects that are calculated in the same way, and to know their relationship to previously published absolute magnitudes. The calculation of absolute magnitudes in the same way is straightforward as we have HST photometry for both the LDSS and CFRS objects, which constitutes an uniform basis for calculation of absolute magnitudes.

This is sufficient for the fainter objects, for which the HST magnitudes are accurate. However, as mentioned in Section 2.3.2, the HST photometry for the brightest objects is uncertain due to the limited area of the HST fields and the associated uncertainties in background estimation. We therefore have to make a connection between the HST photometry and the ground-based calculations. It is therefore necessary to look more carefully at the methods used to calculate absolute magnitudes for the CFRS and LDSS surveys.

The CFRS presented their absolute B -magnitudes based on isophotal I -magnitudes whereas the LDSS-2 presented absolute B -magnitudes based on corrected aperture magnitudes in b_J . Given the good correlation for the 3 arcsec HST magnitudes⁴ and ground based isophotal I magnitudes in Figure 2.4(b), we can measure 3 arcsec HST magnitudes for the LDSS-2 objects which can be used to calculate the absolute B -band magnitude. Using the formalism in Section 2.4 we can also calculate the colour shift between the published M_{b_J} -magnitudes and the magnitudes based on the CFRS B -band. One final difference between the two surveys is that the CFRS used SEDs from Bruzual & Charlot (1993, updated to BC95) whereas the LDSS group used the CWW spectra. It is also necessary to check that this different choice does not affect the calculation of absolute magnitudes.

The results of this exercise are shown in Figure 2.9. The top panel shows the colour terms applied to the b_J magnitudes to get them onto the CFRS filter system, the middle panel shows the shift between the absolute magnitude calculated using the CFRS SEDs and the LDSS-2 SEDs. It is clear that there is good agreement between the two filter sets. In the bottom panel we show the difference between the LDSS-2 absolute magnitudes calculated from b_J and I_{F814W} . We see from this that the published corrected aperture magnitudes for the LDSS-2 give a similar magnitude scale to the CFRS isophotal scale for faint objects. We can also use the published magnitudes for the LDSS-1 and Autofib objects, with the minor correction given above, to get a consistent absolute magnitude system for the entire survey.

In the rest of this thesis, the absolute magnitudes quoted will be based on the isophotal I -band magnitudes for the CFRS galaxies, the 3" F814W aperture magnitudes for the LDSS-2 galaxies, and published b_J photometry corrected as mentioned above for the the LDSS-1 and Autofib surveys. k -corrections will be calculated using the method outlined in Section 2.4.

The accuracy of these absolute magnitudes is almost independent of redshift. This is

⁴The entire argument here can be carried through based on SExtractor magnitudes too, the reason for using 3" magnitudes is to avoid the complications associated with SExtractor breaking up mergers into separate galaxies.

FIGURE 2.9: Verifying the absolute magnitude scales of the CFRS and LDSS-2 redshift surveys. Top panel: $B_{AB} - b_J$ colour for the LDSS-2 galaxies. Middle panel: Difference in M_B for CFRS galaxies using the CFRS and LDSS-2 SEDs. Bottom panel: The redshift dependence of M_B differences obtained by calculating k -corrections for the LDSS-2 galaxies using b_J and I_{F814W} .

because the increased uncertainty due to the faintness (in average) of the distant galaxies is offset by the increased uncertainty in k -correction for the low redshift galaxies. The net result is absolute magnitudes with a median *intrinsic* uncertainty of $\sigma \approx 0.08$ mag.

2.5.2 Quality indicators and naming scheme

The redshift quality indicator that the CFRS used has the property that a higher number indicates more accurately determined redshift, whereas the one used for the LDSS survey has the exactly opposite trend. Since the CFRS survey dominates the numbers, it was decided to keep their quality indicators. To translate from LDSS quality indicators, the following table was used:

LDSS quality class	CFRS quality class
1	4
2	2
3	0
4/5	0

In deciding upon this translation we have chosen to ignore class 8 and 9 from the CFRS system, this is because there is insufficient information in the published LDSS data to determine which of these classes to assign any galaxy to and as we in general will treat galaxies with class 8 together with class 2 and class 9 with class 1; this does not affect results at all.

Finally, to simplify notation, a new naming scheme for the LDSS galaxies was chosen to look similar to the CFRS scheme. The CFRS galaxies all have ID numbers XX.YYYY where XX is the field they are observed in, and YYYY is a running number within this field. Since the running number is always ≤ 9999 for the CFRS galaxies, the LDSS galaxies have been assigned similar id, but with a running number starting at 10000. The translation between old and new IDs are given in [Brinchmann et al. \(1998\)](#).

2.6 Consistency checks

It is important to check that we have not introduced any secondary selection biases in the construction of the HST-based subsample of the CFRS/LDSS galaxies. We do this by comparing the properties of the HST sample with the parent samples. Throughout the discussion in this section, we focus on the LDSS-2 and CFRS samples, as the small numbers of LDSS-1 and Autofib objects make statistical tests difficult. However, the LDSS-1 and Autofib objects are observed on the same HST frames as the LDSS-2 objects, so we expect any secondary selection criterion that affects the LDSS-2 objects to have a similar effect on the selection of LDSS-1 and Autofib objects.

In Figure 2.10 we plot the redshift distribution of the parent and HST based sample for the LDSS-2 and CFRS. As can be seen, the smaller size of the HST-samples, means that the “picket fence” nature of the redshift distribution in different fields (e.g.

FIGURE 2.10: *Normalised redshift distribution histograms for the CFRS survey on top and the LDSS survey on the bottom. Left: the full ground-based surveys and Right: for the objects with HST imaging.*

Crampton et al. 1995; Cohen et al. 1999b) is more pronounced. Comparing these distributions accurately is complicated by the existence of small-scale correlations between galaxies (see Crampton et al. 1995 for a thorough discussion of this). However, we have chosen to ignore this as these distributions are averaged over several fields and we are only interested in testing whether the distributions are roughly similar. For the CFRS data, the subsample of galaxies with HST imaging is consistent with having the same distribution as its parent population at a confidence level of 65.1%, which, given the complications of galaxy correlations is fully satisfactory. Likewise, the LDSS-2 survey has a confidence level of 54%, which due to the smaller number of independent fields involved in the calculation is also satisfactory agreement.

To further ascertain that the subsamples represent a fair selection of galaxies from their parent populations, we show the distribution of absolute magnitudes for the galaxies in Figure 2.11. This should be less affected by clustering than the redshift distributions, and a KS test between the subsample and the parent population show that the CFRS samples are consistent to 94% confidence level and the LDSS-2 samples are consistent to 95% confidence level.

We therefore conclude that the selection of fields for HST imaging has not introduced any further selection biases in the sample. Assuming that the LDSS-1 and Autofib galaxies have the same secondary selection criterion as the LDSS-2 galaxies, we can apply this conclusion to conclude that they also have the same statistical properties as their parent population.

2.7 Summary

In summary this chapter has provided the details of the alignment of the *B*-selected LDSS redshift surveys and the *I*-selected CFRS. This proved to be simplified by the existence of HST imaging for all galaxies. In addition a method to quantify errors in estimates of *k*-corrections was developed and used to show that the *intrinsic* error in absolute magnitude for the sample is almost independent of redshift with $\langle\sigma\rangle = 0.08$ magnitudes.

This has given us a well-defined sample of 341 field galaxies with well-understood selection criteria and uniform photometry. This sample will provide a sound basis to carry out further investigations. The next step in this process is to determine the morphology of the galaxies, and that is the task of the next chapter.

FIGURE 2.11: *The distribution of absolute magnitudes for the LDSS-2 and CFRS surveys.*

Chapter 3

Measures of morphologies

- 1. The classification system shall be so defined that different observers will obtain similar results systematically; that is, conflicting criteria should not be allowed to interfere with the precision with which the system is defined.*
- 2. A specimen that does not resemble any of the standard categories should not be forced into membership of one of them.*

W. W. MORGAN (1958)

3.1 Introduction

To physically interpret the evolution of the galaxy luminosity function (LF) as delineated by the original ground-based redshift surveys, both the CFRS and LDSS analyses sub-divided the samples on the basis of spectroscopic and photometric classes. CFRS analyses of the LF based on rest-frame colour found luminosity evolution to be stronger for galaxies bluer than a Sbc. LDSS samples selected according to the rest-frame equivalent width of the [O II] 3727 line found that the evolutionary trends arose almost exclusively from galaxies with strong emission-lines.

The availability of HST data for 341 galaxies allows us to investigate these changes in more detail. Ideally galaxies should be classified according to a label which is not modified by any of the physical processes responsible for the evolution. Part of the difficulty with colour and emission line strength is that populations defined according to these criteria may well be transient, and thus detailed comparisons of luminosities and volume densities at various redshifts will be confused. The same criticism can no doubt be applied to galaxy morphology (eg. [White 1996](#); [Baugh et al. 1996](#)), although the time-scale for a significant change in morphology is expected to be longer than changes in, say, emission line intensity. In addition the morphologically split number counts from the Medium Deep Survey (MDS, [Abraham et al. 1996b](#); [Glazebrook et al. 1995](#); [Driver et al. 1995](#); [Griffiths et al. 1994](#)) and

FIGURE 3.1: *The Hubble “tuning-fork” diagram for nearby galaxies. The image is courtesy George Lake’s homepage.*

the Hubble Deep Field (Abraham et al. 1996a) raises important questions concerning the physical properties of the apparently rapidly evolving irregular/peculiar/merger galaxies, and it is of considerable interest to investigate the redshift distribution of these morphological categories.

This chapter will start by outlining the subject of galaxy classification, with emphasis on morphological classifications, but touching briefly on classification methods based on spectrum or colours. This will lead to a discussion of the morphological classifications used in this work and a study of the redshift dependence of the machine classifications, before the morphological properties of the sample are studied in Section 3.6 and different methods for classification contrasted.

3.2 An overview of classification procedures

The goal of most methods of classification is to devise a system that correlates well with underlying physical properties. One can imagine many basic qualities of galaxies that one could use as a fundamental quantity for classification, such as their apparent visual morphology, integrated spectra, presence or absence of spectral features, light profiles and environment. The choice of classification method depends on the application. If one is studying environmental effects it is convenient to label galaxies as to whether they are isolated, in loose groups or in dense clusters. When the goal is to study the evolution of galaxies the choice of classification is somewhat more complicated.

The study of visual morphology started with Hubble’s (1926) early work on the visual properties of galaxies. This led him to propose a classification system for galaxies, often referred to as the “tuning-fork” diagram (Figure 3.1), which was subsequently refined and found its final form in “The Hubble Atlas of Galaxies” (Sandage 1961). The Hubble system of classification has been used as the basis for most later visual classification work, although

the original physical interpretation of the Hubble sequence as an evolutionary sequence from early type (spheroidal systems) to late type systems (Sc spirals) is no longer believed to be correct (although this notion survives in the traditional naming of spirals as late types and ellipticals as early types).

The field of morphological classification of galaxies, with particular emphasis on classical¹, visual morphology has recently been thoroughly reviewed by [van den Bergh \(1998\)](#). Much of the discussion here is dealt with in detail there, and I will just summarise the classical classification systems and instead concentrate on the computer based classification systems introduced recently. For the discussion here, the most important classical classification systems are the Hubble system ([Sandage 1961](#)), the de Vaucouleur's T system ([de Vaucouleurs 1959](#)), the extended Hubble system by [van den Bergh \(DDO 1960a,b\)](#) and the Yerkes classification system ([Morgan 1959, 1958](#)) based on central concentration of light in galaxies.

The de Vaucouleur's T system This is a simplified version of the 3-dimensional classification system used in the 3rd Reference Catalogue of galaxies (RC3, [de Vaucouleurs et al. 1991](#)) which in turn is based on de Vaucouleur's (1959) revised Hubble classification system. The T system simply assigns a numerical morphological class to a galaxy from E ($T = -5$) through Sab ($T = 2$) to Magellanic irregulars ($T = 10$)². This system has turned out to be well-suited for classification of local galaxies when the added detail of the full RC3 classification system is unnecessary and has been used as the basis for artificial neural network classification systems (see below).

One criticism of the T system is that the morphological mixture is a strong function of absolute magnitude as illustrated in Figure 3.2 and this is a correlation it is highly desirable to remove when comparing classifications with physical parameters.

The DDO classification system was devised by van den Bergh (1960a,b), to take into account the variation of morphology with luminosity. This was achieved by using a two dimensional classification scheme where the luminosity is one parameter. The fact that the morphological mixture is a function of luminosity will be of interest in the discussion here given that the galaxies are selected according to a fixed *apparent* magnitude limit which translates into a redshift dependent *absolute* magnitude limit. Low-redshift galaxies will therefore display a different morphological mix than high redshift galaxies simply because they have a different typical luminosities (Figure 3.2).

The Yerkes system The last of the classical visual classification systems relevant for this discussion is the Morgan or Yerkes system devised by Morgan (1958, 1959) which primarily assigns classes to galaxies based on the central concentration of light. It is however often forgotten that the classification system devised by Morgan was meant to reflect the

¹In the following a classical morphological system is taken to mean a system based on visual inspection of *B*-band photographic plates.

²In the RC3 $T = 90$ is used to denote chaotic irregulars, with M82 being the archetypical example.

FIGURE 3.2: Right: The median absolute magnitude for galaxies in the RC3 as a function of their de Vaucouleurs T class. The errors bars mark the upper and lower quartile of the distribution. Left: The fractional contribution of the three morphological classes indicated. Note the increased fraction of irregular galaxies at faint magnitudes.

fact that central concentration is well-correlated with the spectral properties of galaxies, so that his subclasses a , f and k were chosen to correspond to galaxies whose spectra resembled A, F and K stars respectively³. Although Morgan was not the first to devise a system of galaxy classification based on form and spectral type it is interesting to note that this connection of morphology and spectral properties is exactly one of the issues this work aims to address. For the discussion here though, the most important result of Morgan's studies is that he found that a simple parameter like the central concentration of light was able to yield a classification sequence that correlated fairly well with the Hubble system.

The classification systems above are all fairly detailed, recording fine detail about a galaxy's morphology, but for high redshift galaxies such detailed classifications are not possible even with the refurbished HST. Thus, when the first large samples of galaxies with HST morphologies became available as a result of the Medium Deep Survey (Griffiths et al. 1994) it became necessary to develop a more coarse system for classification of high z galaxies, allowing for the possibility of a large number of galaxies not encompassed by the traditional Hubble system. The system adopted is described in Glazebrook et al. (1995) and uses three main morphological classes: Elliptical/S0, Spiral and Irregular/Peculiar/Merger. In this work we have adopted a variant of this classification system which is detailed further below. A major complication relative to local studies is that one no longer observes galaxies at the same rest wavelength, but rather at shorter and shorter wavelengths at higher redshift, added to this is the severe effect of cosmological $(1+z)^3$ dimming (see Appendix A) which makes low-surface brightness features exceedingly difficult to detect at high redshifts. These effects have proven difficult to address due to the subjective nature of visual classifications.

These difficulties have led to automated classification systems, described further below, which broadly speaking falls into three groups:

- The “expert” system approach. This typically involves a neural network that is trained on a set of galaxies with known morphology.
- The “light distribution” methods. These use the distribution of light in galaxies to classify them.
- The “spectral” classification methods. These use the integrated spectrum of a galaxy to classify galaxies. Superficially at least, this is the method that most closely resembles the classical stellar classifications. For very faint galaxies this procedure is replaced with classification based on their colours.

We will now deal with each in turn, reviewing progress in this field over the last 5-10 years with particular emphasis on the classification of galaxies from HST images.

³It is also interesting to note that the name cD galaxies for the most luminous elliptical galaxies originates from the Morgan classification system where D galaxies were rotationally symmetric objects with no spiral or elliptical structure

3.2.1 Expert systems

The term “expert systems” was coined in the field of Artificial Intelligence to denote a rule-based system which could be trained to make logical decisions. These are often implemented in Lisp and contain various types of rules for decision-making. This type of systems has not been widely used in the classification of galaxies. [Thomnat \(1989\)](#) is a notable exception; she used an expert system to classify photographic images of galaxies with promising results. In astronomy, however, more progress has been made using artificial neural networks (ANNs).

An ANN is an algorithm that iteratively finds a configuration where it can optimally reproduce a set of classifications based on a set of input data for a “training set”. This configuration is then used for a larger set of data to produce classifications for these. The appeal of this technique is that it seems to closely mimic the process by which a classical morphologist works, with inspection of a select set of images and later classification of unknown galaxies based on what was learned about the reference set.

In practice however, an image of a galaxy has to be reduced to a set of basic descriptive parameters before being fed to the ANN. In their pioneering study of the morphology of the ESO-LV galaxies ([Lauberts & Valentijn 1989](#)), [Storrie-Lombardi et al. \(1992\)](#) made use of quantities such as the average $B - R$ colour, axial ratio, error in the fit to ellipses and central surface brightnesses, in all 13 different quantities, to classify galaxies onto five Hubble classes. They showed that this was a promising method for machine classification of galaxies, and several groups have followed up their work with more detailed studies for nearby galaxies ([Naim et al. 1995b](#)) and faint galaxies observed with HST ([Odewahn et al. 1996](#)). In general it is found that results from ANNs correlate very well with visual classifications, and [Odewahn et al. \(1996\)](#) claim that their classification method is stable with respect to observed frame wavelength and redshift.

The advantage of the ANN method is that it is possible to classify galaxies very similarly to a given human expert. This is quite useful when comparing to local comparison data which has generally been classified by human experts. A weakness of the traditional “supervised” ANNs is that they in some sense only predict what they are given as input. If the training set did not include a particular set of galaxies that exists in your data, this type of galaxies will typically be assigned to a wrong class. To remedy this one can approach the question using an “unsupervised” ANN or alternatively a self-organising map (SOM, [Naim et al. 1997](#)). The latter is a potentially very interesting area, and [Naim et al. \(1997\)](#) claim that it is possible to discover interesting correlations in morphology space using this technique. However, the results are difficult to interpret and results from SOMs are not always stable, in the sense that a different starting algorithm might produce rather different results ([Naim priv. communication](#)).

3.2.2 The “light distribution” methods

In 1948 de Vaucouleurs showed that elliptical galaxies had light profiles that could accurately be fitted by an “ $r^{1/4}$ -law”,

$$I(r) = I_e \exp \left\{ -7.67 \left[(r/r_e)^{1/4} - 1 \right] \right\} \quad (3.1)$$

where r_e is called the effective radius (de Vaucouleurs 1948). A similarly simple relation holds for the azimuthally averaged light profiles of spiral galaxies, which generally have an exponential profile (de Vaucouleurs 1959; Freeman 1970)

$$I(r) = I_0 \exp(-r/r_e). \quad (3.2)$$

This correlation between light profile and morphological type was utilised by Morgan (Morgan 1958,1959) who established (although without stating it explicitly) that a classification based on the degree of central concentration of light of a galaxy gives a fairly good correspondence with the Hubble classifications. This is not particularly surprising as the Hubble system is partly based on the bulge-to-disk ratios of galaxies.

In the last ten years interest has been renewed in these correlations between morphology and light distribution for the automated classification of galaxies. These approaches differ in philosophy from the methods described in the previous section in that they do not primarily seek to reproduce classical morphological systems — rather they attempt to find simple and efficient criteria for classification. These attempts can be split into two distinct methodologies

- The classification of galaxies based on simple measures of the light distribution, typically the central concentration augmented with some independent measure of the light distribution such as the surface brightness (Doi et al. 1993) or the amount of asymmetric light (Abraham et al. 1994, 1996b; Conselice et al. 1999). These methods are typically non-parametric and is hence well-suited for use in uncharted waters.
- Classification of galaxies based on multi-parameter fits to parametric models of light distribution. These fits were traditionally 1D (Freeman 1970; Kent 1985, see Simien (1989) for a review), but with the recent improvement in computing power it has become feasible to perform 2D fits for large datasets (e.g. Byun & Freeman 1995; Schade et al. 1995; Marleau & Simard 1998)

Although the two methodologies essentially are based on the same quantities they differ quite considerably in philosophy. The non-parametric methods have an advantage when the underlying light distribution is not well-known, as is (or at least was) the case for high redshift galaxies, whereas the parametric models can extract far more information about the galaxies — with the assumption that the parametric model is a good representation of the light profile.

3.2.3 Spectral classifications

Stars are in general classified on the basis of their spectral appearance, and this is found to correlate very well with physical parameters such as effective temperature and surface gravity. It would be very helpful if a similar correlation between well-defined physical parameters and spectral appearance was to be found for galaxies. Unfortunately this is not as clear-cut, since galaxies are considerably more complex physical systems than their constituent stars.

Despite this, the spectrum of a galaxy, either in its full form or reduced to photometric measurements, can be used to put limits on the physical characteristics of a galaxy. The use of a given spectral class can thus be used to trace galaxies in similar states of evolution. It has also been known for a long time (eg. [Morgan & Mayall 1957](#)) that spectral properties correlate well with a galaxy's morphological characteristics so this has the potential of giving insight into evolution of galaxies.

The classification of galaxies based on spectral properties comes in two flavours:

- Classification based on detailed spectroscopic information, such as line strengths (for instance [OII] for high redshift galaxies (e.g. [Ellis et al. 1996](#); [Broadhurst et al. 1988](#)) or H α for local galaxies (e.g. [Gallego et al. 1995](#)) or broad-line or narrow-line QSOs), or the full spectrum such as classifications based on principal component+ANN analysis of the spectrum (e.g. [Folkes et al. 1999](#)) or cross-correlation between the spectrum and a set of templates (e.g. [Heyl et al. 1997](#)).
- Classification based on the colours of galaxies. Since a colour is essentially the convolution of a spectrum with a pair of response functions this still traces the underlying spectrum and it has the advantage of being less noisy than measures based on the full spectrum. Such classification methods have been used extensively for faint field galaxies ([Bershady 1995](#); [Lilly et al. 1995b](#); [Kauffmann et al. 1996](#)) and we will adopt this approach in this work where relevant, using the methods outlined in [Chapter 2](#).

Care should be taken in interpreting results from spectral classifications since some signatures might be very short-lived or correspond to a rather insignificant part of the galaxy. It is for instance important to separate out active galactic nuclei (AGN) from star-forming field galaxies when one selects galaxies based on emission line strengths since the process of emission line production is widely different in the two. It is not always easy to do so (eg. [Hammer et al. 1997](#)), which has been evident in the discussion on the nature of high-redshift sub-mm sources ([Smail et al. 1998](#); [Ivison et al. 1999](#); [Guideroni et al. 1999](#)).

3.3 Visual classifications used in this work

Several different approaches to the classification of galaxies were outlined above. In the present work the images are small, and often rather noisy with galaxies observed over a large range in redshift — this makes it very difficult to detect low surface brightness features

FIGURE 3.3: An illustration of our adopted morphological classification system, see also Table 3.1.

TABLE 3.1: *The classification system used in this work*

Class	Name	Description
-2	Star	Objects that are stellar in appearance. This is the only category where the redshift has been used in the classifications. If the spectrum is clearly stellar in nature, an object has been classed as star even if it is difficult to say whether it is a star or a compact from its image.
-1	Compact	Objects that are too compact to be reliably classified
0	E	Clearly elliptical galaxies with high degree of central concentration. No attempt has been made to assign a flattening class
1	E/S0	Centrally concentrated galaxies where no clear hint of a disk is visible, but where it cannot be completely ruled out
2	S0/a	Bulge-dominated objects with very weak disks
3	Sab	Clear bulge, but now also a well-defined disk
4	Sbc	Smaller bulge than in the previous class
5	Scd	Small bulge and often rather patchy spiral arms
6	Peculiar	Anything that doesn't fit in any other category. Amorphous objects and merging galaxies go into this category.
11	Tadpole	Compact objects with faint extensions

and prevents a detailed classification such as the one used in RC3. And even if it was possible to detect low surface brightness features a classification should not depend on it given the strong redshift dependence for surface brightness. Instead we have turned to simple methods for classifications and we also chose to devise automated as well as visual classifications.

The first technique we used to investigate the morphological characteristics of our sample follows the visual approach adopted by the Medium Deep Survey (MDS) team. Following the precepts discussed by Glazebrook et al. (1995b), three experienced observers (Richard Ellis, Simon Lilly and Olivier Le Fèvre) classified all the galaxies by eye according to the scheme described in Table 3.1 and illustrated in Figure 3.3. The scheme we have adopted here differs slightly from that utilised by the MDS team in that we decided to separate compact objects with faint extensions (so-called “tadpoles”) from the irregular/merger/peculiar and compact objects. This was done for objects for which classifications were either compact or peculiar and where no consensus could be reached. However in most of the work below this group will be included in the peculiar category.

An intercomparison of the eyeball classifications between the 3 observers is shown in Figure 3.4 and indicates a scatter of around 1.2 classes. This is similar to the scatter found by Abraham et al. (1996a) at the same magnitude limit. The figure also contains a table

FIGURE 3.4: Correlation between the different classifiers. The radii of the circles are proportional to the value in the correlation matrix. The correlation between the different classifiers is only slightly larger than the internal scatter of one classifier. The table shows the numbers of galaxies in each class for the different classifiers with the class numbers given in table 3.1.

FIGURE 3.5: *Distribution of galaxies in the $M(B_{AB}) - z$ plane for the HST survey. Inlaid histograms show the fractional contribution of the four visual classes as a function of redshift. In this plot the tadpoles have been grouped with the peculiar galaxies.*

FIGURE 3.6: *The luminosity distribution of Sm-Im galaxies compared to the one for I0 and peculiar galaxies in the RC3 catalogue*

showing the distribution of classes for each classifier⁴. The individual classifications were then merged by taking the median value of the different classifiers. The final number of objects in various classes is also indicated in Figure 3.4. The resulting $M_B - z$ diagram is shown in Figure 3.5 with the fractional redshift distributions of the various morphological classes inlaid.

3.3.1 The peculiar class

One of the major results of the early studies of the HST morphologies of faint field galaxies was the discovery of a large number of galaxies with peculiar morphologies that did not fit into the Hubble system (Glazebrook et al. 1995; Driver et al. 1995).

It is natural to dwell a bit more on the nature of peculiar galaxies in this work, and to make a bit clearer what is the characteristic of a peculiar galaxy. Firstly however it is important to clarify the terminology since there has been some confusion in the literature: There has been a tendency to label peculiar galaxies in the HST surveys as “irregulars”. This is a somewhat unfortunate terminology since locally this term is traditionally used for Magellanic irregulars (although the RC3 does introduce non-Magellanic irregulars (I0)⁵).

⁴The three classifiers do not all add up to 341 as for one or two of the objects the classifier had not given a classification

⁵The distinction between Magellanic and non-Magellanic irregulars was first emphasised by Holmberg (1958) who introduced the names Irr I and Irr II to refer to the different types. Later work also uses the term “amorphous galaxies” to refer to similar objects (Sandage & Brucato 1979). Here we will use the terminology

In this work the somewhat more neutral term “peculiar” will be used to denote anything that does not fall into any of the traditional Hubble classes (T=-5 to T=9 in the de Vaucouleurs system).

This definition means that our peculiar category will encompass rather different morphological types, with a wide range of physical characteristics. A similar situation occurs in the local data when I0 and Im galaxies are grouped together, as shown in Figure 3.6 where the luminosity distribution for Sm+Im galaxies in the RC3 is compared with the luminosity distribution for I0 and peculiar systems. Magellanic irregulars are typically low-luminosity objects quite distinct from the I0 and Peculiar categories. This fact is important when interpreting the results from a magnitude limited sample. At low redshift the peculiar galaxies in such a sample will primarily be of the Magellanic irregular type, whereas at higher redshift one would expect a larger contribution from the I0+Pec category.

Similarly the peculiar category in the present work also includes obviously merging galaxies, these are studied in [Le Fèvre et al. \(1999\)](#) where 26 galaxies were classified as visual mergers, indicating a 30% contribution of mergers to the peculiar population, almost all of these at $z > 0.5$. Although the visual classification of mergers is fraught with uncertainties, this indicates a significant contribution of merging galaxies to the peculiar category at high redshift. Hence in summary we are led to the following view of the peculiar category: at low redshift the peculiar galaxies correspond to the local Magellanic irregulars, with similar luminosities. At higher redshifts the peculiar category might correspond more closely to the I0 category locally, but with a large contribution of merging galaxies. This is however speculation without any further corroboration. Clearly a lot more work is needed to understand the evolutionary status and physical properties of peculiar galaxies. We will return to this point in the next chapter.

3.4 Automated classifications

A major difficulty with visual classifiers is their subjective nature ([Naim et al. 1995a](#)). Accordingly, as an objective route forward, we have also performed machine-based classifications using the procedures adopted by Abraham et al. (1994,1996b). The technique is based on measurements of a central concentration index, C , and a rotational asymmetry factor, A . The first of these parameters tracks the bulge-to-disk ratio, while the second traces the degree of irregularity, see Figure 3.7 for an illustration and below for more details. At low redshift, the positions of galaxies on the $\log(A)$ vs $\log(C)$ plane can be used to distinguish between early-type systems, spirals earlier than type Sd, late-type spirals and irregulars/peculiar/mergers, see also Figure 3.10. As will be shown below, at higher redshifts these classes can also be distinguished in principle using an A & C -diagram. However, uncertainties arise because galaxies of a given type may move into a region of the $A - C$ plane occupied by a different class because of redshift-dependent effects. These biases must be carefully studied before quantitative comparisons can be made over a range in redshift.

used in the RC3

FIGURE 3.7: *Calculation of AC. The figure illustrates the calculation of the two parameters, by showing the ellipses containing all and a third of the light for NGC4030 used to calculate C. A rotated copy of the galaxy and the result after subtraction of the rotated copy from the original image to leave the asymmetry image which in turns gives the A parameter*

We defer a discussion of these biases until the next section.

The starting point for measuring the two parameters is a “segmented” galaxy image, constructed by isolating those pixels that lie above a surface brightness threshold $N\sigma$ above the sky brightness, where σ is the sky variance and N is a constant, typically 1.5. For the present work (see discussion below), we have chosen σ so the measurements reach a uniform limiting surface brightness.

3.4.1 Central concentration

The C parameter represents the ratio of light within an inner and outer elliptical aperture determined from the sky-subtracted, intensity-weighted, second order moment of the resulting image. The major and minor axes of the outer aperture are normalised so that the total area within the ellipse is the isophotal area of the galaxy. The inner aperture is defined by scaling these axes down by a linear factor of three. This process is illustrated for NGC 4030 in the top line of Figure 3.7 where the elliptical apertures are drawn on top of the image.

Whereas this definition of central concentration is adequate for local galaxies, the value determined unfortunately depends on redshift since the threshold is defined relative to the

sky (see Figure 3.8). Thus less of the galaxy is sampled at high redshift because of cosmological dimming (Dalcanton 1998). In measuring C , a limiting isophote, μ_l , is selected relative to the background sky. Since the HST images generally have similar limiting isophotes regardless of the galaxy redshift, in the rest-frame there are shifts with redshift which scale as $10\log(1+z)$. Since measuring to a fixed rest-frame isophote throws away information at low z we have decided to correct the measurements with an average shift calibrated with simulations. For symmetric light profiles the central concentration is given by:

$$C = \frac{f(0.3R)}{f(R)}, \quad (3.3)$$

where R is the radius at which the surface brightness is equal to the limiting isophote selected, and $f(R)$ is given by:

$$f(R) = 2\pi \int_0^R I(r) r dr.$$

Equation (3.3) can be solved analytically for a pure de Vaucouleurs law (Equation (3.1)), The resultant expression for the central concentration is then

$$C_{dV} = \frac{g(V)}{g(0.3^{1/4}V)}, \quad V = 7.67 \left(\frac{\mu_l - \mu_e}{8.3276} + 1 \right), \quad (3.4)$$

where μ_e is the surface brightness at the effective radius and $g(V)$ is given as

$$g(V) = \int_0^V v^7 e^{-v} dv = 7! \left[1 - e^{-V} \sum_{k=0}^7 \frac{V^k}{k!} \right].$$

It is worth noting that the expression for C is independent of details of the profile except for the central surface brightness or, equivalently, the surface brightness at the effective radius. This statement remains true for exponential disks, but breaks down for mixed profiles, where both the exponential scalelength and the effective radius come into play.

Accordingly, we therefore have a relation that can be used to calculate the change in C that occurs as a function of redshift: $\Delta C = g(z=0; \mu_0) - g(z; \mu_0)$, where μ_0 is the central surface brightness. This is a function of the details of the profile, but not strongly so. In practice, we used this functional form and calibrated the correction from simulations described below in section 3.5.1. This enabled us to adopt the following relation to correct C :

$$\Delta C(z) = 0.6 \times [C_{dV}(0; \mu_0 = 15.0) - C_{dV}(z; \mu_0 = 15.0)], \quad (3.5)$$

with C_{dV} given in equation (3.4) above. We will refer to this as a *minimal* correction as it does not take into account bandshifting effects, and it has been applied to all C values in in the rest of this work.

FIGURE 3.8: The dependence of C on the limiting isophote for the measurements. The top panels show the surface brightness as a function of radius for an exponential disk (left) and a de Vaucouleurs profile (right). The lower panels show the resulting value for C for the redshift or limiting isophote indicated. The broken lines in the upper and lower panels correspond to the same limiting isophote values.

3.4.2 Asymmetry

The rotational asymmetry parameter A is defined via:

$$A = \frac{\sum_{ij} |I_{ij} - I_{ij}^R|}{\sum_{ij} I_{ij}} - k_A, \quad (3.6)$$

where I_{ij} is the intensity in pixel (i, j) , and I_{ij}^R is the corresponding intensity after image rotation by 180° about the centroid of the segmented galaxy image. The k_A term in equation (3.6) is a small correction accounting for signal introduced into A by noise in the sky background; k_A is determined by measuring the asymmetry within a rotated and self-subtracted region of sky equal in area to that of the galaxy being analysed.

The measurement of these parameters is only practical for that subset of galaxy images with more than 64 contiguous WFPC-2 pixels above the surface brightness threshold (see also the discussion in [Abraham et al. 1994](#)). 25 galaxies (8%) are too compact for reliable classification via this approach. For these objects, only the visual estimates are available. The upper panel of Figure 3.9 shows the corrected A and C distributions for our sample. Dashed lines define three morphological bins (ellipticals/ spirals/peculiar) drawn on the basis of similar measurements made on the local sample described below and shown in Figure 3.10. The properties of this local dataset is discussed in detail in the next section. To avoid confusion with the visual classifications, we will refer to the automated classes as AC-ellipticals ($AC - E$), AC-spirals ($AC - S$) and AC-peculiar ($AC - P$). The angle from the intersection point of the dashed line in the upper panel of Figure 3.9 to each point in the AC plane, defines a continuous classification angle, Θ . The correlation between this angle and the eyeball classifications defined in Table 3.1 is shown in the lower panel of the figure. Overall the agreement is satisfactory but a sizeable scatter is apparent. Note in particular that the angle does not distinguish well between early-type spirals and E/S0 galaxies.

In the following each galaxy will have an AC class assigned based on its location in the A&C plane. The equations employed here were

$$AC\text{-class} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 50 \log C - \log A + 15 > 0, \\ 6 & \text{if } 5.5 \log C - \log A + 1.9444 \leq 0, \\ 4 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

This calibration was derived from our local comparison sample which we will discuss next.

3.4.3 The Frei et al. Calibration Sample

Our calibration sample is taken from [Frei et al. \(1996\)](#) and consists of 82 galaxies with B_J and R CCD images, uniform in quality with foreground stars removed. It is important to note, however, that the Frei et al galaxies were not chosen with the intention of sampling the luminosity function of local systems uniformly. Indeed, Frei et al chose galaxies that are (a) bright, (b) have well-resolved morphological structures, and (c) span a wide range of

FIGURE 3.9: *Upper panel: The distribution of galaxies in the A – C plane. Only objects with area larger than 64 contiguous pixels are shown. Bottom panel: The classification angle Θ (see text) plotted versus the eyeball classification for each object. The large circles show the median of each eyeball class.*

FIGURE 3.10: *The distribution of Frei galaxies in the A&C plane. A&C were calculated from the r_F images. The border-line classes, S0 and Sab are indicated by open symbols.*

Hubble system classification classes. It is therefore important to assess whether this sample is appropriate for calibrating redshift-dependent morphological trends.

The absolute magnitude distribution of the Frei et al sample is shown in Figure 3.11. The plot is based on M_B data published in the Revised Shapley Ames Catalog (RSA). We have applied an additional $0.^m5$ shift to take account of corrections applied for internal extinction in the RSA which we ignore in the CFRS+LDSS samples. We also indicate characteristic M^* values for local elliptical and Scd galaxies (Marzke et al. 1994). The Frei et al data peaks near M^* and, as expected, is deficient in systems ~ 2 mag or more fainter than M^* . This could be a drawback for our purposes, depending on how the morphological biases are corrected. If, for example, we correct morphologies back to those appropriate for the rest-frame I -band, a proper match between the CFRS/LDSS and Frei et al luminosity distributions is more important at high redshift. In this case, the majority of our survey galaxies beyond $z \simeq 0.3$ are drawn from within two magnitudes of M^* . In Figure 3.11 we show lines corresponding to the apparent magnitude limits for the CFRS survey based on k -corrections for early and late-type systems. Clearly the underluminous galaxies which are deficient in the Frei sample are undetectable. This reduces the number of galaxies suitable for our study which again increases the statistical uncertainty. But since we cover the whole range of morphological types, we do not introduce any systematic biases.

One might worry that selecting galaxies that are regular might lead us to infer less band-shifting than is observed. It is not possible to check this with the present sample, but since we are mostly interested in the quantity $\Delta A = A(z=0) - A(z)$ it is likely that the actual value

FIGURE 3.11: *The absolute magnitude distribution of the Frei et al galaxies with the selection limits appropriate for the deep HST survey overlaid. The selection function for Sbc galaxies is indicated.*

of A plays a secondary role. But to answer this satisfyingly a larger sample is needed. Thus, although the Frei et al sample is useful for estimating the apparent shift in morphology with redshift for regular objects of suitable luminosity, it could be improved. Future imaging surveys of local systems should aim to sample fairly the *distribution* of morphological types within both the luminosity selection criteria of the survey and the regions on the A vs. C diagram. Such datasets would also allow compilation of no- and mild-evolution simulated datasets for comparison with high redshift data (see also [Bouwens et al. 1998a,b](#)).

3.5 Redshift dependent biases

High z galaxies imaged by the HST differ in appearance from their local counterparts because of their reduced apparent size and sampling characteristics, a lower signal-to-noise and reduced surface brightness with respect to the sky background, and a shift in the rest-wavelength of the observations. The latter term we will refer to as ‘bandpass shifting’. These effects will combine to give some uncertainty in the morphological classification of galaxies, generally in the sense of shifting objects to apparently later Hubble types.

Glazebrook et al (1995b) attempted to address this in the context of their visual classification procedure via a blind classification of local galaxies whose appearance was carefully simulated as viewed at a redshift $z = 0.7$. For machine classifications this has been addressed to some extent by Abraham et al. (1996b) using the parameters A and C . A benefit of working in the framework of A and C classifications is that it enables more quantitative statements about these biases.

The work here is an extension of the work by [Abraham et al. \(1996b\)](#) for the MDS, here

utilising the known redshifts of our sample to correct for these redshift-dependent biases. To do this we have relied on extensive simulations based on the multi-colour CCD data from [Frei et al. \(1996\)](#) described above. Our approach will be to assess (in various ways) the extent to which the A & C parameters for local galaxies of known type are likely to shift when they are placed at larger redshift. Statistically, over a number of galaxies, we then compare the distribution of classes, as viewed at a given redshift, with the intrinsic value at $z \approx 0$ to determine a ‘misclassification fraction’ for each type which is a function of redshift. The method assumes that the Frei et al galaxies of a given type are representative. Note, in particular, that we do not require an accurate sampling of the local morphological mix. Indeed, in principle, only a few representative galaxies of each type are required. Our goal and procedure differs from the synthetic creation of faint no-evolution samples (e.g. [Bouwens et al. 1998a,b](#)) for which the Frei et al sample is not well suited.

3.5.1 Wavelength-dependent Trends

The simplest test we can perform is to measure the A and C parameters defined earlier in both the R and B_J -band images of the Frei et al galaxies, the distribution in the AC plane for the R -band images is shown in [Figure 3.10](#). Since our faint HST images are taken with the F814W filter, we effectively see the R band at a redshift of 0.2 and the B_J band at a redshift of 0.87. The shift in A and C across the Frei et al sample is thus a crude but simple measure of the shift arising from the bandpass effect over much of the redshift range sampled.

In the top panel of [Figure 3.12](#) we plot the change in asymmetry A observed using the R and B_J images of the same local galaxy. Late-type systems are denoted by filled circles and, as expected, there is a clear trend for such systems to have larger asymmetry at shorter wavelengths where the star-formation signatures are more irregular. However, in quantitative detail, the size of the effect is quite small. The corresponding shift in concentration C , shown in the bottom panel, is somewhat larger. The change in C required for a galaxy to cross the AC -peculiar and AC -elliptical boundary is also indicated on the figure; for the AC -peculiar this is strongly dependent on asymmetry.

This simple comparison indicates that only a small fraction of the Frei *et al* galaxies would cross into the areas defining different morphological types. However, the comparison is crude and takes no account of more complex sampling and noise effects.

3.5.2 Results from Detailed Simulations

To quantify the redshift biases more precisely, we decided to incorporate each of the effects that combine to give the final HST appearance. The method adopted is based on that described in more detail by [Abraham et al. \(1997\)](#) and can be summarised as follows:

- For each pixel we calculated the $B_J - R$ colours; to avoid edge effects we smoothed the images slightly before calculating the colours.
- The pixel $B_J - R$ colours were then used to select an SED to each pixel (cf. the discussion in [2.4](#)). This SED was then used to determine the k -correction applicable

FIGURE 3.12: *Top panel: The change in asymmetry A between the R and B_J images of the local Frei et al galaxies. Filled circles denote late type systems for which the trends are somewhat more pronounced. Bottom Panel: as above for the concentration C illustrating the effect of the bandshifting effects on A&C classifications. Labelled lines define the boundary where the change in C would move an object to a different class as indicated (assuming A is at the median of the distribution)*

to each pixel.

- The final step was to rebin the image, using the known and wanted redshift, applying $(1+z)^3$ surface brightness dimming and adding noise corresponding to the characteristics of WFPC-2 for our mean exposure time.

For each redshift we only analysed those redshifted galaxies that would have been selected into either the CFRS or LDSS-2 redshift surveys. Beyond $z \simeq 0.9$, however, only a few of the Frei et al galaxies would be seen; this is because the bright galaxies in the Frei sample tend to be Sab galaxies whose k -corrections are substantial when the 4000Å break enters the I-filter (see also the discussion in section 3.4.3 and in particular Figure 3.11). This leads to a small number of galaxies, and hence an increase in the statistical uncertainties. To rectify this problem, we adopted an alternative approach. We selected the Frei et al galaxies that would have had $I_{AB} < 23.50$, i.e. one magnitude too faint, and brightened these galaxies so that they fell within our selection criteria. This led to an average brightening of $\langle M_B \rangle \approx 1.5$ magnitudes, and kept $M_B \geq -22.5$. This enabled us to get a satisfactory number of objects without introducing any over-luminous objects. Provided the morphological characteristics do not vary significantly over this small luminosity range (cf. Figure 3.2), this should not affect our conclusions.

The aim of the detailed simulations is to determine that fraction of a given type of Frei et al galaxy which *appears* to be of a different morphological type (as measured by A and C) at a chosen redshift z . For convenience we will denote the number of objects in a given category by N with superscript 'obs' for the observed number and no superscript for the true number in that class. We connect these two numbers via a drift coefficient, \mathcal{D}_{XY} which characterises the drift from category X to category Y , defined as

$$\mathcal{D}_{XY} = \frac{N_{X \rightarrow Y}}{N_X}, \quad (3.8)$$

where $N_{X \rightarrow Y}$ is the number of objects of class X that are classed as Y at a higher redshift. From the simulations we can estimate \mathcal{D}_{XY} for various redshifts.

This methodology is similar to that of the k -correction applied to convert an observed magnitude into a rest-frame value. The ultimate aim here is to recover the *rest-frame morphology*. Although the analogy fails in detail because of the added complications of distance-dependent resampling and surface brightness dimming, our simulations indicate that these are second order effects. If the central concentration is corrected for surface brightness effects as described above, the dominant cause of a migration to a different morphological type is the pixel-by-pixel k -correction.

The analogy with the k -correction suggests two approaches for analysing our data. Given we have R -band images of the Frei galaxies and the local morphological studies are done in B , it seems natural to correct our HST morphologies to those appropriate for the rest-frame B_J -band. As we observe this rest wavelength directly at $z \approx 0.9$, the corrections would be small at high redshift but larger at low redshift. A problem with this approach is that our benchmark sample is not ideal for studying the morphological shifts at the low luminosities appropriate for the nearby objects, due to the low number of faint galaxies.

(a) The shift in C as determined by the simulations with the correction factor defined in Equation (3.5) overplotted as a solid line. The filled circles mark the average of the distribution at those redshifts

(b) The shift in the classification angle determined from the simulations of the Frei et al. galaxies as described in the text. The upper panel show the distribution after the correction to C defined in the above plot is applied, whereas the bottom panel show the distribution before correction of C . The dashed histogram in each panel is the distribution at $z = 0$.

FIGURE 3.13: *The effect of redshift on the automated classification methods*

FIGURE 3.14: An illustration of the calculation of the drift coefficients, the resulting drift coefficients are shown with the arrows showing what changes in the AC plane affect what coefficient. The open symbols represent higher redshift points.

The alternative approach is to correct our HST morphologies to rest frame R assuming, as seems reasonable, that the morphology changes little between rest-frame I and R . In this case, nearby, intrinsically faint galaxies, need no correction and although a larger correction is needed at high redshifts, in this case the Frei *et al* sample is well matched in luminosity. Neither approach is perfect, but we consider the latter to be more reliable until larger, multiband local samples are available which would allow us to correct morphologies at lower redshift. We will therefore concentrate on applying corrections to rest-frame R morphologies (although, for completeness, we tabulate drift coefficients appropriate for rest-frame B_J).

The results of this exercise are summarised in Table 3.2. The numbers here are consistent with the earlier discussion of the change in C from the R to B_J -band images but we consider the results to be more reliable given the more detailed treatment of the effects of sampling and background noise. In particular, the drift coefficients calculated from R to B_J band images agree excellently with the ones found here. We can relate the observed number of objects in class X to the true number through

$$N_X^{obs} = N_X + \sum_{Y \neq X}^{Classes} N_Y \mathcal{D}_{YX} - N_X \sum_{Y \neq X}^{Classes} \mathcal{D}_{XY}. \quad (3.9)$$

Equations (3.9) can be readily solved given the observed number of galaxies.

Broadly speaking, there are two dominant effects. First there is an apparent migration from AC-spirals to AC-peculiar if we classify galaxies from observed I -band images. This

TABLE 3.2: *The movement of Frei galaxies in the AC plane*

	AC-E	AC-S	AC-P	\mathcal{D}_{SP}^b	\mathcal{D}_{PS}^b	\mathcal{D}_{SE}^b	\mathcal{D}_{ES}^b
Drift coefficients for corrections to R rest frame morphologies							
$z=0.0^a$	33	41	5	0	0	0	0
$z=0.2$	29	30	6	0	0	0.06 ± 0.04	0
$z=0.7$	30	29	5	0.13 ± 0.09	0	0.20 ± 0.12	0.32 ± 0.13
$z=0.9$	16	22	6	0.24 ± 0.11	0	0.10 ± 0.07	0.33 ± 0.12
Drift coefficients for corrections to B_J rest frame morphologies							
$z=0.0^a$	33	41	5	0	0.67 ± 0.21	0.29 ± 0.08	0.05 ± 0.05
$z=0.2$	29	30	6	0	0.67 ± 0.24	0.35 ± 0.10	0
$z=0.7$	30	29	5	0.05 ± 0.05	0.67 ± 0.47	0.43 ± 0.14	0.30 ± 0.17
$z=0.9$	16	22	6	0.07 ± 0.05	0.20 ± 0.20	0.26 ± 0.10	0.21 ± 0.12

^aThe numbers for $z = 0$ are for all Frei galaxies.

^bThe errors are 1σ Poisson errors.

bias is expected to occur also for eyeball classification. At $z = 0.7$ we can expect only 13% of the AC-spirals to be misclassified as AC-peculiar, whereas by $z = 0.9$ the misclassified fraction grows to 24%. Presumably this trend continues at higher redshift. Due to the restrictions in the local dataset discussed above, we have not extended the simulations beyond $z = 0.9$. U-band imaging would be highly desirable to quantify bandshifting beyond $z = 1$ (see also [Hibbard & Vacca 1997](#))

Secondly there is a strong trend for AC-ellipticals to migrate into the AC-spiral category. The net result is somewhat less clear as there is also a drift in the opposite sense (from AC-S into AC-E) due to random measurement errors on C where the boundary is nearly vertical.

From the errors in Table 3.2 it is evident that the drift coefficients are uncertain. A larger sample of calibrating galaxies is clearly required to make more precise statements about the drift coefficients. Nevertheless, the principal conclusion of the simulations is a reasonably precise measure of the proportion of high redshift AC-peculiar which are likely to be genuine spiral galaxies. The mixture of regular spirals and spheroidal galaxies should be faithfully observed with HST out to redshifts $z \simeq 1$, however with a likely loss of AC-E at high redshift which might be able to make up for the loss of AC-spirals to the AC-P category.

3.6 Sample properties

In order to determine whether the morphological mixture is robustly estimated, we compared our classifications with that for the larger MDS survey ([Abraham et al. 1996b](#); [Glazebrook et al. 1995](#)). The simplest comparison is to plot the morphological mix from field to field and compare that with the corresponding for the MDS survey. The numbers are given in Table 3.3 and is compared with the mixture found in the MDS survey in Figure 3.15 and shows

TABLE 3.3: *Morphological mixture from field to field*

Field	E	S	I	Compact
03hr	30.19	50.94	16.98	1.89
10hr	28.75	50.00	12.50	8.75
13hr	21.62	40.54	18.92	18.92
14hr	25.58	48.84	22.09	3.49
22hr	25.71	45.71	22.86	5.71
Total	26.89	47.64	18.40	7.08
MDS	20.82	46.39	26.80	5.98

FIGURE 3.15: *The morphological mixture from field to field. The filled circles shows the mixture for the HST survey as a whole. The filled triangles are for the MDS survey as classed by Richard Ellis and the filled squares are the mixture determined by Sidney van den Bergh, see [Abraham et al. \(1996b\)](#) for details. The points are slightly offset for clarity. The discrepant point for compact objects is the 13hr LDSS field which includes objects from the LDSS-1 survey targeting compact objects.*

TABLE 3.4: *The geometric completion of CFRS fields*

Field	$N_{\text{spec}}^{\text{a}}$	$N_{\text{phot}}^{\text{b}}$	Field	$N_{\text{spec}}^{\text{a}}$	$N_{\text{phot}}^{\text{b}}$
cfrs_03_1	16	29	cfrs_03_2	17	25
cfrs_03_3	20	38	cfrs_03_4	18	36
cfrs_03_5	7	37	cfrs_10_1	22	51
cfrs_10_2	16	46	cfrs_10_3	30	56
cfrs_14_1	25	27	cfrs_14_2	14	21
groth_14_1	18	29	groth_14_2	18	24
groth_14_3	25	28	groth_14_4	25	27
groth_14_5	23	36	groth_14_6	13	26
cfrs_22_1	12	39	cfrs_22_2	17	46
cfrs_22_3	21	43			

^aThe number of objects inside the HST field that have been targeted spectroscopically

^bThe number of objects inside the HST field that are within the CFRS selection criteria

good consistency from field to field. There is however a noticeable scatter in the fraction of compact objects in the 13hr and to a lesser degree 10hr fields. This is to be expected as these are the fields where there are objects from the LDSS-1b (see page 17) survey for compact objects. If these objects are taken out of the consideration the relative composition of compact objects is fully consistent from field to field. Compared with the MDS it is clear that there is a somewhat lower fraction of galaxies classed as peculiars in the present sample.

The lower abundance of peculiars could be a consequence of a more conservative approach to classification since the MDS survey was a first look at these galaxies. To check that this difference does not have a significant magnitude trend we have compared the morphologically segregated $N(m)$ for our sample with that for the MDS survey. Since the MDS survey is I -selected, we can only compare it with that subset of our galaxies drawn from the CFRS survey. As the CFRS survey did not target all objects lying between the photometric limits, we must correct for those objects that are in the HST field within the magnitude limits which were not targeted spectroscopically. We have done this by multiplying the counts in each field with the ratio of photometrically to spectroscopically observed objects for each HST frame, these are given in Table 3.4. The final $N(m)$ is compared with the MDS counts in Figure 3.16.

It is clear from this figure that the number counts are in good agreement with no evidence for systematic differences in the classification of galaxies with magnitude. The integrated counts also agree very well. This is consistent with the hypothesis that the lower number of peculiar galaxies here is due to the classification adopted here being more conservative.

FIGURE 3.16: Number magnitude counts for the survey (filled circles) compared with those from the larger MDS survey (open triangles). Error bars are Poissonian (Gehrels 1986). In this plot the tadpoles have been grouped with the peculiars.

FIGURE 3.17: *The correlation between the final eyeball classifications and the machine classification. The symbols have the same meaning as in Figure 3.4. The few points that show A&C class different from 1,4,6 are objects that could not be classified using A&C.*

3.6.1 Contrasting the eyeball and automated classifications

Above we have dealt with the possible biases in the automated classifications as a function of redshift. As mentioned above, this exercise is much more difficult to carry through for eyeball classifications, for this reason and also because there is not a perfect correlation between eyeball and machine classifications it is very interesting to contrast the results obtained using these two classification methods. A fuller discussion of this and comparison with classifications based on colours and bulge-to-disk ratio will be presented in the next chapter.

Before any further discussion, it is important to check how the eyeball and machine classifications compare. One way to do this is to plot correlation matrices, similar to Figure 3.4, as shown in Figure 3.17. From this figure it is evident that the machine and eyeball classifications actually correlate very well, which is just a different way to visualise the agreement in the A&C plane diagram.

One of the most interesting questions is how the two classifications compare as a function of redshift. A particularly intriguing aspect of Figure 3.17 is the fact that almost all objects classed as A&C irregulars are classified as peculiar in the eyeball classification. The reverse is however not true, and it is important to consider whether this is due to redshifting effects

It is therefore useful to look at the difference between the automated and visual classifications as a function of redshift. The result of this exercise is shown in Figure 3.18(a). It is clear from this figure that the A&C-classification on average assigns an earlier type to galaxies⁶, but there is no sign of a trend with redshift.

⁶A similar difference is evident between the two classifiers in the MDS work (Abraham et al. 1996b)

FIGURE 3.18: *Eyeball classifications versus A&C classifications as a function of redshift (the bins in redshift are 0.2)*

To ascertain that this is the case for the different classes in isolation, we plot the fraction of galaxies classed visually as peculiar that also are classed as peculiar by the automated classification system in Figure 3.18(b). This plot is remarkable in that it shows no systematic trend for visual classifications to classify galaxies as peculiar at higher redshift, despite the fact that the classifications were made without reference to the redshift of the galaxies. This does lend substantial support to the notion that out to $z = 1$, visual classifications of bright galaxies from HST images do not suffer from systematic biases.

This absence of any redshift dependent difference between the automated and visual classifications leads us to the conclusion that the discrepancies in Figure 3.17 are solely due to us adopting a conservative location for the AC-peculiar boundary. This will lead us to underestimate the number of peculiar galaxies as compared with eyeball classifications, but the absence of any trend with redshift strengthens our belief that our results will be robust to any redshift dependent biases out to $z = 1$.

3.7 The Yerkes classification revisited

One of the most interesting aspects of Morgan's classification system was his attempt to connect spectral properties with morphological measures. This work established that galaxies with very high central concentration of light in general were dominated by the light from K stars, in other words they were red. At the other extreme were irregular galaxies which were generally blue and dominated by the light from stars with spectral types A5 and younger.

Later work has shown that these correlations seem to be rather strong and this suggests that elliptical galaxies have evolved stellar populations, with little or no current star forma-

FIGURE 3.19: *The distribution of galaxies in the C vs. spectral type plane. Top left: The distribution of all galaxies with measured A and C and known redshift. The other panels show interpolated 2D histograms of subpopulations from the top left corner. Note in particular the spread in spectral class for spiral galaxies and the elliptical galaxies with late type spectral class.*

tion, whereas irregular galaxies have strong blue continua characteristic of star forming region, and are hence believed to be undergoing significant current star formation (Kennicutt 1998a). It is therefore interesting to study the distribution of the sample here in the C versus spectral type plane. The spectral type is here taken to be the best-fit spectral class as defined in Equation (2.13). The result is shown in Figure 3.19. It is evident here that the distributions are mostly as one would expect, with peculiar galaxies being of a blue spectral type and low central concentration, spiral galaxies having a large range in spectral types with the most centrally concentrated spirals typically having redder type spectra and elliptical galaxies typically being red and centrally concentrated. It is however intriguing to see that there are a few fairly blue elliptical galaxies with similar central concentration to the red ones. These galaxies could be young elliptical galaxies (Abraham et al. 1999), but when studying individual galaxies we should be careful about what we mean with elliptical galaxies. In particular it is a surface-brightness dependent statement, as strikingly illustrated for NGC 7252 by Schweizer (1982), where a shallow exposure shows an essentially normal elliptical galaxy, but in a deeper image spectacular tidal tails show up. This issue becomes more important at higher redshift because of surface brightness dimming and the higher rate of mergers at earlier times (Le Fèvre et al. 1999). In view of these problems it might be that the most sensible assumption would be to classify galaxies according to their central light distribution and whether this follows an $R^{1/4}$ law or not. We will not have much to say about these issues here, but they are expanded upon in Schade et al. (1999). Instead we will now turn to the overall properties of the sample, and in this more statistical approach the actual “correctness” of the morphological classification on an object-by-object basis is less important.

Chapter 4

Evolution of the sample

The previous two chapters have detailed the basic analysis of the sample used for the present work. The existence of such a large sample of field galaxies with known redshifts opens up the possibility of a detailed study of the evolution of morphological types from $z = 1$ to the present. In particular it is possible to determine the redshift distribution and the luminosity function for different morphological types.

We start out by very swiftly outlining the basic methodologies used in interpreting data, building on the useful discussion in [Ellis \(1997\)](#), we then proceed to review the local data relevant for our simple modelling before presenting the results for the present data. Throughout results will be given for both the machine and eyeball classifications. Occasionally these results will be contrasted with the results based on spectral classifications and bulge-to-disk decompositions taken from [Schade et al. \(1999\)](#). Finally we will discuss the results and show that further information is needed to distinguish between different approaches.

4.1 Methodological considerations

[Ellis \(1997\)](#) discussed the different methodologies used in interpreting data and divided them into the empirical and ab initio approaches. The empirical approach is primarily descriptive and presents the data with little or no modelling, whereas the ab initio approaches are concerned with modelling of the galaxy properties. The ab initio approach can be further subdivided in two: numerical simulations and semi-analytic models. Numerical simulations evolve dark and baryonic matter, starting from an initial power-spectrum and a given cosmology with prescriptions for galaxy formation (see [Bertschinger 1998](#), for a review). This approach has only recently become viable and is still suffering from substantial uncertainties in the role of feedback and the details of star formation. ([Bertschinger 1998](#); [Kauffmann et al. 1999](#); [Steinmetz & Navarro 1999](#)).

The early semi-analytic models took observed properties of galaxies today and made educated guesses about their evolution, usually incorporating a population synthesis code

to predict their colours. (Tinsley 1977, 1980; Bruzual & Kron 1980; Yoshii & Takahara 1988; Rocca-Volmerange & Guiderdoni 1990). The major disadvantage of these models is that they have to make specific choices for the galaxy population. In particular the choices of Tinsley (1977) that all galaxies formed at the same time, and that each morphological type had a characteristic time-scale of formation have often been taken as a starting point (see also the concise review by Gardner 1998). These guesses have recently been refined by combining the results of numerical simulations with semi-analytic prescriptions for star formation and population synthesis models (e.g. Bruzual & Charlot 1993; Worthey 1994; Jimenez et al. 1998). This approach was pioneered by Kauffmann et al. (1993, 1994) and Cole et al. (1994a) and extended and refined by several authors (Baugh et al. 1996, 1998; Somerville et al. 1998; van Kampen et al. 1998). One of the primary advantages of this method is that it is easy to take into account observational selection effects when comparing with data and they are also much less computer intensive than the full numerical simulations. Although these models might seem not to rely on the understanding of local galaxies, in reality they are normalised to predict the properties of local galaxies, similarly to the earlier models.

The main disadvantage of semi-analytic models is that they are rather complex, and with this complexity it is also more difficult to make model-independent statements (see the discussion in Ellis 1997). Here we will therefore use a simpler approach similar to the early semi-analytic models. We will assume a local luminosity function and evolve this back in time according to some simple relation. The special case where the properties of galaxies are assumed to be unchanged as one goes back in time is called the “no-evolution” prediction. Despite being unphysical it is useful as a comparison model. The aim of this modelling is not to follow the physical evolution of the galaxies, but rather to provide a parametric description of the observed trends. To pursue this we need an understanding of the local luminosity functions and we will turn to discuss these now.

4.2 The local census of galaxies

In the following the term **luminosity function** (LF) will be taken to mean the number of galaxies per Mpc^3 with magnitudes in the interval M to $M + dM$, and it will be denoted by $\phi(M)$. This definition is somewhat awkward to use if the galaxy distribution is non-uniform (cf. discussion in Binggeli et al. 1988), but the present sample extends to high redshifts and is composed of several independent fields so local density fluctuations should not be important. The luminosity function so defined is also sometimes referred to as the *differential* luminosity function.

The LF has been determined in many different environments, here we are interested in the determination of the field LF. This seems to be well represented by a Schechter (1976) function locally

$$\phi(L)dL = \phi^* \left(\frac{L}{L^*} \right)^\alpha e^{-L/L^*} \frac{dL}{L^*}, \quad (4.1)$$

where ϕ^* is an average density¹ (we are assuming spatial homogeneity here), α is referred to as the faint end slope and L^* is a characteristic magnitude where the function changes from the bright end exponential cutoff to the low luminosity power-law. In terms of magnitudes it takes the form

$$\phi(M)dM = \phi^* \frac{\ln 10}{2.5} X^{\alpha+1} \exp -X dM, \quad (4.2)$$

where $X = 10^{-(M-M^*)/2.5}$, from which it follows that for $\alpha = -1$ the faint end of the LF is approximately independent of magnitude and we call this a flat faint end slope.

The early determinations of luminosity functions of galaxies were reviewed by [Binggeli et al. \(1988\)](#). The more recent determinations of the local field LFs have mostly been performed in the *B*-band given the extensive photographic plate material in this band. These include the Stromlo-APM ([Loveday et al. 1992](#)), which found a fairly flat ($\alpha \approx -1$) faint end slope. A similar result was found for the CfA2 LF by [Marzke et al. \(1994\)](#). [Da Costa et al. \(1994\)](#) did also find results in good agreement with the CfA for the Southern-Sky Redshift Survey (SSRS2), but with a somewhat steeper faint end slope ($\alpha = -1.2$). The two surveys also differ in their determination of M^* , but this is at least in part due to the unclear calibration of Zwicky magnitudes used by the CfA2 ([Da Costa et al. 1994](#)).

More recent determinations of the local *B*-band luminosity function have been presented by [Zucca et al. \(1997\)](#) for the ESO Slice Project (ESP), by [Folkes et al. \(1999\)](#) for the 2dF (2 degree field) project and [Ellis et al. \(1996\)](#) for the Autofib redshift survey. The latter covers a large range in redshift space, but their two lowest redshift slices ($0.02 < z < 0.15$ and $0.15 < z < 0.35$) are comparable to the ESP and 2dF surveys. These surveys agree well with each other and confirm the slightly steeper faint end slope of the SSRS2 LF. The advantage of these surveys is that they sample a region of space intermediate to the local determinations mentioned above and the more distant samples of the Autofib survey and the CFRS ([Lilly et al. 1995b](#)).

The *B*-band luminosity functions are sensitive to star forming galaxies and as such do not sample the galaxy population fairly in terms of mass. To get a more complete census of galaxies it is therefore desirable to go to redder passbands, typically the *R*-band. The Las Campanas Redshift survey ([Shectman et al. 1996](#)), selected in the Gunn-*r* band with photometry aligned to Kron-Cousins *R*, contains a sample of ~ 26000 galaxies. The luminosity function for this sample was studied by [Lin et al. \(1996\)](#), who found a normalisation in good agreement with the Stromlo-APM survey and a fairly shallow faint end slope $\alpha = -0.7$, although this seems to be an artifact of their fitting procedure, as they rightly point out. Later, the *R*-selected Century redshift survey ([Geller et al. 1997](#)) found M^* and ϕ^* in rough agreement with the LCRS², but with a significantly steeper faint-end slope ($\alpha = -1$).

The studies mentioned above are summarised in Table 4.1 and plotted together in the top left-hand panel of Figure 4.1. It is immediately noticeable that all surveys except CfA2

¹This notation is somewhat misleading as one would expect ϕ^* to be the density at $L = L^*$, but this density is rather $e^{-1}\phi^*$.

²It should be noted that in the paper, [Geller et al. \(1997\)](#) claim good agreement, but this seems to be based on a misunderstanding of the LCRS' magnitude system

agree well at the bright end. At $\phi = 10^{-5}$ the determinations differ by a maximum of -0.27 mag (ignoring CfA2), part of which might be put down to differences in the magnitude systems (the two R -selected surveys were converted to B using $b - R = 1.3$). It is also clear that the normalisation differs, with the local LFs (SSRS2, CfA and APM) having lower normalisations than the deeper surveys (ESP, Autofib-A and B, Century, 2dF). This difference is discussed by [Zucca et al. \(1997\)](#) who conclude that it might be due to a local underdensity or large-scale photometric errors. The resolution of this discrepancy will probably await the results of the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS).

It is also clear that there is a trend for recent redshift surveys to have steeper faint end slopes. This is most likely due to the heightened awareness of surface brightness selection effects ([Sprayberry et al. 1997](#); [Dalcanton 1998](#); [Impey & Bothun 1997](#)), which are more serious for low luminosity galaxies. In fact several workers report that the Schechter function form seems to break down for very faint galaxies ([Marzke et al. 1994](#); [Zucca et al. 1997](#)). The exception to this steep faint end rule is the LCRS, but considering their figure 12 it seems that at least a flat faint end slope is fully consistent with their data, moreover they did also explicitly exclude galaxies with low surface brightness from their sample and [Bromley et al. \(1998\)](#) claim on basis of their careful analysis of the sample, that with appropriate weighting the faint-end slope of the LCRS is consistent with other determinations. We therefore can conclude that recent determinations of the local LF have started to agree on the overall shape of the LF, but we are more interested in the type-dependent luminosity functions and we will now turn to these.

4.2.1 Type dependent luminosity functions

The type-dependent LF of the samples introduced above are plotted in the three remaining panels of Figure 4.1 and summarised in Table 4.2. Before commenting further on these plots it is convenient to summarise the specifics of the different determinations of type-dependent luminosity functions.

Stromlo-APM The Stromlo-APM survey divided their sample into early-type, late-type and merged/uncertain based on visual classification of Schmidt plates. This provided the basis for the determination of LFs for early-type and late-type galaxies. Recent studies do not support their detection of a steeply decreasing faint-end slope for E/S0 galaxies, which is now thought to be due to incompleteness in their sample ([Zucca et al. 1994](#); [Marzke et al. 1994](#)).

CfA2 [Marzke et al. \(1994\)](#) studied the luminosity function of the CfA2 redshift survey split into five basic types (E, S0, Sab, Scd, Sm-Im). The magnitude system used was Zwicky magnitudes, and this has proved difficult to align with other studies.

SSRS2 There has been two determinations of luminosity functions split by type for the SSRS2. The first study was done by [Marzke & Da Costa \(1997\)](#) who divided galaxies according to colour. This was later followed up by [Marzke et al. \(1998\)](#) who

FIGURE 4.1: *Top left: Different determinations of the field galaxy luminosity function for the surveys listed in Table 4.1. Top right: The early type/elliptical luminosity functions as determined from the surveys indicated. For the Autofib survey this is a sum over the red and blue ellipticals and for the LCRS a sum over their Clan 1 and Clan 2. Bottom left: The late type/spiral luminosity function, where appropriate this is a sum over sub-populations — lines as for the elliptical LFs. For the Stromlo-APM, Autofib (I) and the colour classed SSRS2 this includes very late type/irregular systems. Bottom right: Different determinations of the local irregular/very late type luminosity function.*

TABLE 4.1: *Determination of the total luminosity function in recent surveys.*

Survey	ϕ^* $10^{-3}h^3\text{Mpc}^{-3}$	$M_B^* - 5 \log h$	α
ESP ¹	20.00	-19.61	-1.2
SSRS2 ²	15.00	-19.50	-1.2
Autofib A ($0.02 < z < 0.15$) ³	24.50	-19.30	-1.2
Autofib B ($0.15 < z < 0.35$) ³	14.80	-19.65	-1.4
CfA2 ⁴	20.00	-18.90	-1.0
Stromlo-APM ⁵	14.00	-19.50	-1.0
Century ^{a,6}	25.00	-19.43	-1.2
Las Campanas ^{a,7}	19.00	-19.35	-0.7
2dF ⁸	16.90	-19.73	-1.3

^a Converted to B using $b - R = 1.3$

References: ¹ Zucca et al. (1997), ² Da Costa et al. (1994), ³ Ellis et al. (1996), ⁴ Marzke et al. (1994), ⁵ Loveday et al. (1992), ⁶ Geller et al. (1997), ⁷ Lin et al. (1996), ⁸ Folkes et al. (1999)

divided the sample into elliptical, spiral and irregular/peculiar subsamples based on their visual morphology.

LCRS In their study of the LCRS luminosity function Lin et al. (1996) also examined the behaviour of the sample divided according to the existence of [OII]. A different approach to the issue of dividing the sample according to their spectral properties was undertaken by Bromley et al. (1998) who used Principal Component (PCA) decompositions of the spectra of the LCRS galaxies to divide the sample into different spectral classes, called “clans” in their paper. One difference between this survey and the other surveys studied is that the LCRS explicitly excluded galaxies with low central surface brightness.

Autofib The Autofib survey has approached the question of morphologically split luminosity functions in much the same way as the LCRS: The first Autofib paper (Autofib-I; Ellis et al. 1996) studied the luminosity function of galaxies based on their [OII] emission and the second paper (Autofib-II; Heyl et al. 1997) classified galaxies based on cross-correlation of their spectra with a template set.

2dF The luminosity functions for the 2dF survey are split according to PCA decomposition of the spectra, similarly to the LCRS (Folkes et al. 1999). The split was done so that their five classes are comparable to the Kennicutt (1992b) spectra of different morphological types.

TABLE 4.2: *Determinations of the luminosity functions for different morphological types.*

Survey	Ellipticals			Spirals			Irregulars		
	ϕ^{*a}	M^{*b}	α	ϕ^{*a}	M^{*b}	α	ϕ^{*a}	M^{*b}	α
SSRS2 (morph) ¹	4.4	-19.37	-1.0	8.0	-19.43	-1.1	0.2	-19.78	-1.8
SSRS2 (color) ²	4.9	-19.25	-0.7	4.4	-19.43	-1.5			
Autofib (I) ³	17.4	-19.42	-1.1	20.0	-18.42	-1.0			
Autofib (II) ⁴	1.6	-20.70	-1.0	4.0	-20.00	-1.4	0.5	-19.00	-1.4
CfA ⁵	10.0	-18.87	-0.9	15.0	-18.76	-0.8	5.0	-18.79	-1.9
Stromlo-APM ⁶	2.6	-19.71	0.2	8.4	-19.40	-0.8			
LCRS ⁷	6.8	-18.50	-0.1	13.0	-18.80	-1.0	0.9	-19.26	-1.8
2dF ⁸	9.0	-19.61	-0.74	10.0	-19.68	-1.15	2.1	-19.02	-1.7

^a In units of $10^{-3}(h^{-1}\text{Mpc})^{-3}$.

^b Assuming $h = 1$.

References: ¹ Marzke et al. (1998), ² Marzke & Da Costa (1997), ³ Ellis et al. (1996), ⁴ Heyl et al. (1997), ⁵ Marzke et al. (1994), ⁶ Loveday et al. (1992), ⁷ Bromley et al. (1998), ⁸ Folkes et al. (1999)

FIGURE 4.2: *The colour-type relation for galaxies in RC3 with colour information. The abscissa gives the de Vaucouleurs T-type and the ordinate the total B-V colour. The large dots show the median colour at each T-type.*

It is clear from this summary that the split into different types has been made based on widely different characteristics such as colours, morphologies, emission lines and overall spectral appearance. A straight comparison of these luminosity functions is therefore fraught with uncertainties. It is however known that colour and morphological type correlates, Figure 4.2 shows this for the galaxies in the RC3. We can therefore expect that there is some correspondence between the LFs split by colour and by morphology. Similarly, there is a correlation between spectral type and morphology (Kennicutt 1992a), and again we expect to see similar trends for spectrally and morphologically classified galaxies (see also below).

The most striking disparity is between the early type LFs. If we ignore the APM-Stromlo LF because of its selection bias against early type systems, we are left to conclude that the surveys which use morphological classifications give rise to E/S0 LFs with flat faint end slope. The colour-split LFs of the SSRS2 has a declining faint end slope, and the difference from the morphologically determined E/S0 function is not due to colour incompleteness (Marzke & Da Costa 1997). This suggests that fainter E/S0 galaxies show a wider spread in colour, and therefore possibly a wider spread in formation history or metallicity. The steep decline of the LF for LCRS galaxies with an early spectral type — here taken as the sum of their Clan 1 and Clan 2, is somewhat puzzling. As mentioned above, their clans are based on spectral classifications and should therefore be closely related to the Autofib survey (Heyl et al. 1997), but the two determinations differs strongly. It is unclear what causes this, but the LCRS is abnormal in many respects (see also the discussion in the previous section). In addition the spectral classifiers are more complex and less understood.

The spiral LFs show better agreement although these also differ considerably in M^* . There are also considerable differences in faint-end slope, but it should be borne in mind that some of the surveys do not separate out irregular galaxies which are seen to dominate the faint-end slope in all surveys. The conclusion that seems to come out of these results is that the spiral LF shows a flat or weakly rising faint-end slope.

Finally, the irregular/peculiar luminosity functions show a consistent behaviour in that the faint end slope is steep. All determinations find faint-end slopes steeper than $\alpha = -1$, and most seem to agree on a value of $-\alpha \approx 1.7-1.8$. Such a steep slope could have important consequences for the abundance of faint field galaxies if it is coupled to strong luminosity evolution (Phillipps & Driver 1995), but we will later see that it does *not* explain the problem of the overabundance of faint irregular galaxies.

It is clear that the type-dependent luminosity functions differ much more than the overall LFs, it is therefore less clear what parameters to choose for comparison with faint field galaxies. In the present work the classifications are mainly done based on visual morphology so it seems reasonable to compare with LFs split by morphology. If we look at Figure 4.1 it is clear that a reasonable “mean” luminosity function is provided by the SSRS2 (Marzke et al. 1998), and it turns out that this also agrees reasonably with our determination of the type-dependent low redshift LF (see Section 4.6 below). We have therefore decided to use this as our comparison model. The main results of this chapter do not depend very sensitively on the exact LF adopted although the absolute numbers predicted obviously differ considerably from LF to LF. The shape of the predicted $N(z)$ on the other hand, is fairly

robust given the rough similarity of most of the curves in Figure 4.1.

4.3 The present sample

One of the goals of this work is to bring together the results of the morphologically split number counts from the MDS and HDF and the studies of the evolution of the luminosity function in the field. To achieve this goal we will here study the redshift distribution of different morphological types and in the next section their luminosity functions as a function of redshift.

These results will be of considerable importance when comparing with models as recent semi-analytic models (eg. Baugh et al. 1998; Shimasaku & Fukugita 1998; Kauffmann et al. 1999; Somerville et al. 1998) claim to reproduce the overall trends in star-formation history (Lilly et al. 1996; Madau et al. 1996; Madau 1999, and references therein) but it is important also to constrain the evolution of the sub-populations to get an understanding of the formation and evolution of different Hubble types. These semi-analytic models are also capable (at least in principle) of taking into account the transform of late-type systems into more regular spheroidal galaxies, the possibility of which is still a major source of uncertainty in the interpretation of the results as we will see below. As we mentioned above, these models are attractive since they base their calculations on fairly plausible physical assumptions, but it is still not clear whether they are falsifiable, and the complexity of these models still makes it useful to quantify changes in data using simple modelling, which is the approach taken here.

In the discussion of the observational results focus will be kept on the subsample of the survey containing objects from the CFRS and LDSS-2 redshift surveys, in line with the comments made in section 2.6. This provides us with a total of 249 galaxies with secure redshifts $z < 1.2$. For comparison the discussion here will feature both objects classed according to the A&C classification from section 3.4, and the eyeball classifications (section 3.3). In addition we will also make some comparisons with samples classed according to their spectral class or bulge-to-disk ratio. It is therefore appropriate to summarise briefly how these classifications are obtained.

4.3.1 Classification based on B/T and colours

Parts of this work will divide galaxies according to their bulge to total (B/T) ratio as defined from full 2D fits performed by David Schade (Schade et al. 1999; Lilly et al. 1998, see also Schade et al. 1995) and according to their “spectral class”, c_i , as defined in Equation (2.13). We will refer to these as the BT and spectral class respectively. The BT class and spectral classifications are compared with eyeball morphologies in Figure 4.3 and 4.4. These show a reasonable correlation (cf. Figure 4.2), although the scatter is large. It is nevertheless useful to look at the properties of the sample when classified using these alternative classification methods. In the following we have assigned BT and spectral classes to galaxies according to the following rules:

FIGURE 4.3: *The correlation between the B/T ratio and the eyeball classification for the sample. The filled circles indicate the median B/T ratio for each morphological class.*

FIGURE 4.4: *The correlation between the spectral class, c_i , and the eyeball classification for the sample. The filled circles indicate the median spectral class for each morphological class*

- We have defined the BT class in reference to Figure 4.3 such that
 - Objects with $B/T > 0.6$ have been classified as early types/ellipticals.
 - Objects with $B/T \leq 0.6$ have been classified as late type/spirals.

This division is in good agreement with other comparisons of bulge-to-disk ratios and visual morphology (Kent 1985; Binney & Merrifield 1998)

- The spectral class has been defined analogously to the eyeball and A&C classes
 - Objects with $0 \leq c_i < 2$ are called ellipticals or Spec–E.
 - Objects with $2 \leq c_i < 4$ are called spirals or Spec–S
 - Objects with $c_i \geq 4$ are called irregulars or Spec–I

where c_i is defined in Equation (2.13) and where the names are chosen because of the correspondence with local morphological types.

4.4 Theoretical predictions for the morphologically split redshift distributions

As we outlined in Section 4.1 above, it will be helpful to have simple predictions of what to expect based on local LFs when discussing the observed type-dependent redshift distributions, $N(z)$. The number density of objects in a magnitude limited survey is given by

$$N(z)dz = A \int_{M(z,m_i;c_i)}^{M(z,m_b;c_i)} \Phi(M,z) \frac{dV}{dz} dM dz, \quad (4.3)$$

where A is the solid angle surveyed (multiplied with spectroscopic and geometric completeness), the volume element dV/dz is given in Table A.1, $\Phi(M,z)$ is the luminosity function adopted and $M(z,m;c_i)$ is defined as the absolute magnitude an object with observed magnitude m and SED³ c_i has at redshift z :

$$M(z;c_i) = m - k(z;c_i) - 5 \log d_L(z)/10\text{pc} - E(z), \quad (4.4)$$

where the luminosity distance, $d_L(z)$, is given in Table A.1 and $k(z;c_i)$ and $E(z)$ are the k and evolutionary corrections respectively (section 2.4).

The k -correction has traditionally been a major uncertainty in the calculation of $N(z)$ and $N(m)$; mostly because the observed B -band samples the rest-UV at higher redshift (Ellis 1997), but as already Sandage (1961b) pointed out, this uncertainty is substantially less in redder bands. The evolutionary corrections on the other hand, are very model dependent and comparisons with $z = 0$ data requires not only a knowledge of a galaxy's *past* star formation history, but also about its *future* star formation.

³We here mean the SED corresponding to the spectral class c_i

The simplest picture is to assume no evolution, i.e. $E(z) = 0$. Although this is unphysical, it is a useful reference model. More detailed predictions call for a physical model of galaxy evolution and since the time from $z = 1$ till the present is between 4 and 10 Gyr depending on cosmology (assuming $h = 0.5$), any assumption of a galaxy's future star formation history is very uncertain unless one has a good reason to assume a star formation history for that kind of galaxy. A good example of the latter is ellipticals in rich clusters which are observed to follow passive evolution at all redshifts out to $z \sim 0.7$ (e.g. [Barger et al. 1998](#); [Van Dokkum et al. 1998](#); [Poggianti et al. 1999](#)) For such a galaxy observed at $z = 0.9$ it is a reasonable assumption that the future will bring no significant star formation and as such it can be modelled with a rather simple star formation law.

Because of this dependence on future evolution of galaxies, it can be argued that the inclusion of evolutionary corrections require an elaborate model for evolution of galaxies, in particular in models with extensive merging such as CDM. This would require a full semi-analytic model. Instead we will adopt a simple parametric evolution of the luminosity function. This does not necessarily reflect the physical processes in the galaxy evolution, but the emphasis here is on making statements on the evolution of different subpopulations from the observational perspective rather than testing models.

4.4.1 Dependence of $N(z)$ on cosmology and LF

It is convenient for later discussion to have a feel for how the free parameters in our modeling, the cosmology and the luminosity function, influence the calculated redshift distributions for a survey with fixed magnitude limits. Some of the parameters are trivial to discuss, the Hubble constant H_0 does not enter into our calculations as long as we avoid using evolutionary corrections which would depend on time, and the density normalization ϕ^* will merely scale the calculated $N(z)$ up or down *as long as ϕ^* is independent of z* .

The other parameters are somewhat more complicated. $N(z)$ is in fact fairly insensitive to cosmological parameters in our redshift range although this is a non-trivial effect since the cosmology comes into both the volume-element and the luminosity distance. The dependence on M^* and α is best seen by forming the ratio of two luminosity functions with otherwise similar parameters. Doing this it is straightforward to see that as long as $\alpha < 0$, a brighter M^* gives more galaxies at all redshifts and luminosities. Similarly, with a given apparent magnitude limit, a steeper faint end slope gives a redshift distribution that is more skewed towards low redshift. This means that if a steep faint end slope is invoked to explain the excess number counts ([Marzke et al. 1998](#); [Driver et al. 1995](#)) it will cause the redshift distribution to be more weighed towards lower redshifts. These dependencies are summarised in Figure 4.5 which shows the dependence on α , M^* and cosmology in separate panels.

FIGURE 4.5: The dependence of $N(z)$ on cosmological parameters and assumed, redshift independent, luminosity functions. The top panels show the dependency on M^* and α for a $\Omega_0 = 1$ model. The bottom two panels show the predictions for a fixed luminosity function but for different Ω_0 in an open (left) and flat (right) cosmological model with $M^* = -19.5$, $\alpha = -1.0$ and $\phi^* = 10^{-3} \text{Mpc}^{-3}$; h is set to 1 in all plots.

4.5 The observed redshift distribution of different morphological types

Turning now to the observed properties of the galaxies in the present sample, Figures 4.6–4.9 show the redshift distribution of the sample split according to their classification by A&C class, eyeball morphology, spectral class and bulge-to-disk ratio. The dashed lines in the plots are the predictions of a no-evolution model. In addition we show the results of simple evolutionary model with 1 mag of brightening in M^* to $z = 1$ which we will refer to as the mild evolution model; this model is shown as a dash-dotted histogram in the plots. In the comparison with the A&C classes the theoretical calculations have been corrected as explained in section 3.5.2⁴. The cosmology adopted is $\Omega_0 = 0.35$, $\lambda_0 = 0.65$, the results do not depend sensitively on this choice.

Focusing on Figure 4.6 for the moment, it is clear that the redshift distribution of the AC-spiral galaxies is in good agreement with the predictions of the mild evolution model, whereas the no-evolution predictions quite clearly show too few spiral galaxies at $z \sim 1$. A K-S test rejects the no-evolution hypothesis at 97% confidence level, a conclusion which would be stronger if the failures are at high redshift which is likely to be the case. Note that this is a statement about the *shape* of the redshifts distribution and it can therefore not be explained by an uncertain normalization of the local luminosity function. For the AC – E galaxies, the data are not sufficient to distinguish between the two. A K-S test applied to the elliptical $N(z)$ is unable to distinguish between the no evolution and mild evolutionary models. However taking into account the relatively large number of galaxies with unknown redshifts the mildly evolving model seems to be favoured.

In stark contrast to the $N(z)$ for AC – S and AC – E which show only signs of mild evolution, the redshift distribution for AC – P galaxies are strongly inconsistent with both no- and mild evolution models. This is the strongest feature in Figure 4.6 and the excess population of AC – P beyond $z \simeq 0.4$ cannot be explained through residual uncertainty in the misclassification fraction applied to the spiral. This plot quite clearly shows how the large excess population recognized from early ground-based studies arises primarily from these sources with peculiar morphologies. Note also that the *form* of the redshift distribution is skewed to high redshift and thus a mistaken normalisation in the local LF would not be helpful in reconciling the data with the simple model predictions, indeed from Figure 4.5 we see that the LF of these galaxies is required to be time-dependent since changes of a static LF are unable to recreate the given redshift distribution. In particular the redshift distribution does not agree with the popular bursting dwarf models, since the models that best fit the number count data show a redshift peak around $z \sim 0.2$ (Phillipps & Driver 1995; Driver et al. 1996b). In general all models with a steep faint end slope will produce large numbers of galaxies at low redshifts, and for the peculiar/irregular category this is not in agreement with the data.

⁴Since the local morphological mix is based on B -band morphologies the \mathcal{D}_{XY} values have been taken to be the ones appropriate for correction to B -band morphologies, but this does not change our results very much due to the predicted low number of irregular galaxies at high redshift

These results are consistent with the findings of [Im et al. \(1999\)](#) for a smaller sample of 143 galaxies. This is not a formally independent result however, since there is considerable overlap between that survey and our data. An independent determination of $N(z)$ for faint field galaxies is provided by [Driver et al. \(1998\)](#) using the photometric redshift catalogue of [Fernandez-Soto et al. \(1998\)](#) for the HDF, and this determination also agrees reasonably well with our results. Both of these studies also confirm our finding that the redshift distributions of spirals and ellipticals are well described by no- or mild-evolution models.

The same trends and conclusions apply when galaxies are classed visually, with the trend for the peculiar galaxies even more pronounced (Figure 4.7), and since visual classifications don't classify galaxies systematically as more peculiar at higher redshifts (section 3.6.1), this is probably a reflection of the A&C classifications being more "conservative". Since we have already seen (Figure 4.3 and 4.4) that the spectral and BT class correlate well with visual classifications, it is perhaps unsurprising that they also show similar trends to the visual classifications.

Focussing on the spectral classification first, we see that the mild evolution prediction is in very good agreement with the redshift distribution of the Spec-S galaxies, whereas the $N(z)$ for the Spec-E is closer to the no-evolution predictions. Since the spectral classification essentially splits galaxies according to their rest-frame colour, these results are directly comparable to those of the CFRS group for the evolution of the LF for red and blue galaxies ([Lilly et al. 1995b](#)). These authors found a non-evolving LF for red galaxies, similar to our Spec-E class, out to $z \sim 1$ and an evolution of the blue luminosity function of ~ 1 magnitude to $z \sim 1$, in good agreement with our results, using a different classification procedure.

Finally, for the redshift distributions split by B/T -ratio, we again see a good agreement between the mild-evolution model and the late type $N(z)$, but the early type $N(z)$ is poorly fit by either model. The origin of this is uncertain, but it might be partially caused by the fact that we have used morphologically split luminosity functions rather than LFs based on B/T ratios.

The problem with all these redshift distributions is that they hide the luminosity information in the data. This information is of interest since for instance [Im et al. \(1999\)](#) find that the redshift distribution of *bright* peculiar galaxies is well described by a slight brightening of the local luminosity function for irregulars, and this is also what we see in our data: the low redshift bins for the peculiar population are reasonably fit by the no- or mild-evolution model for the local Sm-Im luminosity function. To disentangle these luminosity-redshift effects, it is desirable to study the luminosity functions of these galaxies and we will turn to these next.

4.6 Luminosity functions

The preceding discussion has dealt with the $N(z)$ distribution for galaxies, which corresponds to a marginal distribution in the $M_B - z$ plane, and a disadvantage in the interpretation of Figures 4.6–4.9 is the need to assume a local LF and particularly its normalisation.

FIGURE 4.6: The redshift distribution of different morphological types as defined by A&C classification. The solid line is the observed distribution, the dashed line is the no-evolution prediction and the dash-dotted line is the mild evolution model (see text for details). The missing redshift includes objects with note=1 (see Chapter 2).

FIGURE 4.7: Similar to the previous figure, this figure shows the redshift distribution of different morphological types split according to the visual classifications

FIGURE 4.8: The redshift distribution of different classes of galaxies split according to their spectral class.

FIGURE 4.9: *The redshift distribution of the galaxies divided according to their BT class.*

In order to understand *how* the population of AC-peculiar galaxies evolves so dramatically to provide the excess population, and to complement the study of AC-S and AC-E, it is therefore valuable to consider the form of the luminosity function at various redshifts. This can be calculated for the HST survey galaxies using a V_{\max} formalism (Schmidt 1968; see also Eales 1993; Ellis et al. 1996). V_{\max} is defined to be the volume in which a galaxy with a given spectral class will have a magnitude within the selection criteria of the survey. The V_{\max} -method is sensitive to clustering, but with the large number of individual fields and large redshift range this should not be a concern for us. It is also a somewhat biased LF estimator (Willmer 1997) but since other high- z LFs are estimated using the V_{\max} formalism and we are mainly interested in point-to-point comparisons of similarly estimated LFs we have adopted it for the discussion here.

As the CFRS and LDSS surveys have quite different selection criteria, we utilise an approach similar to that adopted by Ellis et al. (1996). For each galaxy in the survey, V_{\max} was calculated using

$$V_{\max,i} = \sum_j^{\text{Surveys}} V_{ij},$$

where V_{ij} is the accessible volume of galaxy i in survey j ,

$$V_{ij} = \Omega_j \int_{z_{\min}}^{z_{\max}} \frac{dV}{dz} dz, \quad (4.5)$$

where Ω_j is the effective area of the survey and z_{\min} and z_{\max} are the minimum and maximum redshifts that a galaxy can be at and still be within the survey selection criteria, defined implicitly through

$$M = m_b - k(z_{\min}; c_i) - 5 \log d_L(z_{\min}) + 25, \quad (4.6)$$

with m_b being the bright limit of the survey — change this to the faint limit to give z_{\max} .

To cope with the different selection criteria in the two surveys, estimates of the b_J magnitudes of the CFRS galaxies and I_{AB} magnitudes of the LDSS-2 galaxies are required. For the LDSS-2 objects we used the HST 3'' magnitudes and converted these to I_{AB} following methods discussed in section 2.4. For the CFRS objects we calculated b_J magnitudes synthetically from V -band photometry in similar fashion. The method was checked for a subset for which B_{AB} photometry was available and a reasonable agreement was found (see Figure 4.10). The median shift is $B_{\text{obs}} - B_{\text{synthetic}} = 0.05$ with a scatter of ~ 0.6 magnitudes. This is sufficiently accurate for our purposes since the additional volume due to the LDSS selection function is small for most objects.

The LFs were then calculated in three different redshift bins, and the resulting functions are plotted in Figure 4.11 and 4.12 for A&C and eyeball classifications respectively. The error bars were determined using a bootstrap technique similar to the one used by Lilly et al. (1995b): 249 galaxies were selected from the sample *with replacement* and the luminosity function was calculated for this realization, this was repeated 1000 times and errors were derived from the statistical spread in these measurements. Bootstrap techniques such

FIGURE 4.10: *The synthetically calculated B magnitude for the CFRS objects compared with the observed B magnitudes for this subsample. The dashed line shows Synthetic B = Observed B.*

as this are known to give useful estimates of errors if the individual variables are statistically independent. This is not necessarily the case for a redshift survey given the observed galaxy-galaxy correlation function, but [Davison & Hinkley \(1997\)](#) point out that in the case of weak correlations, bootstrap methods still work reasonably well. In addition, the CFRS survey uses a sparse sampling technique and we average over 23 independent fields, so the use of bootstrap methods should be acceptable for our purposes (although they might be insufficient for complete, local redshift surveys)

The dashed line in the plots is a reference luminosity function intended to ease comparisons between panels, it is the CFRS $0.2 < z < 0.5$ luminosity function and has $M^* = -19.30$, $\alpha = -0.85$ and $\phi^* = 0.03h^3 \text{Mpc}^{-3}$. The solid line is a weighted non-linear least squares fit to the points, using a Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm to find the minimum in χ^2 ([Press et al. 1992](#)). Since the faint end slope is not constrained by our data, we performed the fits with α fixed. By comparison with the local data of [Marzke et al. \(1998\)](#), we chose this to be -1.0 for the E/S0 galaxies, -1.1 for the spirals and -1.7 for the peculiar galaxies (-1.5 in the high redshift bin to reproduce the LFs with some accuracy). The parameters of the fits are given in Table 4.3, but it is important to realise that the combination of a fixed faint end slope and few objects means that these fits are only useful as numerical descriptions of the data. No physical significance should be attributed to trends in the fitting parameters without reference to the luminosity function.

The dotted line in the plots show the SSRS2 $z = 0$ luminosity functions, and it is encouraging that these show good agreement with the luminosity functions in the lowest redshift

FIGURE 4.11: The luminosity function in three different redshift bins split by A&C-class. The arrows indicate upper limits to the luminosity function in these magnitude bins, and represent one galaxy at the average redshift of the bin. The solid line shows the best-fit Schechter function with fixed faint end slope, see text for details. The dashed line is a reference LF to ease comparison between the panels and the dotted line shows the local luminosity functions from [Marzke et al. 1998](#).

FIGURE 4.12: Similar to figure 4.11, for the eyeball morphological classifications

bin. In particular the spiral LF is sufficiently well determined that we can conclude that little evolution has taken place in the spiral population between $z \sim 0.3$ and the present⁵. The data can be well described by a brightening of the local LF by 0.1 magnitudes between $z = 0$ and $z = 0.3$. At higher redshift a slight change in the LF of spirals is apparent. The numbers in Table 4.3 indicate a dramatic number evolution, but this can easily be confused with luminosity evolution and the disentanglement of these physically distinct processes require further information. In addition the CFRS redshift survey is known to be slightly oversampled in the $0.5 < z < 0.75$ range, causing a slight increase in the normalisation here (Lilly, personal communication).

The luminosity function for the elliptical galaxies is much less well-constrained and no strong statements can in fact be made based on these LFs. They are fully consistent with a non-evolving luminosity function, but we cannot rule out mildly evolving models.

In contrast to the slight change in the spiral and elliptical LFs, the rapid evolution of the peculiar population is immediately noticeable in Figure 4.11 and 4.12. To highlight the lack of bright low-redshift peculiar galaxies, the arrows indicate the contribution of one galaxy per absolute magnitude bin, assumed to be at a redshift in the middle of the range in question and with a spectrum typical of an irregular galaxy. The fact that high- z peculiar galaxies are bright in B combined with the apparent faintness of such objects at lower redshift, indicates that the peculiar category is combined of more than one population, since a fading of the high redshift peculiars by 1.5 magnitudes or more from $z = 1$ to $z = 0.3$ require that we observe all high redshift peculiars in the middle of a very strong starburst that is abruptly cut off (Phillipps & Driver 1995).

4.6.1 Luminosity densities

We now attempt to quantify the extent to which the evolution we have found for the AC-peculiar contributes to that observed for the overall population. Numerous authors (Cowie 1988; Lilly et al. 1996; Madau et al. 1996; Madau 1999, and references therein) have expressed the overall evolution of the galaxy population in terms of a rest-frame luminosity density or a volume-averaged star formation rate as a function of redshift, often phrased in terms of metal production rate since this is less dependent on the assumed IMF. Over the redshift range $0 < z < 1$, these articles interpret the observations in terms of a substantial decline in star-formation activity at recent times (see however Treyer et al. 1998; Cowie et al. 1999). A crucial question is whether virtually all of this decline arises from the rapidly-evolving irregular component discussed above.

We can address this by examining the rest-frame B_{AB} luminosity density, of the galaxies in our HST survey as a function of morphological type. The results of this exercise are shown in Figure 4.13 and 4.14 for visual classifications, where the errors bars are obtained through bootstrap resampling as before. To correct for the fact that we observe only a limited magnitude range, we use the Schechter function fits in Table 4.3 to calculate a correction factor to the luminosity density. It is clear from the plots of the LFs that this

⁵Note that the values in Table 4.2 are for Vega magnitudes, AB magnitudes are ≈ 0.17 magnitudes brighter

TABLE 4.3: *The formal fits to the luminosity functions for different classification methods*

$\Omega_0 = 1.0, \lambda_0 = 0.0, h = 1$									
z-range	AC-E			AC-S			AC-P		
	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}
0.20 < z < 0.50	-20.47	(-1.0)	9.28	-19.98	(-1.1)	7.34	... ^c	... ^c	... ^c
0.50 < z < 0.75	-19.98	(-1.0)	6.62	-19.88	(-1.1)	13.23	-19.54	(-1.5)	4.90
0.75 < z < 1.00	-20.69	(-1.0)	2.77	-20.12	(-1.1)	9.85	... ^c	... ^c	... ^c
z-range	E/S0			S			P		
	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}
0.20 < z < 0.50	-20.80	(-1.0)	5.08	-19.68	(-1.1)	8.68	-20.28	(-1.7)	0.71
0.50 < z < 0.75	-19.78	(-1.0)	6.40	-19.89	(-1.1)	12.00	-20.01	(-1.5)	4.64
0.75 < z < 1.00	-21.75	(-1.0)	1.34	-20.39	(-1.1)	7.58	-23.03	(-1.5)	0.69
$\Omega_0 = 0.35, \lambda_0 = 0.65, h = 1$									
z-range	AC-E			AC-S			AC-P		
	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}
0.20 < z < 0.50	-20.25	(-1.0)	7.02	-19.34	(-1.1)	6.58	... ^c	... ^c	... ^c
0.50 < z < 0.75	-19.51	(-1.0)	4.81	-20.06	(-1.1)	6.01	... ^c	... ^c	... ^c
0.75 < z < 1.00	-20.31	(-1.0)	1.71	-19.84	(-1.1)	5.62	... ^c	... ^c	... ^c
z-range	E/S0			S			P		
	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}	M_{AB}^* ^a	α	ϕ^{*b}
0.20 < z < 0.50	-20.80	(-1.0)	5.08	-19.68	(-1.1)	8.68	-20.28	(-1.7)	0.71
0.50 < z < 0.75	-19.78	(-1.0)	6.40	-19.89	(-1.1)	12.00	-20.01	(-1.5)	4.64
0.75 < z < 1.00	-21.75	(-1.0)	1.34	-20.39	(-1.1)	7.58	-23.03	(-1.5)	0.69

^a Assuming $h = 1.0$.^b In units of $10^{-3}(h^{-1}\text{Mpc})^{-3}$.^c Too few objects to perform a fit.

FIGURE 4.13: *The B-band luminosity density of the galaxies in the survey, classified according to A&C-classification. The filled symbols correspond to the observed luminosity in the survey, the open symbols are corrected for objects outside the selection limits according to the procedure outlined in the text. The arrow shows the effect of misclassification of spirals derived in Chapter 3.*

FIGURE 4.14: *Similar to Figure 4.13, but for visual classifications.*

leads to considerable uncertainties. In particular the fit for AC-P in the low redshift bin is too uncertain to be useful. The corrected values have been plotted as open symbols in Figure 4.13.

Since the correction for AC-peculiaris at low redshift is unknown, one could argue that their rapid rise in the blue light density is just an artifact of the limited magnitude range sampled at low redshift. However, it is interesting to note from Figure 4.11 that we do not see any bright AC-peculiaris, *even though they would lie within the selection criteria*. This constrains the luminosity function for this region, and we use a correction factor of 1.3 in Figure 4.13, a conservative upper limit to the correction factor is 1.5. It could also be argued that the lack of bright AC-peculiaris is an artifact of the classification scheme applied, but Figure 4.14 shows the same trends for the visual classifications which should be accurate at low redshifts. Thus we would argue that the rapidly-increasing contribution to the blue light by the peculiar galaxies is a robust result. Over $z \simeq 0.3\text{--}0.9$ this class provides an order of magnitude increase in the detected luminosity density in a given magnitude limited sample, consistent with their dominant effect of the HST galaxy counts over the range detected by the surveys.

4.7 Spectroscopic properties

The previous sections has emphasised the substantial evolution in the peculiar category. If this is associated with dramatic fading, as proposed in the bursting dwarf models, it is necessary that the peculiaris are undergoing substantial star formation. It is therefore natural to try to estimate the star formation properties of these galaxies. Star formation rates have been calculated using several different methods (see Kennicutt 1998a, for a review); we will here focus on [OII]. This is not a direct tracer of star formation, and has to be calibrated using H α measurements but [OII] measurements are available for all galaxies here and makes comparisons with other samples more straightforward. To that end we also adopt the relation between EW[OII] and SFR from Guzman et al. (1997)

$$\text{SFR}(M_{\odot}\text{yr}^{-1}) \approx 2.5 \times 10^{-12} \times 10^{-0.4(M_B - M_{B\odot})} \text{EW}[\text{OII}]. \quad (4.7)$$

This corresponds to $(U - V)_{AB} = 0.7$ in the simple model of Hammer et al. (1997) — a colour which is representative for the galaxies in the higher redshift interval.

The median and upper and lower quartiles of the equivalent width of [OII] for the galaxies in the sample is shown in the top panel of Figure 4.15. This includes all galaxies where a measurement of [OII] has been attempted (i.e. excluding galaxies where the line would be obstructed by skylines etc. see the discussion in Hammer et al. 1997 for details). The middle panel shows the fraction of galaxies in the different morphological classes that have $\text{EW}[\text{OII}] > 15\text{\AA}$, and the lower panel shows the star formation rate calculated according to Equation (4.7).

The most noticeable point in Figure 4.15 is that although the peculiar galaxies have the largest equivalent widths, they are faint so their star formation rates are very similar to those of the spiral galaxies. The other interesting aspect of the figure is the steady rise

FIGURE 4.15: *Top panel:* The median equivalent width of [OII] for galaxies in the sample, the error bars show the upper and lower quartiles of the distribution respectively. *Middle panel:* The fraction of galaxies in the sample with $\text{EW}[\text{OII}] > 15\text{\AA}$ as a function of morphological type and redshift. *Bottom panel:* The median star formation rate in different morphological types as a function of redshift, using Equation (4.7).

in average star formation with redshift. This is true for all galaxy types, and it is clear that there is non-negligible star formation in E/S0 galaxies at higher redshift. This is in good agreement with the findings of the MORPHS survey for their field sample at $z \sim 0.4$ (Dressler et al. 1999; Poggianti et al. 1999), who report that about 50% of the E/S0s show emission lines, somewhat more than the $\sim 35\%$ found here, but fully consistent within the errors. This is in contrast to their cluster sample where only 7% of the E/S0s show emission lines (Poggianti et al. 1999).

Figure 4.15 can not be used to make quantitative statements about the entire galaxy population since it does not take into account the different absolute magnitudes in the calculation. We therefore calculated the comoving star formation density, using the same $1/V_{\max}$ technique as before with

$$\rho_{\text{SFR}} \approx \sum \frac{\text{SFR}_i}{V_{\max,i}}. \quad (4.8)$$

This quantity is plotted in Figure 4.16, to correct for the galaxies outside the selection criteria we followed the same approach as for the B -band luminosity density, assuming that the star formation is roughly proportional with the B -band luminosity, and ρ_{SFR} so corrected is plotted as the open symbols in the figure. It is clear from this figure that the peculiar galaxies contribute a substantial amount of star formation at high redshift, The exact contribution is uncertain since it is clear from comparing the two panels in Figure 4.16 that it depends on the classification scheme used. The arrow in the figure shows the effect of the estimated mis-classification derived in Chapter 3.

The only other attempt at determining the evolution of the star formation rate for morphologically distinct galaxies, is the study by Guzman et al. (1997, G97). These authors identified a class of “compact” galaxies in their deep spectroscopic survey as contributing a substantial amount of the star formation at high z . A direct comparison of their survey with ours is complicated by the rather different selection criteria as G97 targeted galaxies with $I_{\text{F814W}} < 23.74$ coupled with a compactness criterion.

Given this difference in selection we will therefore be more interested in a qualitative comparison of the results of the two datasets. To do this we analysed the G97 sample using $A&C$ as described in the previous chapter. In Figure 4.17 we show the resulting distribution in the $A&C$ -plane. It is particularly noticeable that the despite the small size we are able to measure $A&C$ and they show a large spread on the $A&C$ diagram. It is therefore immediately clear that part of the difference between the two papers is due to a difference in nomenclature.

This is made even clearer in the bottom panel which compares the star formation density from the present work (open symbols) and G97 (filled symbols). The agreement is encouraging and it is clear that much the same picture is seen in the G97 data, we can therefore conclude that the difference between their conclusions and our conclusions is mostly down to differences in nomenclature.

FIGURE 4.16: *The star-formation rate per comoving Mpc^3 for the different morphological types in the present study. The top panel shows the data split according to visual morphology and the bottom panel according to A&C-morphology. The filled symbols show the observed rates, the open symbols are LF-corrected values as explained in the text.*

FIGURE 4.17: Top panel: *The distribution of the galaxies in G97 in the A&C-plane. The galaxies that were too compact to be classified using A&C are plotted with $\log C = 0.0$.* Bottom panel: *The star formation density as a function of z for the G97 objects compared to that in the present work. The solid points correspond to the G97 data and the open points to that of our survey.*

4.8 Discussion

This section will try to join the results presented in the previous sections to form a coherent picture. We will start with a discussion about the properties of spirals and elliptical/spheroidal systems where the picture is reasonably clear, before finishing with a section on peculiar galaxies where it is much less clear what is going on and in particular how to quantify it. We will end with some conclusions that will point the way forward to the next chapters.

4.8.1 Spirals

The simplest interpretation of the $N(z)$ and luminosity function results, is to postulate that spiral galaxies only undergo fairly mild evolution from $z = 1$ till the present, of the order of 1 magnitude fading from $z = 1$. This conclusion is further substantiated by the study in [Lilly et al. \(1998\)](#) which utilises a sub-sample of the present sample. Those authors show that the size-function of large spiral galaxies, with scalelengths, $h > 2h^{-1}$ kpc, is unchanged from $z \sim 1$ to $z = 0$. This seems difficult to reconcile with a scenario where spiral galaxies grow significantly as a result of accretion, and indeed the results in [Lilly et al. \(1998\)](#) are consistent with the simplest interpretation of the evolution seen here: That the spiral population was more-or-less in place at $z \sim 1$ and has undergone only mild luminosity evolution since.

However this conclusion depends on the assumption that we are seeing a *similar population* in the different redshift bins. And this might not be the case for various reasons. In particular the hierarchical models of galaxy formation predict copious merging between galaxies over the period from $z = 1$ to $z = 0$, somewhat depending on cosmology and that spiral disks at high redshift were smaller at a given mass than present day disks. To test this one would ideally want kinematical information which is not available for the present dataset. An alternative would be to exploit the close correlation between near-IR light and mass (e.g. [Kauffmann & Charlot 1998b](#)), and this is the approach we will take in the next chapters.

4.8.2 Ellipticals

The elliptical sample is unfortunately a bit too small to provide a consistent picture of elliptical evolution. Recent studies have made use of either superior data (e.g. HDF, [Zepf 1997](#); [Kodama et al. 1999](#); [Abraham et al. 1999](#)) or larger samples (e.g. [Menanteau et al. 1999](#)) than what we have here. The results here are insufficient to determine the evolutionary properties of this sample. It is clear from the luminosity functions in [Figures 4.11 and 4.12](#) that any statement about the evolution of the spheroidal population based on these observations is going to be rather uncertain. The expectation from hierarchical clustering models (e.g. [Kauffmann 1996a](#); [Kauffmann & Charlot 1998a](#); [Baugh et al. 1996](#)) is that E/SOs form at low redshifts from mergers of spiral galaxies, and the LFs are consistent with

FIGURE 4.18: An example of the redshift distribution of two independent populations classified as the same. The red curve shows $N(z)$ for a population of galaxies that undergoes rapid merging from $z = 1$ and the blue lines show the local population of irregulars. The luminosity parameters are as given in the text. The solid line is the observed redshift distribution and the dashed the resulting model $N(z)$.

this scenario as well as one in which the E/S0 population has been present since very high redshift.

What we can say from the data is that there are no signs of a dramatic evolution in the spheroidal population from $z = 1$ to $z = 0$. It is however interesting to note that there is more star formation activity in the field ellipticals than in the cluster population (Dressler et al. 1999), hinting that the field ellipticals have a more prolonged phase of star formation than their cluster counterparts.

4.8.3 Peculiars

Finally, the peculiar galaxies show strong evidence of evolution in their properties. At low redshift our data seem to be in good agreement with local observations of irregular/peculiar galaxies if some luminosity evolution is assumed. The amount of luminosity evolution required depends on the assumed density evolution, at face value the numbers in Table 4.2 and 4.3 indicate luminosity evolution of ~ 0.5 magnitudes and a density evolution of a factor of 3 to $\langle z \rangle \sim 0.3$. Reducing the amount of density evolution increases the amount of luminosity evolution, so it is clear that there is considerable evolution in the irregular population at low redshift.

More puzzling and robust is the rapid rise in luminosity density of peculiar galaxies out

to $z \sim 1$. As shown in section 3.5.2 this can not be explained by misclassification of spiral galaxies. We also saw that we need evolution of the luminosity function of these objects to explain the redshift distribution.

A simple model (see also Im et al. 1999, for a similar model) which can explain the redshift distribution of the peculiar galaxies can be found by assuming that the peculiar category is composed of two distinct populations: one population of normal irregular galaxies undergoing some luminosity evolution and another population undergoing rapid merging from $z = 1$ to the present. Specifically we take the SSRS2 parameters for irregular galaxies and let these undergo evolution in luminosity consistent with the observed luminosity function in the $0.2 < z < 0.5$ range. The rapidly merging component is assumed to end up as elliptical galaxies and we chose the LF to give 10% of the local elliptical population with $M^* = -19.5$, $\alpha = -1.0$ and $\phi^* = 0.35 \times 10^{-3}$. We then use assume that these galaxies undergo rapid number evolution with a merger rate $\propto (1+z)^{3.5}$ — close to what is actually seen in the sample (Le Fèvre et al. 1999).

The result of this simple model is shown in Figure 4.18 and it can be seen that this toy model provides a very good fit to the observed redshift distribution. The crude nature of this model makes this agreement somewhat fortunate, but it serves to illustrate that a two-component model of the peculiar galaxies with one component undergoing rapid merging does reproduce the basic observational facts.

4.9 The road forwards

The results for the spiral and peculiar galaxies beg further questions, for both a fundamental uncertainty is caused by the lack of a fixed label to monitor change against. In particular we were unable to rule out the bursting dwarf hypothesis for the high- z peculiar galaxies, although the absence of dramatic star formation and the required amount of fading strongly argues against this interpretation of the high- z peculiar galaxies. This is consistent with the findings of Glazebrook et al. (1998) who used near-IR data for a small sample of galaxies with HST morphology to constrain their properties and found a large variety in the physical properties of the high- z peculiars.

Glazebrook et al. highlighted the potential use of near-IR photometry. One of the most attractive aspects of near-IR photometry is that it closely correlates with the stellar mass in a galaxy and as such should be a better physical parameter to monitor change against. We will therefore now turn to our efforts in getting near-IR photometry for the galaxies in our sample.

Chapter 5

Infrared observations and data assembly

In Chapter 4 we concluded that near-IR measurements of a sample of galaxies with HST imaging would be of great help in studying the properties of these galaxies. This chapter will describe our effort at obtaining such information, with the detailed analysis postponed to the next chapter.

The absence of near IR-detectors with large field of view (FOV) until recently, has meant that it has been time-consuming to obtain deep near-IR images for large samples of field galaxies. For instance the FOV of IRCAM3 on UKIRT, which has been used for some of the observations here, is only $72''$ square *ie.* slightly smaller than one WFC *chip*. It is therefore required to take at least three exposures to cover the HST field of view. In addition the dithering required to improve sky subtraction reduces the field even further. A similar problem exists for other near-IR cameras on large telescopes such as NIRC (Matthews & Soifer 1994) on Keck which has a field of view of $38.4'' \times 38.4''$, and also the newly commissioned UFTI, a 1024×1024 HgCdTe HAWAII array, on UKIRT which despite being four times larger than UKIRT in linear size, has a FOV only slightly larger than IRCAM3 at $92.5'' \times 92.5''$, due to the much smaller pixel-size, chosen to optimally sample the improved seeing on UKIRT.

The availability of 1024×1024 pixel near-IR arrays on smaller telescopes however offers the possibility of wide area images. The Quick Infrared Camera (QUIRC, Hodapp et al. 1995) on the University of Hawaii 88'' (UH88) provides a FOV of $193''$ square which is sufficient to comfortably cover the field of view of an HST WFC exposure. The drawback is that the telescope aperture is small and therefore cannot reach as deep with its exposures. The situation is however improving rapidly and CIRSI (Beckett et al. 1997) is already providing wide-field capabilities in the *J* and *H* band on various telescopes, and ISAAC and CONICA on VLT, IRCS on Subaru and NIRI on Gemini will add to this by providing high resolution, deep imaging of larger areas than has previously been possible. Eventually the availability of adaptive optics on for instance Gemini will probably allow the determination of morphologies of galaxies in the near-IR directly from ground-based images with a resolution comparable to HST.

However the present situation is less fortunate and we have therefore chosen to complement our observations with previously published near-IR observations of HST fields to assemble as large a sample as possible. The first section will describe the observations performed at UKIRT and their reduction, we will then indicate how we have extended our sample using data from the literature and conclude with a study of the accuracy of our calculation of near-IR colours using synthetic or observed spectra.

5.1 The IRCAM3 observations

IRCAM3 is a 256×256 InSb near-IR array on UKIRT on Mauna Kea, Hawaii. As mentioned above the field of view is $72'' \times 72''$, which is sufficient to cover one HST WFC chip. We planned to use this to detect as many of our HST sources as possible in K . Since most of the galaxies were selected in the I band the primary consideration was to detect $I_{AB} = 22.5$ galaxies in K . We estimated the exposure needed by calculating the $I - K$ colour of galaxies at various redshifts and we found that the most stringent requirements were set by irregular galaxies at $z \sim 0.2$, where the colour was found to be $I - K \approx 1.8$ and $B - K \approx 2.9$. We therefore estimated that we would detect virtually all CFRS galaxies if our images reached a depth of $K \sim 20.5$. This might however not detect all LDSS galaxies since a $b_J = 24.0$ flat-spectrum galaxy at $z \sim 0.2$ will have $K \approx 21$, but the added exposure time requirement proved prohibitive on UKIRT, and the number of LDSS objects did not warrant such use of observing time. The exposure time estimated from UKIRT's homepage turned out to be 4860 seconds to make a 5σ detection of a $K = 20.5$ point source in $0.''8$ seeing.

The allocation was of 3 nights, 21/5 1998–24/5 1998. The observations are summarised in Table 5.1 which shows the total effective exposure time for each field as well as an estimate of the depth of the image — see below for details on the determination of this. Given the small area coverage, the observation strategy was designed to target parts of the HST areas with as many galaxies with spectroscopic information as possible. However, the limited hour angle reachable by UKIRT meant that a large number of 13hr fields had to be targeted leading to a complete coverage of the LDSS 13hr fields as illustrated in Figure 5.1 which also shows the final IRCAM fields.

The observations were conducted in standard fashion. To facilitate sky subtraction a dither pattern was adopted with 9 one-minute exposures with $5''$ offsets between each exposure in a square pattern with random offsets between each 9 exposure sequence. Before each set of 9×9 exposures, a one minute dark frame was taken. Standard stars were observed at the beginning, middle and end of night at airmasses covering the range at which the science observations were taken at. These were selected from the UKIRT list of faint standards (Casali & Hawarden 1992), and mostly observed with a 5 point dither with $8''$ offsets and exposure times between 0.5 and 40 seconds per pointing.

Some light cirrus was visible the first night, it can therefore not be regarded as photometric, but the conditions were otherwise good and fairly stable. In particular the seeing did not vary very much between the different frames during each night. This is illustrated in

TABLE 5.1: *K*-band observations with IRCAM3, May 1998

Night starting	Field	Ra (J2000)	Dec	Exposure time	Completeness ^a
21/05/98	LDSS 13A_1	13:44:15.63	-00:10:08.67	81 minutes	(20.15)
	LDSS 13A_2	13:44:15.63	-00:10:08.67		(20.26)
	Groth 14_6 (1)	14:17:35.36	52:25:41.84	72 minutes ^b	20.26
	CFRS 22_1 (1)	22:17:32.73	00:17:53.95	79 minutes	(20.21)
22/05/98	LDSS 13B_3	13:44:18.98	-00:08:18.15	80 minutes	20.32
	LDSS 13B_2	13:44:17.09	-00:07:09.25	81 minutes	20.44
	Groth 14_6 (2)	14:17:33.88	52:26:49.87	82 minutes	20.28
	CFRS 22_3 (2)	22:17:54.42	00:17:16.16	80 minutes	20.37
23/05/98	LDSS 13A_3	13:44:17.48	-00:10:45.35	81 minutes	20.22
	LDSS 13B_1	13:44:15.18	-00:08:30.81		20.35
	Groth 14_6 (3)	14:17:26.33	52:26:34.95		20.30
	Groth 14_6 (1)	14:17:35.36	52:25:41.84	9 minutes	
	CFRS 22_2 (1)	22:17:44.46	00:18:07.29	81 minutes	20.23

^a This refers to the 50% completeness limit as determined by simulation of point sources on the images, see section 5.1.3 for details of calculation. The values in parenthesis are for observations that were taken in non-photometric conditions where no independent calibration could be obtained.

^b A further 9 minutes of exposure time was secured on the last night, the completeness refers to the full exposure time of 81 minutes. See text for further details

FIGURE 5.1: The coverage of an LDSS HST field (13B) with IRCAM3 fields. The IRCAM3 fields are shown to the right of the main image. The arrows on the display are all $10''$ long and point in the direction of increasing declinations, i.e. towards north.

FIGURE 5.2: The full width half-maximum (FWHM) for the standard stars observed by Ircam, separated into days. The dotted lines indicate the median FWHM for each night. It is clear that the two first nights have the same or very similar conditions and that the last day is somewhat better. There is also no sign of a trend within each night.

Figure 5.2 which shows the FWHM of the standard stars observed¹. It is also clear that the two first nights have comparable conditions in terms of seeing and the last night is somewhat better — in terms of numbers the median seeing improves from 0.93 to 0.85 between the second and third night. Thus the final frame of the exposures of Groth 14.6 (1) (see Table 5.1) should in theory be convolved with a Gaussian to match the seeing, but in reality there was little difference in the seeing between these long exposures so no correction was necessary.

5.1.1 Reduction

Since the observing procedure followed a standard n-dither pattern, it was possible to use the standard IRCAM reduction package, IrcamDR, as distributed by Starlink. This was modified slightly as described below to improve the sky subtraction. The reduction procedure was performed on a field by field basis, *i.e.* in general for a 9×9 set of dithered frames. The steps for each such set was as follows:

- First the data was dark subtracted using the dark obtained at the start of the dither sequence. It was found to be unnecessary to interpolate between darks of different sequences.

¹Ideally this should show the target fields but the lack of stars in the fields makes it more difficult to compare the images directly

FIGURE 5.3: *The improvement in sky subtraction using running medians as compared to a fixed median. The left shows the first 1 minute exposure of the LDSS 13_3 (1) field reduced without a running median. On the bottom is the slightly smoothed average of 10 lines of the image showing the gradient in the sky. The right shows an image later in the dither sequence using a running median for the sky subtraction.*

- The next step in the process was to subtract a sky-subtraction frame from the data. We have modified the method in IrcamDR somewhat. Normally a median of all frames in a 9-dither set is formed and used as a sky-frame. We use this technique for the first and last dithers in a 9×9 dither, but for the others we modified IrcamDR to use a running median estimate of the sky by taking the median of the images taken during the 10 minutes surrounding the image in question. This creates a better estimate of the local sky as compared to a median over a sample of 9 which effectively estimates the sky in the middle of the 9 minute exposure. The improvement in sky-subtraction resulting from this process is illustrated in Figure 5.3². It is clear that the sky-subtraction resulted in very flat images; in most cases the images are flat to 0.1%.
- Following sky subtraction, images were corrected for airmass using the average extinction coefficient found on Mauna Kea, by multiplication by $10^{-0.4\alpha(\chi-1)}$, where $\alpha = -0.08$ is the tabulated extinction on Mauna Kea and χ is the airmass. This average extinction was subsequently found to agree well with the extinction correction found below.
- Bad pixels were masked out using the bad pixel mask distributed with IrcamDR. This was found to be sufficient for the present purposes. In addition, frames with poor cosmetics or bad sky subtraction were rejected, a fact which is reflected in the small

²That figure actually shows one of the worst sky-subtractions retained in the reduction

variation in exposure time in Table 5.1.

- Finally the images were mosaiced in a two stage process. First the telescope offsets tabulated in the headers were used to automatically mosaic the images, this gave acceptable results, but to improve the quality almost all images were analysed with the `center` routine in `Iraf` and re-mosaiced. This proved impossible for Groth 14_6 (3) and LDSS13B_2 which had no objects visible in the 60s exposure and the automatic mosaicing had to be used. By comparing with other frames this could increase the FWHM by 0.3–0.5 pixels or up to $0''.15$, which does not affect our photometry noticeably. The frames were combined using the `quilt` procedure in `IrcamDR`. Since the fields in general are at high galactic latitude there was in general no stars in the frames so the centroiding had to be done on whatever bright object was visible. Despite this, there is only an increase of 4–8% in the FWHM of compact objects in the combined frames as compared with the 60s exposures. The final mosaiced images were then normalised to 1 second exposure time.

The reduction of standard stars followed the same pattern except that the images were flatfielded using the median of all images in the dither. Since the dithers were sufficiently large to avoid overlapping stars and the exposures short compared to the timescale for changes in the sky, this gave good results. No airmass correction was applied for obvious reasons.

5.1.2 Analysis and photometry

The first step in the photometry of the images was to perform photometry of the standard stars. This was done using $5''$ apertures using `pho` in `IrcamDR`, and subsequently checked with `apphot` in `Iraf`. The final measurements were then fitted to

$$m - m_{\text{star}} = ZP + \beta(J - K) + \alpha\chi, \quad (5.1)$$

where m is the instrumental magnitude, i.e. with a generic zeropoint, m_{star} is the published K magnitude of the star, $(J - K)$ is likewise the published colour, χ is the airmass and α , β and ZP are the extinction, colour term and zeropoint respectively, all of which we wanted to solve for.

The solution is easily obtained using singular value decomposition (eg. [Press et al. 1992](#)). To take into account the observational uncertainty on the magnitudes measurements in our observations and the quoted uncertainty in the magnitudes of the standards, the singular value decomposition solution was wrapped inside a Monte Carlo simulation where stars were assigned a magnitude assuming Gaussian errors. For each such realisation Equation (5.1) was solved. The process was repeated 5000 times and Figure 5.4 shows the resulting best fits and 1σ error bars, with the error in α illustrated graphically. These numbers agree very well with those quoted as average values from UKIRT, who quote a zeropoint of 22.32 and an average extinction in K of -0.08mag/airmass .

FIGURE 5.4: *The standard star solution for the UKIRT standards. The filled symbols refer to the second day and the open to the third. The dotted lines show the 1σ uncertainty in the slope, normalised at airmass one.*

This calibration is strictly only useful for the photometric nights. The photometry of the Groth 14.6 (1) field was calibrated to the exposure from the last night to correct for non-photometric conditions. The other fields observed the first night were examined on a frame-by-frame basis and the magnitudes of the brightest objects were found to be constant on the individual 9 minute exposures within the photometric errors. This suggests that no exposure was severely affected by extinction and we will in the following use the photometry of these fields without any correction.

Each frame was analysed using SExtractor (Bertin & Arnouts 1996) after smoothing with a Gaussian matched to the seeing to get optimum detection (Irwin 1985). To facilitate the analysis of objects close to edges, the detections were weighted using the BACKGROUND option in SExtractor which adjusts detection criteria and error estimates depending on the local variance of the background. The objects were matched to the HST frames and a total of 63 objects from the CFRS/LDSS+HST sample were found to be targeted by the K -band survey, four of these were not detected in K , all LDSS objects as expected. The resulting K - z diagram is shown in Figure 5.5, where dashed and solid lines show the expected tracks of a $I_{AB} = 22.5$ E/S0 and irregular galaxy respectively. The dash-dotted line shows the median 50% completeness (see the next section) for the fields.

5.1.3 Completeness and non-detections

To estimate upper limits for the magnitudes of the non-detected objects we decided to perform completeness simulations for the images, similar to those used for number counts (e.g. Hogg et al. 1997; Smail et al. 1995; Metcalfe et al. 1995).

FIGURE 5.5: The $K-z$ diagram for the objects observed with IRCAM3. The solid and dashed lines show the magnitude for a $I_{AB} = 22.5$ irregular and elliptical galaxy respectively. The objects with unknown redshifts are shown at $z = -0.15$ and the objects undetected in K at $K = 14$ at their respective redshifts. Open circles are for objects from the first, non-photometric, night. The median 50% completeness for the fields is shown as the dash-dotted line.

FIGURE 5.6: The completeness of the CFRS 22_2 (1) field as determined from simulations as described in the text. The top panels show the completeness as a function of magnitude for galaxies with (from the left) de Vaucouleur, exponential and stellar light profile. The bottom panels show the magnitude measured by SExtractor compared to the input magnitude.

The methodology is simple: simulated galaxies with known magnitude are inserted at random positions and the image re-analysed; averaging over a large number of realisations provides the completeness as a function of magnitude. We chose to perform 100 realisations with 25 objects each. Each object was assigned a random X&Y coordinate, uniformly distributed inside the frame. The magnitude was chosen randomly between $K = 16.5$ and $K = 21.0$, where the bright limit was chosen to avoid excessive overlapping between galaxies. The galaxies were assigned sizes consistent with the median size of the sample and assigned an axial ratio; taken to be uniformly distributed between 1 and 0.3 for ellipticals (E0–E7), and given by $(a/b)^2 = 0.99 \sin^2(i) + 0.01$ with a uniformly distributed inclination angle, i , for spirals. This prescription was taken from the `Iraf` task `gallist`.

These objects were added to the original images using `artdata` and the new images analysed using `SExtractor` as before. Comparing the `SExtractor` detections with the input list results in a completeness assessment, shown in Figure 5.6 for simulated stars (Gaussian profiles), elliptical ($r^{1/4}$ -profiles) and spiral (exponential profiles) galaxies in CFRS 22_2 (1). The detection of simulated stars is 50% complete at $K = 20.23$, whereas the spirals are 50% complete at $K = 19.95$ and the ellipticals at $K = 19.76$. The photometry of elliptical galaxies also seems to produce a systematic under-estimate of the real magnitude. The reality of this effect is however somewhat uncertain as `artdata` actually does apply a profile-dependent correction to the magnitudes before inserting galaxies into the frame. But it is in good agreement with previous studies of Kron magnitudes (e.g. [Bershady et al. 1994](#)), and is a consequence of the extended emission implied by the $r^{1/4}$ -law at large radii.

The completeness limit is used to assign an upper limit to a galaxy's K -magnitude if it is not detected. It is clear from Figure 5.6 that this is a function of profile and we have decided to use the HST morphology of the galaxy to chose the appropriate limit, extended objects are given an upper limit corresponding to the exponential profile and compact object that of stellar sources. Our results are not affected by the details as only very few objects have no measured K -magnitude. Henceforth we will define the completeness limit of a field as the 50% completeness for stars. The completeness so determined is tabulated for each field in Table 5.1 and it is clear that we are close to the expected detection limit of $K = 20.5$. The slightly brighter detection limit is probably attributable to the somewhat worse seeing ($1''$) than that assumed in the calculations ($0.8''$).

5.2 From the literature

Although the data described in the previous section provides a very useful database for deep IR measurements of field galaxies it only gives K -band data for 59 galaxies (plus 4 upper limits). A substantially larger sample is required to perform a detailed analysis. The CFRS did obtain K -band data for some of their sample ([Lilly et al. 1995a](#); [Hammer et al. 1997](#)), but since they only measured $3''$ aperture magnitudes this should ideally be replaced by new data, analysed in a similar vein to the Ircam data. We have therefore decided to augment our Ircam data with near-IR data from the literature, mostly re-measured from the original images to make sure the magnitudes are measured in a consistent manner. We will first

FIGURE 5.7: *The response curve for the HK' filter described in the text. The dashed and dash-dotted line show the response curve for the UKIRT K and H band respectively.*

summarise the additional near-IR data for the CFRS galaxies before introducing the new HST data.

5.2.1 CFRS and Groth strip fields

Menanteau et al. (1999) observed a large number of CFRS and Groth strip fields in their photometric search for elliptical galaxies. For this work they obtained near-IR data in the HK' filter using QUIRC on the UH88, which were used in conjunction with HST I -band data. The HK' filter (Wainscoat & Cowie in preparation) covers the H filter and the short wavelength part of the K filter as shown in Figure 5.7. The reduction of these data is described in Menanteau et al. (1999) and followed a similar approach to the one described above for the Ircam data.

The frames are somewhat less deep than the Ircam data described above, cf. the completeness limits given in Table 5.2. Despite this 195 out of 203 of the objects are detected in the HK' frames giving a success rate of 96%. In addition there is considerable overlap between the frames and it is therefore possible to stack overlapping frames to achieve a fainter detection limit. Re-analysis of the stacked data results in detections for 4 of the 8 non-detections.

Where there is overlap between the UH88 data and the Ircam data we will use the Ircam data in the following as it is deeper. We have however verified that the two give consistent photometry within the errors taking into account the filter difference. For galaxies without UH88 or Ircam photometry we have used the published CFRS K-band data. To correct the $3''$ magnitudes published by the CFRS group, we first checked that the aperture magnitudes measured by SExtractor on the Ircam frames were in good agreement with the CFRS mea-

TABLE 5.2: *The HK' data taken from Menanteau et al. (1999)*

Name	α	(J2000)	δ	Completeness ^a
CFRS 03_1	03:02:51.70	00:07:11.29		19.5
CFRS 03_2	03:02:39.63	00:06:55.42		19.5
CFRS 03_3	03:02:26.96	00:07:07.64		19.5
CFRS 03_4	03:02:42.42	00:13:20.28		19.5
CFRS 03_5	03:02:33.59	00:12:51.35		19.5
CFRS 10_1	10:00:27.66	25:14:06.48		19.5
CFRS 10_2	10:00:40.73	25:13:58.40		19.5
CFRS 10_3	10:00:51.49	25:13:42.98		19.5
Groth 14_1	14:18:01.76	52:31:54.51		19.5
Groth 14_2	14:17:55.96	52:30:42.75		19.5
Groth 14_3	14:17:48.08	52:29:51.50		19.5
Groth 14_4	14:17:41.11	52:30:51.40		19.5
Groth 14_5	14:17:33.39	52:27:49.94		19.5

^aThe 50% completeness limit from Menanteau et al. (1999), sufficient here due to uncertainties in the photometric calibrations.

surements (0.04 magnitudes scatter). Our $3''$ measurements were then compared with the “best” magnitudes from SExtractor and we found that the relation

$$K_{\text{best}} = -2.81 + 1.14K_3, \quad (5.2)$$

reproduced the “best” magnitudes with a scatter of only 0.15 magnitudes. This relation has been adopted in the following.

5.3 Further HST data

To extend our dataset we decided to use publicly available HST data with near-IR photometry and redshifts. The primary source for such data is the Hubble Deep Field North (Williams et al. 1996) with its flanking fields. In addition there are further CFRS galaxies coincident with the Hawaii deep field data (Cowie et al. 1996); as we will see below it is not possible to use all the data provided by the Hawaii Deep Field. Some data does also exist for galaxies from the MDS survey (Glazebrook et al. 1998), but we have chosen not to include these.

Galaxies are selected on HST images with with $17.12 < F814(3'') < 22.12$ for follow-up observations³. Given the tight correlation between CFRS isophotal magnitude and HST $3''$ magnitude found in Chapter 2 (see Figure 2.4(b)), this selection criterion is very close to that adopted by the CFRS survey. We then cross-correlate our list with the published

³The difference of 0.1 from the CFRS selection criteria is the average difference between the CFRS I -band and the HST F814W.

TABLE 5.3: *The additional HST data used*

Name	Exposure	α	(J2000)	δ	IR Filters
HDF-F814W ^a	123600s	12:36:49.40	62:12:58.00		<i>JHK</i> ^b and <i>HK'</i> ^c
HDF-F606W ^a	109050s	''	''		''
HDF-F450W ^a	120600s	''	''		''
HDF-F300W ^a	153700s	''	''		''
ie ^a	5300s	12:37:01.73	62:12:18.04		<i>HK'</i>
iw ^a	5300s	12:36:33.28	62:13:39.54		''
ne ^a	2500s	12:37:03.38	62:15:07.64		''
nw ^a	2500s	12:36:49.14	62:15:48.44		''
oe ^a	3000s	12:37:15.94	62:11:37.14		''
ow ^a	2500s	12:36:19.04	62:14:20.14		''
se ^a	2500s	12:36:45.89	62:10:09.24		''
sw ^a	2500s	12:36:31.67	62:10:49.94		''
SSA22 ^c	28800s	22:17:38.34	00:15:01.66		<i>K</i> ^d and <i>K'</i> ^e

^a Williams et al. (1996)

^b Dickinson et al (not published, see Connolly et al. 1997)

^c Barger et al. (1999)

^d Cowie et al. (1996)

^e Lilly et al. (1995a); Hammer et al. (1997)

redshift data and retain any object which has been targeted spectroscopically. Since this procedure can introduce additional selection effects, due to the way galaxies were selected for spectroscopic follow-up, we will verify below that the redshift distribution and magnitude distribution resulting from this criterion is in good agreement with that of the CFRS survey galaxies.

Table 5.3 summarises the additional HST data with the relevant references. The detection of objects on all of these images has been performed in a way similar to that adopted by Bouwens et al. (1998a). We convolve the images with a gaussian with FWHM of 4 pixels and extract objects with area larger than 30 pixels above a 1.5σ threshold. In agreement with Bouwens et al. (1998a) we find that this strikes a reasonable balance between splitting up objects and clumping objects together.

5.3.1 The Hubble Deep Field North and flanking fields

The Hubble Deep Field (HDF, Williams et al. 1996) has been the focus for intense research efforts in part due to the choice of making the data publicly available. Follow-up efforts have stuck to this policy and provided the community with a large body of data. The flanking fields have been less intensely observed, but a very useful dataset has been made available by Barger et al. (1999) who obtained large area images of the HDF and its flanking fields in *B, V, I* and *HK'*. The *HK'* data were described in the previous chapter, we will here

FIGURE 5.8: *The dashed lines show the selection criteria for the Hawaii Deep Fields, compared with the $I - K$ and $B - I$ colours of the CFRS survey. Note the loss of galaxies with $I > 21$ in the upper panel.*

concentrate on the HST images and the BVI photometry. The observations and reduction of the BV and I images are detailed in [Barger et al. \(1999\)](#), and the reduction of the HST images in four bands for the HDF and F814W only for the flanking fields is described in detail in [Williams et al. \(1996\)](#). In addition Dickinson et al. (unpublished, see [Connolly et al. 1997](#)) have provided deep IRIM J, H and K imaging of the HDF.

We have analysed the ground-based data using SExtractor filtered with a matched Gaussian filter as for the Ircam data before. The ground-based photometry was compared with HST photometry from the HDF and good agreement was found when objects that were split by SExtractor on the HST image were added together by hand. We have in general followed the rule that if a source is composite in the HST image but unresolved on the ground based image, the galaxies have been analysed as one. In the view of the limited resolution of the spectroscopy this is the most consistent way of treating these objects.

5.3.2 The Hawaii Deep Field

The Hawaii Deep Fields have been studied in detail by Cowie and collaborators ([Cowie et al. 1996](#); [Cowie et al. 1995a,b](#)) and is a set of three fields with deep ($B = 26.3$, $I = 25.3$ and $K = 21.8$) imaging. We have here only concentrated on the SSA22 field which contains 18 CFRS objects, complementing our previous survey. The reason for not using more objects than this is that the selection criteria for the spectroscopic targeting of objects are complicated. The criteria were $K < 20$, $I < 22.5$ and $B < 24.5$ (Vega magnitudes, not AB!), which

means that a galaxy near the I limit in the CFRS sample with $(B-I) > 2$ or $(I-K) < 2$ will not be detected. The severity of these selection criteria for the CFRS survey is illustrated in Figure 5.8. Note in particular the strong bias against faint red galaxies in the upper panel.

Given that we only target CFRS objects in this field, we can use the CFRS selection criteria directly and their ground-based photometry. One exception was made for total K magnitudes, these were derived from the published $6''$ K magnitudes in Cowie et al. (1996) since these would be closer to total magnitudes than $3''$ magnitudes. We calibrated this by measuring $6''$ aperture magnitudes for galaxies in our Ircam fields and found that the SExtractor magnitudes could be approximated as

$$K_{\text{best}} = 1.132(K_6 - 20.06) + 20.06 \quad (5.3)$$

with a scatter of 0.15 magnitudes, in good agreement with Equation (5.2) above.

The HST image was reduced using the drizzle technique (Fruchter et al. 1997; Hook et al. 1999) using a pixel size of $0''.05$. The objects were identified on the HST frames and analysed as for the other CFRS galaxies.

5.4 Consistency checks

It is important to check that the spectroscopic selection criteria did not introduce any further selection biases in the sample. As we noted in Chapter 2 this is non-trivial due to the field-to-field variations in the redshift distributions. We will here therefore discuss two distributions, the V/V_{max} statistic (Schmidt 1968; Avni & Bahcall 1980) and the distribution function of absolute B -band magnitudes. The V/V_{max} measures the volume in which a galaxy is observed, V , to the maximum volume it could be observed in and still be inside our selection criteria V_{max} . A uniform sample obviously has $\langle V/V_{\text{max}} \rangle = 0.5$, but clustering and incompleteness might affect this.

In the top panel of Figure 5.9 we compare the V/V_{max} and M_B distributions of the CFRS+HST sample with that of the HDF+FF data. The $\langle V/V_{\text{max}} \rangle$ for the CFRS+HST sample is 0.49, fully consistent with a uniform distribution, whereas the HDF+FF data have $\langle V/V_{\text{max}} \rangle = 0.46$. The agreement is satisfactory, but the effects of clustering renders this test uncertain. The alternative is to use the distribution of M_B as shown in the bottom panel of Figure 5.9. The two distributions shown there are consistent with each other to 64% according to a KS test. To assess the significance of this quantity we compared subsamples of the CFRS survey with the full survey and this gave KS probabilities of 40% – 78%, hence the M_B distribution of the HDF+FF sample can be regarded as fully consistent with that of the CFRS sample as a whole. We therefore conclude that the additional dataset from the HDF and its flanking fields has been selected in a way consistent with the CFRS survey, this allows us to treat the two samples in a uniform way in the following.

FIGURE 5.9: Top panel: The V/V_{\max} distribution for the CFRS sample (solid line) compared with that for the HDF+FF extension sample (dashed line). The two are comparable and give $\langle V/V_{\max} \rangle = 0.49$ and 0.46 respectively. Bottom panel: The absolute B-magnitude distribution for the two samples. The HDF+FF distribution is consistent with the CFRS sample to the same degree as the CFRS subsamples are consistent with their parent population.

FIGURE 5.10: The distribution of colours of galaxies from the CFRS (top) compared with that of the HDF and its flanking fields (bottom). Left: The $B - V$ colour as a function of redshift. Middle: The $V - I$ colour as a function of redshift. Right: The $I - HK'$ colour as a function of redshift. The lines in the plot are from the bottom and up a burst with length 0.5 Gyr observed at the end of the burst, an Irr/Sdm SED, an Sbc SED and an E/S0 SED. All SEDs are unevolving.

5.5 Photometric properties

We will conclude this chapter with a brief study of the photometric properties of the sample, showing that the photometry is consistent with the synthetic colour calculated from model spectra. This is of considerable interest since we in the next chapter will make extensive use of synthetic colour predictions. The aim of this discussion is therefore to illustrate that we can accurately reproduce the observed colours of the galaxies studied here. We will not go in detail as a better comparison with morphological types was given in Chapter 3 and a more thorough study of the galaxies will follow in the next chapter.

We start by examining the optical colours of the galaxies. In Figure 5.10 we plot the $B - V$, $V - I$, and $I - HK'$ colours for the sample versus redshift. The top panels are for the CFRS and the bottom panels for the HDF+FF⁴. The lines in the plot show the colours of four *non-evolving* SEDs at the different redshifts.

We see that the model tracks reproduce the envelope of colours to a high degree of accuracy. All outliers are consistent with the model colour tracks within the errors. What is

⁴There are less points in the $B - V$ plot because not all galaxies have B -band photometry

FIGURE 5.11: *The $HK' - K$ relation for the galaxies in our sample as a function of redshift. The dotted line shows the relation suggested by Barger et al. (1999). The thick and thin and dashed and solid lines all refer to different SEDs used to calculate synthetic colours. The triangles correspond to objects in the Groth strip, whereas the filled circles represent objects in the HDF.*

interesting to note is that even at $z \sim 1$ an unevolving E/S0 SED provides an excellent fit to the upper envelope of the colours. If this was due to additional reddening in form of dust it would require a very finely tuned increase in extinction with redshift to keep the envelope consistent with the non-evolving E/S0 track.

The overall agreement with the optical colours, encourages us to examine in more detail our predictions for near-IR colours. In particular we are interested in seeing if the calibration of the HK' filter system is sufficiently accurate to allow detailed comparison with models. Since the HDF data gives us a large sample of galaxies with deep HK' and K photometry, we single out these colours for a close comparison.

Barger et al. (1999) claim that the transformation between HK' and K for galaxies is of the simple form $HK' - K = 0.30$. We plot this relation for our data in Figure 5.11 as a function of z . To test our routines for calculation of near-IR colours we calculated the colour tracks for two CWW SEDs, and two for similar spectra calculated with the Bruzual&Charlot (in preparation, BC96) code. The BC96 spectra are chosen to have an exponential star formation with an e-folding time of $\tau = 0.1$ and $\tau = 5\text{Gyr}$ respectively. The model with short e-folding timescale has an age of 10Gyr and solar metallicity and is taken to represent an evolved elliptical galaxy, whereas the $\tau = 5\text{Gyr}$ model is young, 1Gyr old, with 1/50 of solar metallicity and is chosen to represent a very blue galaxy.

It is evident from the figure that the agreement between the observed colours and those calculated from the synthetic spectra is very good, and this give us confidence that the

methodology from section 2.4 can be used to transform colours onto a uniform system. The relation from Barger et al. (1999) is shown as a dotted line and differs from our observed relation by ~ 0.15 magnitudes. We would instead advocate $HK' - K = 0.45$ as a rough translation, valid at $z > 0.3$, but application of this relation would introduce a scatter of 0.1–0.2 in the K -band magnitudes due to the spread between models seen in the figure.

The agreement between our photometry and the predictions based on synthetic spectra is reassuring. This will allow us to compare the photometry with extensive modelling in the following chapter. The dataset we will use there is the main result of this chapter, an assembly of 387 objects with HST imaging and K or HK' -band imaging that have been targeted spectroscopically. Of these, 321 have known redshift and K -band detection, with 14 objects being undetected in K or HK' , 34 being stars and 18 objects having unknown redshift. The main goal of the next chapter is to use the near-IR magnitudes in conjunction with the morphological information to constrain the physical properties of these galaxies.

Chapter 6

Evolution revisited

If we indulge a fanciful imagination and build worlds of our own, we must not wonder at our going wide from the path of truth and nature ... On the other hand if we add observation to observation, without attempting to draw not only certain conclusions, but also conjectural views from them, we offend against the very end for which observations ought to be made.

WILLIAM HERSCHEL (1785)

In Chapter 4 we pointed out that one ideally would like to tag a galaxy by a physical quantity that does not change as the galaxy evolves. There is probably no such quantity, but the stellar mass of a galaxy could at least be expected to be reasonably constant or increasing with time. An alternative would be to derive dynamical masses from kinematical studies of field galaxies (e.g. Vogt et al. 1996, 1997; Rix et al. 1997; Simard & Pritchett 1998), but these require large amounts of observing time and also require the galaxies to have suitable orientations. The two mass determinations are also complementary, as we will see below the the circular velocity of spirals is a tracer of the halo properties whereas the luminous mass is more closely related to the galaxy formation process. Previous studies have used the K -band light to study the evolution of stellar mass (eg. Cowie et al. 1996), but as is clear from Kauffmann & Charlot (1998b) and highlighted below, this suffers from potential evolutionary biases since a passively evolving population of stars with a given stellar mass would always have been brighter in the past.

To correct for such biases we have developed a method for estimation of stellar mass using all available photometry and a χ^2 fitting technique to derive stellar mass estimates for the sample of galaxies summarised in the previous chapter. The method will be summarised in section 6.1. These data will be used to study the stellar mass distribution of different morphological types in section 6.2 below. The main question we want to address here is whether peculiar galaxies seen at high redshift can be dwarf galaxies that are experiencing strong star-bursts and subsequently fade to end up in the faint-end of the local luminosity function. We will then study the evolution of the mass density of spirals, ellipticals and peculiars leading to an in-depth study of the properties of the sample spirals before we finish with a look at the relation between star formation and mass for the sample. Throughout, all results are shown for our fiducial cosmological model with $\Omega_0 = 0.35$, $\lambda_0 = 0.65$, $h = 0.65$

unless stated otherwise. The dependence on cosmological parameters is fairly weak but it will be addressed where relevant.

6.1 Prediction of luminous masses from K -magnitudes

With a standard IMF such as Salpeter or Scalo (see Kennicutt (1998a) or Scalo (1998) for an overview), the main contributors to a galaxy's stellar mass are the long-lived lower-mass stars. And although they might not dominate the B -band light of galaxies with on-going star formation, their contribution to K -band light is significant (e.g. Bruzual & Charlot 1993, their Figure 2). This leads to the expectation that near-IR (NIR) light ought to correlate well with the total luminous mass of a galaxy.

Locally this seems to be a reasonable assumption (see eg. Gavazzi et al. (1996) for an application to spiral galaxies), and the advent of large near-IR detectors has led to extensive studies of galaxies using K -band data (eg. Cowie et al. 1996; Glazebrook et al. 1995, 1998; Cohen et al. 1999a,b). One of the main problems for these studies has been the fact that although the NIR light correlates with the stellar mass of a galaxy, the exact correlation does depend on the age of the galaxy which introduce an uncertain correction factor, although some studies try to take this into account by adding an evolutionary correction (Yoshii & Takahara 1988, see eg. Gardner 1996).

Kauffmann & Charlot (1998b) highlighted the importance of K -band surveys for theories of galaxy evolution. In particular the predicted close agreement between stellar mass and K -band light was shown to give a useful constraint on galaxy evolution models. To illustrate this, Figure 6.1 shows the stellar mass of a galaxy with $M_K = -23.5$ as a function of age of the galaxy for different star formation models, using the BC96 code. The main point illustrated by this plot is that most models show similar trends for $t > 1$ Gyr (see the lower panel), which amounts to an increase in mass of roughly a factor of 1.5 between $t = 5$ Gyr and $t = 12$ Gyr for a fixed absolute magnitude, or correspondingly a change of 0.44 magnitudes in the K -band luminosity at fixed mass.

Whereas Kauffmann & Charlot emphasised the close agreement between the curves, we will here highlight the fact that although this difference is slight, it is nevertheless systematic with redshift since we naturally expect high redshift galaxies on average to have younger stellar populations than low redshift galaxies. The question is therefore whether it is possible to correct for these biases and obtain a more robust photometric estimate of galaxy mass by utilising the observed colours to constrain the star formation history. This is similar in spirit to the previous attempts at correcting absolute K -magnitudes to $z = 0$ taking into account evolutionary corrections (Gardner 1996), but we do not make any speculative assumptions about future star formation. The close correspondence does however lead us to use the methods we previously developed for the estimation of k -corrections.

Our approach will follow closely the methodology outlined in Chapter 2. For each

FIGURE 6.1: Top: The stellar mass required to give a luminosity $M_K = -23.5$ as a function of time for different star formation histories. Bottom: The figure on top normalised to the $\tau = 2.5$ Gyr model. The dotted horizontal lines are for a factor of two difference.

galaxy we calculate a χ^2 fit to the broad-band colours

$$\chi_k^2 = \sum_i \frac{(T_{ik} - C_i)^2}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (6.1)$$

where T_{ik} is colour i for template k and C_i is the observed colour ($C_i = m_{i+1} - m_i$ see also section 2.4). This expression is minimised over k and the best-fit model determined. This is an approach similar to that adopted for estimation of photometric redshifts (see eg. Yee 1998 and references therein) but without the maximisation over redshift. The models used in the process are summarised in Table 6.1. The attenuation law adopted is based on the data in Calzetti (1997, see also Witt & Gordon 1999). For $\lambda < 0.556\mu\text{m}$ we use the fitting formula given by Calzetti et al. (1994)

$$k(\lambda) - k(2.2) = 1.17(-2.156 + 1.509x - 0.198x^2 + 0.011x^3) \quad \lambda < 0.556\mu\text{m}, \quad (6.2)$$

with $x = 1/\lambda$ and λ in μm . At longer wavelengths we fitted a second-order polynomial in $\log \lambda$ to the data points in Calzetti (1997) giving

$$-2.9758 - 8.70922 \log \lambda + 9.917375 (\log \lambda)^2 \quad \lambda > 0.556\mu\text{m}, \quad (6.3)$$

with λ in μm . $k(\lambda) - k(2.2)$ is related to the extinction $A(\lambda)$ through

$$A(\lambda) = 2.27E(B - V)(0.44 \{k(\lambda) - k(2.2)\} + A(V)). \quad (6.4)$$

We follow Calzetti (1997) in using $A(V) = 2.15$ which gives an extinction in K of 0.02 magnitudes. The exact value of the extinction in K does not change our results noticeable, even an extinction as large as 0.15 in K as recently advocated for edge-on spirals by Tully et al. (1998) will change our mass-estimates by less than 0.1 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$.

After a best-fit model is found, it is first used to estimate the absolute K -band magnitude, K_{obs} , from K , K' or HK' photometry from which the luminous mass, or the mass in stars, is estimated through

$$\log \left(\frac{M}{M_{\odot}} \right)_k = 0.4 (K(1M_{\odot}; k) - K_{\text{obs}}), \quad (6.5)$$

where k refers to model k and $K(1M_{\odot})$ is the absolute K -magnitude for $1M_{\odot}$ for the best-fit model. In the case of the BC96 code, the spectra are normalised to $1M_{\odot}$ total mass, i.e. stellar and gas, and this has to be corrected to $1M_{\odot}$ in stellar mass. Throughout the rest of the chapter we will only discuss luminous mass unless otherwise specified. It is well worth keeping in mind that this is not necessarily directly related to the dynamical mass. In the following we will use M_{lum} to denote this luminous mass to distinguish it from the total mass.

In addition we calculate and tabulate the absolute B -magnitude, M_B , from the I -band photometry, and the age, extinction, z_{min} , z_{max} and $K/K'/HK'$ -magnitude corrected to UKIRT

FIGURE 6.2: *The distribution in $\log M_{\text{lum}}/M_{\odot}$ for a random selection of galaxies from the CFRS survey.*

TABLE 6.1: *The models used in the χ^2 fitting procedure described in the text*

Age	From 10^8 to 2×10^{10} years in steps of 0.1 in log age.
SFR	$\tau = 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 2.5, 5.0$ Gyr and constant
Metallicity	$Z = 0.02, Z = 0.004$
$E(B - V)$	0.0, 0.2, 0.4 — Calzetti law

K-band. Errors are estimated by a Monte-Carlo procedure as explained in section 2.4.1. It turns out that the distribution of all quantities except the age and extinction are reasonably approximated by a Gaussian. This is illustrated for $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ in Figure 6.2.

Another result which is immediately visible from this figure is that the luminous mass is well constrained apart from a few spectacular failures such as 03.0466 which has very poor K -photometry ($\sigma_K \sim 2$). This has been included to illustrate the consequence of poor K -photometry and in the following galaxies that have very poor K -photometry will mostly be ignored since only 2% of the galaxies were not detected in K .

It is important to point out that the error estimates here are all *intrinsic* to our procedure. They are composed of the error on the magnitudes which in turn gives rise to an uncertainty in k -corrections and colour corrections. These again affect the estimate of absolute K magnitude and hence the mass estimate. This does take into account the added uncertainty in the absolute K -magnitude when it is based on HK' rather than K photometry for instance, but does *not* account for complex uncertainties such as the uncertainty in the local sky estimate and there could also be systematic problems with the mass estimate depending on what set of synthetic spectra one adopts (Charlot et al. 1996). Since the HDF+FF sample has no overlap with the CFRS sample we have not been able to directly calibrate the magnitude systems so to allow for some residual uncertainty in the overall magnitude scale we have added 0.05 mag in quadrature to all errors. In the following we will primarily use the intrinsic error estimates since these should give correct relative weighting when fitting relations to the data. These are however underestimates of the real errors, and it would be useful to have more realistic errors on the estimate of luminous mass.

We should first make a general remark, which is useful to assess the redshift range over which our method is useful. We will illustrate this with a variant of Figure 6.1. In Figure 6.3 we plot the stellar mass of a galaxy with $K = 18$ at $z = 0.5$ as a function of model and age. This very fundamental figure illustrate that with a reasonable limit on the age a tight constraint can be had on the mass. The vertical lines show a spread of $\Delta \log \text{Age} = 0.5$ and the corresponding vertical lines show the resulting error in mass, roughly a factor of two smaller. This is purely a consequence of the slope and spread of the lines. At $z \sim 0.5$ the error in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ is $\sim 1/2$ of the error in log age from this figure, but this is of course a worst-case scenario since the different models have quite different colours at different ages and the errors are therefore less in reality¹. If one includes colour information the

¹If one carry out this exercise for different redshifts up to $z = 2$, we find that at $z \sim 1.5$ the error in M_{lum} and log age are comparable and a good determination of M_{lum} does therefore require a reasonable estimate of

FIGURE 6.3: *The mass of a galaxy with apparent magnitude $K = 18$ at $z = 0.5$ as a function of different age and star formation rate of the model. The vertical lines show an uncertainty in $\Delta \log \text{Age} = 0.5$. The horizontal lines show the corresponding uncertainty in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ which is ~ 0.3 .*

simulations give errors in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ that are $\sim 1/3$ those on log age. This robustness of the M_{lum} determinations to the age determination also means that the determination of M_{lum} is stable to the amount of colour information, since the apparent K -magnitude is an additional strong constraint on the mass (cf. Figure 6.3).

Next it is also important to realise that the approach here uses a discrete set of models, and since a real SED probably differs from those considered here it is possible that this will affect our results. To study this effect we decided to address the closely related question of whether the inclusion of a bulge would bias our mass estimates of the galaxy, since we do not use 2D photometry here this is of course equivalent to adding a proportion of a younger population to an old galaxy. To study this we made synthetic models of galaxies with different bulge-to-total (B/T) ratios where the bulge was taken to be a $\tau = 0.1$ Gyr model seen at an age of 10 Gyr, and we considered two disks, one with a $\tau = 1$ Gyr exponential SFR and another with a $\tau = 5$ Gyr model; for both the age of the disk was taken to be 1 Gyr and the extinction was taken to be $E(B - V) = 0.2$ with a Calzetti law; the bulge was assumed to be extinction free. We then calculated $BVIK$ photometry for these galaxies with realistic errors and estimated M_{lum} for different redshifts and different B/T ratios. Figure 6.4 shows the resulting difference between the real input mass and the mass inferred

the age. By $z = 1.5$, the K -band flux also probes rest frame I -band and effects of recent star formation might be non-negligible, hence the method is likely to require much more careful testing at such redshifts.

FIGURE 6.4: *The difference between M_{lum} estimated from photometry and the input M_{lum} in a mixed population plotted against the bulge-to-disk ratio of the system. The magnitude errors were taken to be 0.1 magnitude. The solid line is for a $\tau = 1$ Gyr disk and the dashed line for a $\tau = 5$ Gyr disk.*

from the photometry with our grid of models versus B/T ; as there was no trend with redshift we show the results for $z = 0.5$. There are two points worthy of note here: the first is that the mass estimates are fairly accurate in average even with a magnitude error as large as 0.1 magnitudes, but there is a shift which is due to the finite magnitude errors thus the algorithm is somewhat biased, but the exact value of the bias depends on the magnitude errors and is typically < 0.08 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ for the typical magnitude errors for the objects. Secondly, there is a trend so that the addition of a small blue population tend to lead to a higher estimate of the mass. In general this means that we have to allow for an uncertainty in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ of ~ 0.10 – 0.15 due to uncertainties in the SED. The only way to improve on this would be to use multi-band surface photometry to isolate different components of the galaxy that have similar photometric characteristics.

We have also tested the dependency on the metallicity assumed, by performing our mass estimates with different metallicity tracks. This effect was expected to be small since K is not very affected by metallicity effects (cf. Figure 6.1), and we find that variations in metallicity resulted in a scatter of 0.08 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$. We have also tested slightly different extinction laws in the near-IR, and different combinations of the SEDs. These changes also led to a scatter of 0.09 and 0.08 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$ respectively. In total we therefore estimate that a more realistic error estimate for our mass estimates is 0.2 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$.

6.1.1 A comparison with dynamical mass estimates

An interesting test of our method for estimating stellar mass is to compare it with independent measurements of masses of these galaxies. There are very few dynamical measure-

FIGURE 6.5: Comparison between the [Vogt et al. \(1997\)](#) dynamical mass measurements and our photometric mass estimates. The triangles show the comparisons with the absolute K -band magnitudes, i.e. without correction for evolutionary trends.

ments for the galaxies in our sample, but we have six objects in common with the study by [Vogt et al. \(1997\)](#). There is a study of the rotational properties of the galaxies, and hence the quantity estimated is the rotational velocity V_{term} . To compare with our estimates of luminous mass, we have converted the rotational velocity to mass using $M_{\text{tot}} \propto V_{\text{term}}^3$ (see equation (6.15) below and [Mo et al. 1998](#)). The results here are virtually unchanged if we use $M_{\text{tot}} = V_{\text{term}}^2 R / G$ with a generic radius of $R \sim 15\text{kpc}$ as advocated by [Vogt et al.](#) The comparison between our photometrically estimated luminous masses and the dynamical mass estimates is shown in Figure 6.5, where the error bars only include our estimated error of 0.2 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$. The scatter around the mean is 0.3 if 12.1095 is included and 0.18 otherwise. The triangles show the same for $0.4M_K$, where M_K is the absolute K -magnitude, i.e. without the correction for evolutionary effects. The agreement is poorer than for the corrected mass estimates with a scatter around the mean of 0.7 if all points are included, and 0.5 if 12.1008 is excluded. The shift of the relation is $M_{\text{lum}}/M_{\text{tot}} \approx 0.97$ for $M_{\text{tot}} \propto V_{\text{term}}^3$. This is in rough agreement with the estimates of luminous to total mass in the Milky Way which indicate that luminous matter make up about 10% of the total mass in the galaxy ([Binney & Merrifield 1998](#)). Since the M_{lum} to total correction is uncertain with such a small sample and also depend on our V_c to mass conversion and possibly varies from galaxy to galaxy, we will only occasionally and only for spirals correct the mass estimates to total.

It should be emphasised, however, that this is not necessarily a test of our mass estimates. If we assume that the baryon fraction in every halo is the same, then our estimate of

M_{lum} should be directly proportional to the mass of the halo. Instead the relation between V_c and M_{lum} can be seen as a probe of the dark-matter content of these galaxies. The errors are however too large and the sample too small to make any strong statements at present, but this is a very interesting line of research for the future.

6.1.2 Selection criteria

The sample here has a straightforward selection criterion in observed I -band. This does not, unfortunately, translate into simple selection criteria in luminous mass or K . This will make it difficult for us to make statements about the distribution of M_{lum} for the entire population of galaxies. Below we will compare our mass functions to independent determinations of the K -band luminosity function to assess this issue, but here we will go through some theoretical considerations about these problems.

It is actually easy to calculate the relevant selection criteria, since we already have a large pre-computed grid of models. We therefore insert galaxies with $I_{\text{AB}} = 22.5$ and $I_{\text{AB}} = 17.5$ into our machinery and derive stellar masses for these galaxies for each possible model. This gives us an upper and lower luminous mass that we are sensitive to *for each model*. The limits depend much more on the age and extinction of the model than on the specific star formation law, so we have only shown the predictions for a $\tau = 1\text{Gyr}$ exponential star formation law for clarity. A change in extinction of 0.2 give similar effects to the changes in age shown. In other words the line for an age of 0.1 Gyr and $E(B - V) = 0.4$ is fairly close to the line for 1 Gyr with $E(B - V) = 0.2$ and so on.

The simplest way to quantify these incompletenesses is to compare with galaxy samples selected in the K -band and we will do this below. It turns out that despite the difficulties raised here, these effects are not very severe at the high mass end, although we probably omit some high mass galaxies at low redshift. The incompleteness at the faint end of the stellar mass distribution is much more difficult to assess however since type-dependent incompleteness could be important here and would require morphological information for the K -selected sample.

6.2 The mass distribution of the sample

We will first concentrate on the overall properties of the sample, starting with the mass distribution of the different morphological types and their mass functions. We will then proceed to look at the distribution of mass at different redshifts. Since luminous mass is expected to be a monotonically increasing function of cosmic time, it is possible to detect changes in the galaxy classes by looking at their contribution to the mass density of the universe.

As we highlighted in Chapter 4, there have been several attempts at explaining the large population of faint blue/peculiar galaxies by assuming that they are dwarf galaxies undergoing a massive burst of star formation (Broadhurst et al. 1988; Cole et al. 1992; Babul & Rees 1992; Babul & Ferguson 1996; Phillipps & Driver 1995; Campos & Shanks

FIGURE 6.6: *The I-band selection criteria mapped over to mass space for our sample and overlaid the determinations of M_{lum} for our sample. The two outliers close to $z = 0.6$ have very poor K-band photometry.*

1997). Although we pointed out there that the high redshift and associated high L_B found for these galaxies argue strongly against the interpretation of peculiar galaxies as bursting dwarfs, the argument does depend somewhat on the specific model. In addition the data presented there did not address the question of what the fate of these peculiar galaxies is, nor what their physical characteristics are — although we did argue that the class of peculiar galaxies probably consists of different physical objects.

The blue luminosity of galaxies is not a very straightforward quantity to interpret, whereas the mass of these galaxies is a natural variable. Although the luminous mass will increase with time due to star formation, this is a fairly gradual process, barring dramatic star formation, and more importantly it has to be a monotonically increasing function of cosmic time. Since local dwarf galaxies typically have masses $M < 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ (eg. Mateo 1998), it follows that any high- z peculiar galaxy more massive than this must end up as either a spiral or an elliptical galaxy locally.

In Figure 6.7 we plot histograms of the mass-distribution of different morphological classes for three different redshift intervals, with bins of 0.4 in $\log M$. In addition we also show the average mass in bins of 0.1 in redshift for the three different classes. It is clear from this that the peculiar galaxies at high redshift are (regardless of the cosmological model) more massive than local dwarf galaxies. But it is true to say that they typically make up the low-mass end of the sample at any given redshift.

Because of volume- and k -correction effects it is not possible to make any stronger

FIGURE 6.7: Top left: The average mass in bins of 0.1 in redshift for the three morphological types considered here. The other three panels show the distribution of luminous mass for the different morphological types in three different redshift bins with a bin width is 0.4 in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$. The histograms all have unit area under the curve.

statements. To proceed further we are led to consider the mass function² and the mass density function. The mass function, ϕ_{MF} , is defined as

$$\phi_{\text{MF}}(M, z; C) dM = \#\{j : M_j \in [M, M + dM] \text{ and class } C\}, \quad (6.6)$$

and the mass density, $\Psi_{\mathcal{M}}$, as

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{M}}(M, z; C) dM = M \phi_{\text{MF}}. \quad (6.7)$$

To calculate these functions we adopt the $1/V_{\text{max}}$ method as described in 4, so that for instance

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{M}}(M_i < M < M_{i+1}) = \sum_{\{j: M_i < M_j < M_{i+1}\}} \frac{M_j}{V_{\text{max}, j}}. \quad (6.8)$$

To estimate errors we use a bootstrap technique as in Chapter 4. The resulting mass functions as a function of class and redshift are shown in Figure 6.8 and 6.9 respectively. The mass density function is shown for A&C and eyeball classifications in Figure 6.10 and 6.11.

To estimate the completeness of our sample we would ideally compare with a K -selected sample. Unfortunately no such (large) sample exists with morphological information, thus

²We will refer to this as the mass functions, rather than the luminous mass function for simplicity, and similarly for the mass density function.

FIGURE 6.8: *The mass function of the three different morphological types as a function of redshift. The top panel shows AC-E galaxies, the middle AC-Spirals and the bottom AC-peculiar. Note the difference in the peculiar mass functions between high and low redshift.*

FIGURE 6.9: The mass function as a function of morphological type for three different redshift intervals. The dashed line is the Loveday (1999) K-band LF converted using $M_{lum}/L_K = 0.8$. The diamonds give the mass function of the K-selected Caltech redshift survey which serves as a comparison sample in order to assess completeness (see text). The crosses are our mass function summed over our morphological classes.

we have to settle for an overall correction. The largest deep, purely K -band selected sample is the Caltech redshift survey (CFGRS, [Cohen et al. 1999a,b](#)) and we used their published photometry to calculate M_{lum} . The mass function and mass density so derived is plotted as diamonds in Figure 6.9–6.11. The disadvantage of the CFGRS sample is that it is from a single field and clustering could affect the mass function severely. In particular there is an almost total absence of galaxies with $0.8 < z < 1.0$, which is not due to incompleteness in the redshift determinations, but rather to clustering (R. Blandford, private communication). This means that we cannot use the CFGRS mass function to assess completeness in the high redshift bin and puts the determinations in the other redshift ranges in question. We therefore complement this approach by showing a mass function derived from the K -band LF of [Loveday \(1999\)](#) assuming a mass-to-light ratio of 0.8 ([Cowie et al. 1996](#)), as the dashed line in the figures³. It is clear that this agrees well with the CFGRS, except in the highest redshift bin, and we will use this mass function when making quantitative statements about incompleteness.

The bottom panel of Figure 6.8 shows that ϕ_{MF} for high- z peculiars is inconsistent with that of low-redshift irregular/peculiar galaxies, showing that these are physically different. The high redshift peculiar galaxies therefore have to end up as either spirals or ellipticals. The lack of massive peculiar galaxies with $0.2 < z < 0.5$ cannot be due to any selection effect, because as we saw in Chapter 4 there is a real absence of bright peculiar galaxies.

The $AC - E$ and $AC - S$ galaxies show a more modest evolution, although ϕ_{MF} for $AC - E$ galaxies seems to decrease with increasing redshift (Figure 6.8). Comparing Figure 6.10 and 6.11 we see however that the strength, or reality of this trend depends on the classification method used.

To study these trends more clearly, we have calculated the integrated mass density in the different classes as a function of redshift. The resulting plots for three different cosmological models are shown in Figure 6.12. The solid line shows the estimates of the local mass density in luminous matter from [Fukugita et al. \(1998\)](#) (see also [Gnedin & Ostriker 1992](#); [Persic & Salucci 1992](#)). There is clearly a peak for $0.5 < z < 0.75$, but this seems to be an oversampled redshift range in the CFGRS (see also [Lilly et al. 1998](#)). We immediately see that the dependence on cosmology is not very strong. This is because M_{lum} also depends on the cosmology and the dependencies nearly cancel. We therefore only present results for our fiducial model in the following.

To address the incompleteness we have normalised the mass-density between $10^{10}M_{\odot}$ and $10^{12}M_{\odot}$ to the value expected from the Loveday LF. Similar correction factors are found for the CFGRS in the two lowest redshift ranges. The resulting integrated mass-density is shown in Figure 6.13, where we also compare the eyeball classification with the A&C-classification. It is clear that the choice of classification procedure strongly affects the results and we will return to this below. But first we will summarise the results of Figures 6.12 and 6.13.

- The total mass density is shown as open symbols and it is clear that it is in good agreement with the determination of the local mass-density. We agree well within the

³Other K -band luminosity functions differs little from this, see [Loveday \(1999\)](#) for details

FIGURE 6.10: *The mass density distribution of galaxies as a function of morphological type for three different redshift ranges. The dashed line shows the predictions from the Loveday (1999) K-band LF with $M_{\text{lum}}/L_K = 0.8$, and the diamonds the mass density function derived from the CFGRS (see text). The crosses show the total mass density, summed over our three morphological types.*

FIGURE 6.11: Similar to the previous figure, but using visual classifications to assign morphologies.

(c) $\Omega_0 = 0.35, \lambda_0 = 0.65, h = 0.65$

FIGURE 6.12: The total luminous mass in galaxies in our survey as a function of redshift for three different cosmologies. The morphological classifications are based on A&C indices. The solid and dashed lines shows the local density of luminous baryonic matter and its 1σ uncertainty from Fukugita et al. (1998).

FIGURE 6.13: *The integrated luminous mass corrected for incompleteness between $10^{10} M_{\odot} < M_{\text{lum}} < 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ as described in the text. Top panel: A&C-classification, Bottom panel: Eye-ball classification. Note the clear difference in the abundance of high redshift ellipticals depending on the classification system used.*

errors, and the observed galaxies in the survey make up $\sim 50\%$ of the preferred value for Ω_* , rising to 95% if we correct for incompleteness.

It is also clear from Figure 6.12 that the integrated mass density is fairly constant as a function of redshift. This might be surprising since the star formation history of the universe shows a strong increase to $z \sim 1$ (Lilly et al. 1996; Madau et al. 1996; Madau 1999). Most of this star formation is however in galaxies less massive than those studied here, and if we integrate the star formation rate we found in Chapter 4 between $z = 1$ and $z = 0.2$ we find that the mass of stars formed is $\sim 3\text{--}5 \times 10^7 M_\odot/\text{Mpc}^{-3}$, depending on the correction factor used, which is well within the errorbars. A similar result is found for the extinction corrected star formation law in Madau & Pozzetti (1999), and also for flatter star formation histories (Treyer et al. 1998; Cowie et al. 1999) since these typically find a lower SFR at high z (e.g. Cowie et al. 1999). We can therefore conclude that the relative constancy of the integrated mass-density is fully consistent with the observed star formation history of galaxies.

- The decline in the mass density of peculiar galaxies is quite evident in the Figures, irrespective of cosmology or classification method. In the $0.2 < z < 0.5$ bin we find that peculiar galaxies make up $\sim 3\text{--}7\%$ of the total mass density *observed*, depending on classification scheme.
- The behaviour of the elliptical and spiral population is much less dramatic and requires more careful study. In particular it depends on the classification method used. If the A&C-classification is adopted there is a clear increase in the mass-density of AC – E from $z \sim 1$ to $z \sim 0.2$ and a corresponding decline in the mass density of AC – S, indicating morphological transformation of AC – S to AC – E. In Chapter 3 we did however note that the classification of AC – E at high redshift was uncertain and classification errors could contribute to the decline in the mass-density of AC – E.

It is therefore interesting to note that if the visual classification is adopted we find a less clear trend with redshift, although the mass-density in E/S0s still increases with decreasing redshift. The mass-density in spirals is however no longer clearly decreasing and most of the increase in the mass density of E/S0s can be explained by the declining contribution of peculiar galaxies.

The correction applied to the data in Figure 6.13 is type-independent, and therefore not suited to quantify the significance of the declining spiral population. We have therefore calculated the mass-density in the mass range $6 \times 10^{10} M_\odot < M_{\text{lum}} < 4 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$ in which we are fairly complete (cf. Figure 6.11), and where we expect only little amount of type-dependent incompleteness from the discussion in section 6.1.2. We can therefore look at the *fractional* contributions to the mass-density in this mass range which should be comparable across the different redshift ranges. Note that the galaxies with unknown redshift classed as E/S0 or AC – E only contribute 1.7% of the total number and are therefore not important here.

FIGURE 6.14: *The percentage contribution to the total mass for different morphological types as a function of redshift and classification method.*

The resulting plot for eyeball and A&C-classification is shown in Figure 6.14 which highlights the dramatic increase in mass density of elliptical galaxies⁴. To estimate the significance of the changes for spirals and ellipticals we performed a bootstrap analysis of the dataset, calculating the slope with respect to redshift for the fractional contribution of ellipticals and spirals. The resulting distribution in slope is shown in Figure 6.15. The likelihood that the slope is flat or decreasing for ellipticals is indicated in the figure and it is clear that the rising mass-density for elliptical galaxies is highly significant, > 99%, regardless of classification method, and similarly for the downward trend for AC – S. But the visually classified spirals are consistent with no change in the mass density of spirals from $z = 1$ to the present.

We therefore conclude that the data show a significant increase in the mass density of elliptical galaxies, regardless of classification method, and a corresponding decline in the mass density of peculiar galaxies. If the visual classifications are taken to be correct, this decline is sufficient to explain the rise in the mass density of ellipticals and we arrive at the conclusion that most peculiar galaxies end up as elliptical galaxies at the present, and the spiral population stays rather unchanged from $z = 1$ to $z = 0.2$. However, if the A&C classifications are used there is an additional conversion of spirals into ellipticals. The latter is exactly what is expected in an hierarchical model of galaxy formation and it is therefore logical to take a detailed look at the spiral galaxies before we return to the overall scenario and comparison with models and other observational results at the end of the chapter.

⁴The large percentage of mass in E/S0 is because we here concentrate on the most massive galaxies.

FIGURE 6.15: *The distribution of slopes for the fractional contribution of spirals and ellipticals, see text for details. The dotted line shows flat slope and the probability of having a flat trend with redshift is given in the plot.*

6.3 Properties of spiral galaxies

In the present discussion our primary aim is to study model-independent properties of galaxies, but at this stage it is convenient to contrast this with the predictions of specific models. We will therefore briefly review attempts to explain the formation of spiral galaxies, including early work in the field.

The first such studies focussed on the formation of our Milky Way. In an influential paper, Eggen et al. (ELS, 1962) invoked a rapid initial collapse of the protogalaxy in order to explain their observations of low-metallicity dwarf stars. Soon after, Mestel (1963) made the interesting observation that the angular momentum distribution of our Galaxy is similar to that of a uniform sphere in solid body rotation which led him to postulate that the specific angular momentum of the collapsing material had been conserved during collapse. This became known as the “Mestel” hypothesis and has been assumed in subsequent studies.

Later these considerations were extended to general exponential disks by Freeman (1970), in a seminal paper best known for the discovery that most spirals considered in that paper had a central surface brightness $\mu_0 = 21.65 \pm 0.3$, usually referred to as Freeman’s law. Another important discovery in that paper was that dark material of mass similar to that of the disk itself was needed to explain the HI rotation curves of NGC 300 and M33.

The significance of a large, dark halo was realised by White & Rees (1978) who combined this with cooling arguments in a hierarchical model for galaxy formation and succeeded in explaining the shape of the luminosity function and typical masses of galaxies. By employing Mestel’s hypothesis, Fall & Efstathiou (1980, see also Kashlinsky 1982) incorporated rotational effects into galaxy formation picture and showed that collapse factors of 10 or more were needed to explain the rapid rotation of discs and the Mestel hypothesis resulted in fairly flat rotation curves. Later refinements of this model were made by Gunn (1982) and van der Kruit (1987, 1989), and still form the basis upon which recent ana-

lytical models are built (see e.g. [Sellwood & Moore \(1999\)](#) for an approach using N-body simulations).

The most direct descendant of this approach to spiral galaxy formation is that of [Dalcanton et al. \(DSS, 1997\)](#). These authors include a massive halo with a realistic halo potential which responds dynamically to the collapse of a gas disk. One of the prime results of this work was to show explicitly for the first time that a self-consistent solution for this problem automatically creates an exponential mass density distribution⁵. They also discuss the origin of the Tully-Fisher relation, and the surface brightness distribution of spiral galaxies, but they do not explicitly put their models in a cosmological context.

In contrast [Mo et al. \(MMW, 1998\)](#) emphasised the redshift dependence of parameters in their discussion of spiral formation. For this reason, and because the results differ little from those of DSS, we will follow MMW in our discussion. But several important results can actually be obtained from very simple scaling arguments. We will first use the result, originally derived by [Gunn & Gott \(1972\)](#) and subsequently refined and compared with N-body results by several authors (e.g. [Cole & Lacey \(1996\)](#) and references therein), that a spherical perturbation typically virialises when the *average* density inside is $200f_{\Delta}$ times the critical density so the density of the spherical region can be written

$$\rho_{200} = 200f_{\Delta}\rho_{\text{crit}} = 200f_{\Delta}\frac{3H(z_f)^2}{8\pi G}, \quad (6.9)$$

where $H(z) = H_0E(z)$ with $E(z)$ given in Appendix A, z_f is the redshift of formation. For any given mass this density implies a natural length scale given as

$$r_{200} = \left(\frac{3}{4\pi}\right)^{1/3} \rho_{200}^{-1/3} M^{1/3}. \quad (6.10)$$

If specific angular momentum is conserved, the angular momentum distribution follows from an homologous contraction towards the rotation axis ([Mestel 1963](#)) and no other length scale should come into play normal to the rotation axis. Hence we expect that the typical scale of the resulting galaxy will be proportional to r_{200} , giving

$$\alpha \propto r_{200} \propto M^{1/3}, \quad (6.11)$$

where α is the scale length of the exponential disk. This scaling is also a feature of the more detailed models. This leads to a redshift dependence⁶ for the scale-length of $E(z)^{-2/3}$, which could be modified if the shape of the halo potential depends on z_f (e.g. [Navarro et al. 1997](#)).

The details of the more accurate models are of fairly minor importance here since we will mainly focus on the scaling properties of the models, but it is useful to summarise the

⁵That this would be the case was however already realised by [Gunn \(1982\)](#)

⁶Note that the exact redshift dependence depends on whether the circular velocity, V_c or M_{lum} is the variable studied. This is the reason why the redshift dependence in [Mao et al. \(1998\)](#) differs from the one here.

derivation and results obtained. As mentioned above we will follow the approach taken by MMW, but essentially identical results are obtained by the approach taken by DSS. A difference between the two papers is the halo density profile adopted. DSS concentrated mostly on the Hernquist profile (Hernquist 1990)

$$\rho(r) = \frac{M}{2\pi} \frac{a}{r(r+a)^3}, \quad (6.12)$$

where M is the total mass and a is a scale length. The profile mostly used by MMW is the Navarro-Frenk-White (NFW, Navarro et al. 1997) profile

$$\rho(r) = \rho_{\text{crit}} \frac{\delta(c)}{cx(1+cx)^2}, \quad (6.13)$$

where c is the concentration of the halo, $c = r_{200}/r_s$, where r_s is a scale radius (see however Bullock et al. 1999) and $x = r/r_{200}$. The profile depends on the mass of the collapsed objects since c decreases with increasing mass; since low-mass objects collapse earlier, this also leads to a dependence on the redshift of formation (Navarro et al. 1997). MMW did also present a pedagogical derivation for an isothermal sphere

$$\rho(r) = \frac{V_c^2}{4\pi G r^2}, \quad (6.14)$$

where V_c is the constant circular velocity of the halo. In the case of an isothermal sphere this can be integrated to r_{200} and we get a relation between M_{lum} and V_c

$$M_{\text{lum}} = f_{\Delta} f_{\text{lum}} \frac{V_c^3}{10GH(z)}, \quad (6.15)$$

which was the equation used above to compare the Vogt et al. spirals with our estimates of M_{lum} . A similar derivation for a modified Hubble profile is given by Mac Low & Ferrara (1999).

The scalings are similar for the different halo profiles although the quantitative predictions differ somewhat. But, given a halo profile, one can use the virial theorem and the assumption of conservation of specific angular momentum to calculate the resulting disk mass distribution. If the mass-to-light ratio is constant in the disk this is also the scale length of the luminosity distribution in the disk. The resulting expression for the scale length in the isothermal sphere model is

$$R_d = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{f_j}{f_{\text{lum}}} \right) \lambda r_{200}, \quad (6.16)$$

where f_j is the fraction of the total angular momentum that is in the luminous matter⁷, and λ is the spin parameter (Peebles 1969; Fall & Efstathiou 1980)

$$\lambda = \frac{J|E|^{1/2}}{GM^{5/2}}, \quad (6.17)$$

⁷ f_{lum} is related to m_d in MMW through $f_{\text{lum}} = m_d M_{\text{lum}} / M_d$, where M_{lum} is the luminous mass of the disk and M_d is the total mass, and $f_j = j_d J_{\text{lum}} / J_d$, where the J 's are the angular momentum of the luminous and all matter in the disk respectively

with E being the total energy of the halo and J its angular momentum. The corresponding relation for the NFW halo profile is

$$R_d = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{f_j}{f_{\text{lum}}} \right) \lambda r_{200} f_c^{-1/2} f_R(\lambda, c, f_{\text{lum}}, f_j), \quad (6.18)$$

with $f_c \approx \frac{2}{3} + \left(\frac{c}{21.5} \right)^{0.7}$ and f_R given in MMW. The relationship between R_d and the luminous mass of the galaxy follows from Equation (6.10) and $M_{\text{lum}} = f_{\text{lum}} M$ so in total we have the following scaling

$$R_d \propto f_{\text{lum}}^{-1/3} M_{\text{lum}}^{1/3}, \quad (6.19)$$

where we have kept the dependence on f_{lum} explicit to emphasise that it might depend on the mass of the galaxy. Using these scaling laws we now proceed to examine the detailed properties of the spiral galaxies in our sample.

6.3.1 The mass-luminosity relation

One of the simplest relations is the mass-luminosity relation. Locally [Gavazzi et al. \(1996\)](#) find that

$$\log \left(\frac{L}{L_\odot} \right) = 1.66 + 0.76 \log \left(\frac{M}{M_\odot} \right) \quad (6.20)$$

in the B -band. This relation steepens for redder wavelengths so that the mass-to-light ratio is independent of mass in the H -band.

Pure luminosity evolution would shift the zero-point of this relation, whereas mass-dependent luminosity evolution would also change its slope. Any shift with redshift is therefore a very simple probe of the physical evolution of galaxies, and in Figure 6.16 we show the relationship between mass and luminosity for the spirals in our sample divided into three different redshift bins. The dash-dotted line shows Equation (6.20) shifted according to the shift determined relative to the [Vogt et al. \(1997\)](#) spirals above. The dashed lines show orthogonal least-squares fit to the data.

It is clear that our data are insufficient to distinguish between pure and luminosity-dependent luminosity evolution, but the local slope is a good description of our data and in the absence of any clear indication of luminosity-dependent luminosity evolution, we fix the slope of the data to the local value and calculate the shift relative to this slope. This gives a brightening of $\Delta M_B = 0.32 \pm 0.58$ between $\langle z \rangle \approx 0.38$ and $\langle z \rangle \approx 0.86$. This corresponds to a brightening of $\Delta M_B \sim 0.6 \pm 0.6$ from $z = 0$ to $z = 1$ assuming a linear relation with redshift. This is somewhat less than we found in Chapter 4, but considering the errors in reasonable agreement. It is also in reasonable agreement with the independent determination of luminosity evolution from the Tully-Fisher relation from [Vogt et al. \(1997\)](#).

FIGURE 6.16: *The relationship between mass and blue luminosity for the spiral galaxies in the sample. The dash-dotted line shows the local relation from Gavazzi et al. (1996).*

FIGURE 6.17: The local R_d vs V_c relation from [Mathewson & Ford \(1996\)](#) with different fits to the data overlaid. The slope of the best fit lines varies from 0.92 to 1.2

6.3.2 The concentration of spirals

Our aim here is to assess whether the physical properties of spirals change with redshift. A fairly generic prediction of hierarchical models of galaxy formation is that the spiral galaxies at high z are smaller at a given mass than local counterparts ([Kauffmann 1996b](#); [Bouwens et al. 1997](#); [Mo et al. 1998](#)). We will here refer to the size relative to the mass of an object as its concentration, c_R , and study this in more detail.

According to Equation (6.9) the redshift dependence is such that the characteristic radius $R_d \propto E(z_f)^{-2/3}$; in an $\Omega_0 = 1$ model this simplifies to $R_d \propto (1 + z_f)^{-1}$. For the NFW profile the redshift dependence is more complicated since the concentration parameter, c , also depends on z_f . The effect is such that a larger c at high redshift steepens the relation. [Mao et al. \(1998\)](#) attempted to constrain the sizes of spiral disks in this way, but their analysis was hampered by the different datasets used over a large redshift interval. The major step forward here is that we can study trends within one dataset with well-understood selection criteria.

In practice it is difficult to test the applicability of such scalings since they depend on the redshift of formation, z_f and not the redshift at which the galaxy is observed. It is possible to attack this problem in a model dependent way, but we will here focus our interest on model-independent statements as far as it is possible. Following [Mao et al.](#) we will focus on the quantity $c_R = R_d/M_{\text{lum}}^{1/3} \propto R_d/V_c$. In the context of the MMW model this isolates the redshift dependence quite easily. To check that this is a reasonable assumption locally, we follow [Syer et al. \(1999\)](#) and take values for R_d and V_c from [Mathewson & Ford \(1996\)](#). These are plotted against each other in Figure 6.17 and ignoring errors on the values we find $R_d \propto V_c^\alpha$ with values of $\alpha \in [0.92, 1.2]$, fully consistent with the proportionality expected in

FIGURE 6.18: *The mass-radius relationship for the large spirals in our sample. The galaxies were selected to have $R_d > 1.25h^{-1}\text{kpc}$ and negligible bulge component, $B/T < 0.1$. The dashed line shows the orthogonal fit to the data, the dash-dotted line a robust fit. The solid line shows the relation expected by theory $R_d \propto M_{\text{lum}}^{1/3}$.*

the MMW and DSS models, in agreement with [Syer et al. \(1999\)](#).

As we mentioned above it is not immediately obvious that $R_d \propto M_{\text{lum}}^{1/3}$ although $R_d \propto V_c$, since f_{lum} could be mass-dependent. It is therefore necessary to test this assumption for our sample, and in Figure 6.18 we plot R_d vs M_{lum} for spiral galaxies with $R_d > 1.25h^{-1}\text{kpc}$ and negligible bulge component, $B/T < 0.1$. Theoretically one would expect considerable scatter since Equation (6.18) depends on five parameters, and it is clear that the data are noisy and the high redshift data in particular do not constrain the slope at all. The solid line in the plot is the theoretical prediction, $R_d \propto M^{1/3}$, the dashed line an orthogonal least squares fit and the dash-dotted line a robust fit (e.g. [Babu & Feigelson 1996](#)). It is clear that we cannot constrain the relation between R_d and M_{lum} with the data, but the theoretical prediction does at least seem to be a reasonable fit to the data and we will therefore adopt this here. We note in passing that together with the local result above, this implies that f_{lum} does not depend very strongly on the luminous mass. If we parameterise $f_{\text{lum}} = M_{\text{lum}}^\gamma$ we find that $|\gamma| \lesssim 0.1$.

Given this result we have some confidence that $c_R = R_d/M_{\text{lum}}^{1/3}$ will isolate the redshift dependence of the concentration of spirals. Since there are no formal errors on the scale-lengths, we assigned each galaxy an error on the scale-length of 10% of the length in arcseconds and an RMS error of $0.04''$ added in quadrature. For the mass estimates we used the intrinsic errors in $\log M_{\text{lum}}$, and errors were propagated using a simple Monte Carlo

FIGURE 6.19: c_R plotted as a function of redshift for three different selections of spirals in the sample. The top left corner shows all galaxies with $B/T < 0.1$, the top right panel shows the same but this time only galaxies with $R_d > 2h^{-1} \text{ kpc}$, and the last panel shows the galaxies morphologically classified as spirals. The solid line is an unweighted least-squares fit to the data, and the dash-dotted line is the theoretical prediction from Equation (6.18). The dashed blue line shows the predictions of scenario where all spirals formed at the same time and the dot³-dash line shows the relation for a simple merging scenario (see text for details).

analysis. Although the error-bars on the scale-lengths are not rigorous the final results are not very sensitive to our assumptions.

The resulting plot of c_R versus redshift is shown for three different selections of spirals in Figure 6.19. The top left panel shows c_R for all galaxies with $B/T < 0.1$ in our sample, these we can regard as “pure” disks in the sense that the bulge contributes very little. The top right panel shows the relation for big disks defined as in Lilly et al. (1998), with $R_d > 2h^{-1}$ Mpc (These should have the most accurate surface photometry). The last panel shows spiral galaxies as defined by their $A&C$ morphology, in this panel a small number of galaxies that were preferentially fit by de Vaucouleurs profiles were excluded (see also the discussion in Lilly et al. 1998). The solid line in each panel is an unweighted least-squares fit to the points.

The general impression from these panels is that there is a clear trend for disks at high redshift to have smaller c_R . The redshift dependence for the different selections differs somewhat, in the sense that the dependence for the big disks is flatter. The latter is to be expected however, since at a given $R_d = R_{\min}$, say, a decreasing c_R implies a higher mass at high redshift, but high masses are less likely (cf. the mass functions above), thus we will primarily pick up galaxies with low masses for a given scale-length, or higher c_R . The correction for this bias depends on an understanding of the scatter about the best-fit line, and we will instead view the relation found for the most massive disks as a lower limit to the evolution in the sample, and the relation for pure disks as the best estimate. We therefore arrive at an observed evolution of

$$c_R \propto \begin{cases} (1+z)^{1.4 \pm 0.35} & \text{for } \Omega_0 = 1.0, \\ (1+z)^{1.3 \pm 0.35} & \text{for } \Omega_0 = 0.1, \\ (1+z)^{1.3 \pm 0.35} & \text{for } \Omega_0 = 0.35, \lambda = 0.65. \end{cases} \quad (6.21)$$

A comparison with theory requires a model for spiral formation since Equation (6.18) depends on the redshift of formation, z_f . We illustrate this with two toy models, which despite not being rigorous capture the essentials of more elaborate models. Throughout we will use $f_{\text{lum}} = 0.05$, $c = 20$ and $f_J = 0.05$, but unless these values change systematically with observed redshift the conclusions below are not influenced by the actual values, although the zeropoint will change somewhat.

The first model is one in which all spirals formed with z_f drawn from a Gaussian with width 0.5 around $\langle z_f \rangle = 2.0$. This corresponds to a traditional collapse model where spirals form at high redshift and evolve mildly thereafter. This does of course give rise to a distribution of c_R values, shown as a dashed blue line in Figure 6.19 instead of as points for clarity. We see that the predictions of this model is in clear disagreement with the observations.

The second model, shown as the red line in Figure 6.19 is a model where spiral galaxies are 2 Gyr old when they are observed. In comparison with a hierarchical merging model this says that the life-time of a spiral is ~ 2 Gyr before it is transformed. This line can be seen to give a fairly good description of the data, cf. the the solid line fitted to the data. To illustrate the effect of the assumed age, we also plot the expected relation if galaxies were formed at the redshift we observe them as the dash-dotted line.

FIGURE 6.20: The size function derived from the mass functions and Figure 6.19 versus the $z = 0$ size function from De Jong (1996). The top panel shows the size function in three different redshift ranges with no evolution in density. The bottom shows the same but for an evolution consistent with Figure 6.14. See text for further details.

Clearly a model in which spirals undergo merging and morphological transformation is in better agreement with the data than a model in which spirals all formed at high redshift. This statement is most secure for the large disks, since these have the most accurate estimates for R_d and the best K -band photometry. This result is in agreement with Mao et al. (1998), but more robust since it is all within one sample. We therefore conclude that Equation (6.18) is a reasonable description of our data considering the uncertainties.

An important question that this raises is whether this trend for smaller galaxies, at a given mass, at high redshift is consistent with the finding in Lilly et al. (1998) that the size function of spirals is constant with redshift. To check this we fitted a Schechter function by eye to the high-mass end of the low-redshift mass function for spirals; this turns out to be well fit by a Schechter function

$$\phi_{\text{MF}} dM = \phi^* \left(\frac{M_{\text{lum}}}{M_{\text{lum}}^*} \right)^\alpha \exp \left(-\frac{M_{\text{lum}}}{M_{\text{lum}}^*} \right) \frac{dM_{\text{lum}}}{M_{\text{lum}}^*}, \quad (6.22)$$

with $M_{\text{lum}}^* = 1.8 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$, $\alpha = -1.16$ and $\phi^* = 6.6 \times 10^{-4}$ for our fiducial cosmological model. Parameterising the redshift dependence of c_R as $(1+z)^\gamma$ we can write

$$M_{\text{lum}} = \left(\frac{R_d}{R_0} \right)^3 (1+z)^{3\gamma}, \quad (6.23)$$

where we will adopt $\log R_0 = -2.76$ and $\gamma = 0.9$ from the fits for big disks. Relating M_{lum}^* to a characteristic radius R^* using Equation (6.23) at $z = 0$ we arrive at the following relation

for the size function

$$\phi_{\alpha}(R_d, z) = 3\phi^* \left(\frac{R_d}{R^*} \right)^{3\alpha+2} (1+z)^{3\gamma(1+\alpha)} \exp \left(- \left\{ (1+z)^{\gamma} \frac{R_d}{R^*} \right\}^3 \right) \frac{dR_d}{R^*}. \quad (6.24)$$

We compare this with the local size function from De Jong (1996) in Figure 6.20. The top panel shows Equation (6.24) assuming no evolution of the normalisation of the mass function, whereas the bottom panels shows the relation with an evolution, $\phi^* \propto (1+z)^{1.33}$, consistent with Figure 6.8 and 6.14. The main point of these figures is that the change in the size function due to the size evolution found in Figure 6.19 is very small. By comparing this with Figure 3 in Lilly et al. (1998) we see that the size functions derived there are unable to detect these small changes.

6.4 Star formation characteristics

There are two basic physical changes governing galaxy evolution: changes in number density — i.e. merging and the effect this has on morphological mixtures, and changes in the star formation rate. In Section 6.2 we found evidence for changes in the mass density of peculiars and possibly spirals, which is good evidence for the existence of morphological evolution of the galaxy population. In this section we will concentrate on the star formation characteristics of our sample. We studied this as a function of morphological type in Chapter 4, here we will look at the properties as a function of mass.

There has been relatively little work on this in the local universe, but as Kennicutt (1998a) points out there are some tantalising hints that mass and star formation are closely related. In particular Gavazzi & Scodreggio (1996) have proposed a close link between the mass of galaxies and their star formation properties. They based their conclusions mainly on the colours of the galaxies, but they could also support their findings using $H\alpha$ imaging of a poorly characterised subsample. Their main conclusion was that the observations could be explained in a model where the star formation histories of spiral galaxies were exponential with shorter time scales for more massive galaxies. At higher redshift, the only study that compare the mass and star formation is Cowie et al. (1996), see G97 for a very similar study for a subpopulation of galaxies and also Glazebrook et al. (1998) for a related study. The basic result of that investigation was that at higher redshift galaxies with brighter M_K had the largest equivalent widths of [OII].

The disadvantage of star formation alone is that it does not immediately lend itself to physical interpretation, since a SFR of $60 M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$ implies very different physical conditions in a tiny dwarf galaxy and a giant spiral galaxy. Recognising this Cowie et al. (1996) introduced the concept of "mass doubling time": the time it takes a galaxy to double its stellar mass under a simple model. They found that more massive galaxies have shorter mass doubling times at higher redshift, which indicated that massive galaxies "formed" before less massive galaxies, an effect they termed "downsizing".

FIGURE 6.21: The star formation rate per M_{\odot} for the galaxies in the sample. The lines are fits to the three redshift intervals indicated in the figure. The arrows are 2σ upper limits to [OII] for those galaxies with no detected [OII].

TABLE 6.2: The specific star formation rate as a function of redshift

Redshift range	EdS ^a		Open ^b		Flat ^c	
	$\log \mathcal{R}_0$	α	$\log \mathcal{R}_0$	α	$\log \mathcal{R}_0$	α
$0.2 < z < 0.5$	1.98	1.21	1.52	1.20	1.70	1.19
$0.5 < z < 0.75$	2.19	1.18	1.76	1.16	1.96	1.16
$0.75 < z < 1.0$	1.74	1.12	1.52	1.11	1.71	1.12

^a $\Omega_0 = 1.0, h = 0.5, \lambda_0 = 0.0$

^b $\Omega_0 = 0.1, h = 0.75, \lambda_0 = 0.0$

^c $\Omega_0 = 0.35, h = 0.65, \lambda = 0.65$

In the following we will concentrate on the specific star formation rate,

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{SFR}} = \text{SFR}/M_{\text{lum}} \quad (6.25)$$

For a constant star formation rate this is simply the stellar mass doubling time. In Figure 6.21 we plot this quantity as a function of the luminous mass of the galaxy. The SFR was calculated as in Chapter 4 from the observed [OII]. The different colours show the different redshift intervals with an orthogonal least squares fit overlaid for each redshift range. It is obvious that there is a surprisingly tight relation between \mathcal{R}_{SFR} and M_{lum}

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{SFR}} = \mathcal{R}_0 M_{\text{lum}}^{-\alpha} \quad \text{with } \alpha \approx 1.1 - 1.2 \quad (6.26)$$

This relation does not depend sensitively on cosmology (see Table 6.2). The most striking thing about Figure 6.21 is perhaps the fact that \mathcal{R}_{SFR} increases in a monotonic way with redshift, implying that the overall physical evolution of the galaxy population between $z = 1$ and the present is a steady decline in specific star formation rate.

Before going further we should address the question of selection effects. In Figure 6.21, galaxies with no detected [OII] emission are plotted as arrows at their 2σ upper limits. It is clear that the galaxies lie in positions that are roughly consistent with the relations found, but they could point to a downward trend at high masses. There is also a small fraction of galaxies with unknown redshift and of these about 1/3 are expected to be quiescent galaxies (Hammer et al. 1997, see also Crampton et al. 1995). Although these galaxies would tend to steepen the relation, they certainly would *not* flatten it, and we can conclude that the relations summarised in Table 6.2 represent upper limits to the steepness of the specific star formation-mass relation.

This independent data shows why the high mass end of the mass density function is approximately constant out to $z \sim 1$, since there is very little additional mass created through star formation relative to the mass of the galaxies. In Figure 6.21 this is illustrated by the lines which show the level at which a galaxy has to produce stars, with a constant SFR, to double its mass or increase by 10% from $z = 1$ to $z = 0$. It is clear that galaxies with $M_{\text{lum}} > 5 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ at $z < 0.5$ will increase in luminous mass by much less than 10% till the present, and similarly it is clear that we expect very little change in the luminous mass for galaxies with $M_{\text{lum}} \gtrsim 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ over the entire redshift range. This is again consistent with the mass density functions studied earlier.

From Figure 6.21 it is clear that there is little mass-dependent evolution in \mathcal{R}_{SFR} , and that star formation dominates more in low mass galaxies than in massive galaxies. The trend is similar to the “downsizing” effect found by Cowie et al. (1996), but the use of mass as an independent variable makes the trends much clearer. The most immediate consequence of this is that massive galaxies form the majority of their stars at high redshift $z > 1$.

The slope of the lines is also close to $M_{\text{lum}}^{-1.2}$, hence the star formation rate is almost independent of mass. This has interesting implications for the nature of supernova or gamma-ray burst host galaxies (Hogg & Fruchter 1999). If gamma ray bursts are connected to supernovae/hypernovae (Wang & Wheeler 1998; Kippen et al. 1998; Bloom et al. 1998; Paczynski 1998) then the likelihood of a gamma-ray burst happening in a galaxy between

FIGURE 6.22: The star formation rate per unit blue luminosity for galaxies in the sample in three different redshift ranges, notice the lack of a clear correlation with L_B .

$z = 0$ and $z = 1$ is proportional to the mass function of galaxies, which again is roughly proportional to the K -band luminosity function. Since there are many more faint galaxies, this implies that the majority of all gamma-ray burst host galaxies should be very faint in K . Indeed many would be undetected except in very long integrations.

A similar situation would happen with Type II SNe which are thought to be caused by core-collapse in massive and therefore short-lived stars. For the better studied case of Type Ia SNe, the situation is somewhat more uncertain since the formation and evolution of these systems is not well understood although they are thought to happen by thermonuclear explosion of white dwarf (e.g. Canal et al. 1996). If the typical time between star formation and SN Ia is short compared to the Hubble time at the given redshift we would expect a similar result to the one for Type II SNe, whereas if the high-redshift hosts of Type Ia SNe turn out to be bright in K they have to be caused by star formation at $z > 1$. The specific star formation rates derived above could therefore in principle be used to derive constraints on the supernova progenitors. A thorough investigation of this in the context of global star formation rates has been presented by Madau et al. (see also Ruiz-Lapuente & Canal 1998 1998), but we will not pursue this further here.

It is however important to realise that this is a statement about the *mass* of the galaxies, if we instead plotted the star formation rate per unit blue luminosity, the result is quite different. This is shown in Figure 6.22 which shows a lot more scatter than Figure 6.21. It is therefore clear that although the host galaxies are faint in K , they can still be fairly bright in B and hence detectable.

To give a quantitative prediction for this we can adopt the fit to the mass function given above to calculate probabilities for detecting a supernova Type II in a galaxy with a lumi-

nous mass greater than $M_{\text{lum}} = M_{\text{lim}}$ and we find

$$P(\text{Type II SNe} | M_{\text{lum}} > M_{\text{lim}}) = \begin{cases} 0.54 & \text{for } M_{\text{lim}} = 10^9 M_{\odot} \\ 0.22 & \text{for } M_{\text{lim}} = 10^{10} M_{\odot} \\ 0.04 & \text{for } M_{\text{lim}} = 10^{11} M_{\odot} \end{cases} \quad (6.27)$$

where we have normalised by the mass function down to $M_{\text{lum}} = 10^8 M_{\odot}$; since the \mathcal{R}_{SFR} relation only is defined above $M_{\text{lum}} = 10^9$ this normalisation is uncertain. Although the absolute numbers are uncertain, we find that roughly half the Type II SNe host galaxies will have $M_K > -19$.

6.5 Summary

Here we summarise the main results obtained in this chapter and compare them with the results of the previous chapters. For the spiral galaxies we found in Chapter 4 that a brightening of the spiral LF by one magnitude to $z \sim 1$ provided a good fit to the data. The mass-luminosity relation in the B -band is inconsistent with such a large change in the characteristic magnitude; it did instead hint at a milder evolution of about 0.5–0.6 magnitudes or so. Since the quality of the LFs makes it impossible to distinguish clearly between changes in M^* alone and a combination of changes in M^* and ϕ^* , we can therefore conclude that a small decrease in ϕ^* from $z \sim 1$ till the present would bring the LFs and the $M_{\text{lum}} - L_B$ relation in agreement. This is consistent with what we found when looking at the mass density as a function of redshift, and the qualitative agreement of these two almost independent lines of reasoning is gratifying, but the errors are too large in both cases to make a strong statement about merging of spiral galaxies. An additional piece of evidence is however the finding that spiral disks are more compact at high redshift, in good agreement with the predictions of hierarchical clustering and again indicating that some spiral disks undergo morphological changes from $z = 1$ till the present.

Similarly we can conclude that the peculiar galaxies seen at high redshift must be physically distinct from their low redshift counterparts. They must therefore end up as either spirals or ellipticals and since the sum of the mass density in peculiar and elliptical galaxies is roughly constant, it is likely that many peculiar galaxies are transformed into elliptical galaxies. If, as seems likely, some peculiar galaxies end up as spiral galaxies, this only reinforces the argument above that some spirals are transformed into ellipticals. The likely mechanism for this morphological transformation is merging (Schweizer 1982; Barnes & Hernquist 1992, 1996), and it is therefore interesting to look back at the toy model in Chapter 4. There we tried to explain the redshift distribution of peculiar galaxies by postulating two populations, one which changed its number density as $(1+z)^3$ as found by Le Fèvre et al. (1999) and one which was just a slight brightening of the local population of peculiar galaxies.

We now combine these findings together in one simple model that reproduces all the observed properties of the sample. The details of the model are as follows:

FIGURE 6.23: *The simple model described in the text, dashed line, compared with the observed luminosity functions for our fiducial cosmological model.*

- The spiral population is modelled by brightening of the local [Marzke et al. \(1998\)](#) spiral luminosity function by 0.6 magnitudes to $z = 1$ with no change in space density. This is consistent with all the data for our fiducial model, at least if we assume that the visual classifications are correct, and the amount of merging found in the spiral population is minor even with *A&C*-classifications. For an $\Omega_0 = 1$ model we need to assume some merging of spirals to reproduce the LFs below and still satisfy the $M_{\text{lum}} - L_B$ relation.
- The peculiar population is taken to be the sum of the SSRS2 peculiar LF and a population of mergers. The merger population is assumed to make up 10% of the elliptical population locally and have a similar LF, but with an SED similar to an Sbc spiral to allow for the additional star formation during the merging phase; the results are not sensitive to this latter assumption. The number density of the merger population is assumed to evolve with redshift as $(1+z)^3$. This is taken from the study of mergers and close pairs in the sample by [Le Fèvre et al. \(1999\)](#).
- The elliptical population is modelled with the SSRS2 elliptical LF, but the merger population is subtracted off so the space density of elliptical galaxies decreases with redshift.

These choices are consistent with the results of this chapter and since the redshift distributions for spirals and ellipticals do not differ greatly from those shown in [Figure 4.7](#) and the peculiar redshift distribution is shown in [Figure 4.18](#), we will only show the comparison between the simple model and the *B*-band luminosity function. This is shown in [Figure 6.23](#) and agrees very well with the data. It is also interesting to note that this fit is achieved without reference to the absolute *B*-band magnitudes of the peculiar and elliptical galaxies, nor to their redshift distribution.

The bottom line is therefore that we have detected the signature of merging in massive field galaxies between $z = 1$ and the present, but this does not seem to be associated with substantial *unobscured* star formation. We also found that the overall evolution in the star formation characteristics in field galaxies out to $z = 1$ is primarily a monotonic change in specific star formation rate and there is no clear sign of a mass-dependence in this trend. Finally the specific star formation rates also show that most massive galaxies formed the majority of their stars at $z > 1$.

6.6 Future prospects

One of the limitations of our investigation is the relatively poor correspondence between apparent *I*-band magnitudes and mass. This means we are unable to make strong statements about the low-mass end of the mass-function. In contrast, a selection by apparent *K*-band magnitude would suffer much less from selection biases. This is illustrated in [Figure 6.24](#) which shows the selection criteria for a $15 < K < 20$ survey mapped into mass space. This can be compared with [Figure 6.6](#) which shows the same for *I*-band selection. It is clear

FIGURE 6.24: *The selection criteria for a $15 < K < 20$ survey mapped into mass space, similar to the previous figure.*

that the K -band selection is much cleaner. For the present sample it would be possible to perform spectroscopy of the galaxies that are within the K -selection criteria and extend the sample to also be a K -selected sample. In addition it is clear that future surveys should strive towards long-wavelength selection; H and K are particularly interesting in that respect.

Another weakness of the current work is the lack of spatially resolved optical and near-IR photometry. We saw above that the assumption of a given set of BC96 models leads to one of the largest sources of error in M_{lum} . Since real galaxies might have fairly complex star formation histories, varying from place to place, it is clear that the assumption of one best-fit model for the whole galaxy is a somewhat crude approximation. An alternative is to consider spatially resolved photometry since a simple SFR history might be a more reasonable approximation for a small area of the galaxy. Such calculations have been performed with very promising results by [Abraham et al. \(1999\)](#) for galaxies in the HDF-N, but without the near-IR photometry necessary to give resolved mass-distributions in these galaxies. On the ground, the primary sources for this resolved near-IR photometry will be the AO systems on telescopes such as Gemini and Keck, though it might be possible even with the improved optics of UKIRT. However the addition of resolved optical colours require space observations for now, and the availability of NICMOS and the Advanced Camera (ACS) in Cycle 10 will permit such studies to be carried out with HST and much more efficiently by NGST at a later stage.

A major disadvantage at high redshift is however the fact that observed K starts to sample optical wavelengths when $z \gtrsim 1.5$ and already at $z = 1.5$ is the uncertainty in mass similar to the uncertainty in age when the mass is derived from observed K -band. Sufficiently high-resolution mid-infrared imaging capabilities on NGST would be able to address this.

Similarly the detection of dust and gas in these galaxies with sub-mm and mm instruments would allow one to give an account of the total baryonic mass in these galaxies and the relationship between stellar and gas/dust mass at different redshift and in different types of galaxies (see Flores et al. 1999a,b, for a pilot study of some of these galaxies in the far-IR).

Another interesting path of research would be to extend the comparison between V_c and M_{lum} , since these together will provide limits on the mass fraction that end up as disk mass or luminous mass (cf. Equation (6.15)), and with a measurement of R_d we can start studying the dynamical and structural properties of high redshift galaxies in detail. This would be complementary to local studies (Syer et al. 1999), but with the added advantage of a large leverage in redshift.

Finally it would be sensible to extend further the study of star formation in galaxies as a function of stellar mass since it might have interesting implications for the large-scale star formation in normal galaxies (e.g. Silk 1997). It would be of interest to perform a similar analysis in the local universe and in particular to extend the discussion above to give predictions of the magnitude distribution of gamma-ray burst and SN II hosts. Similarly it might be possible to perform an analysis similar to that of Madau et al. (1998) to give predictions of the K -band magnitudes of the Type Ia SNe host galaxies.

Bibliography

- Abraham, R. et al. 1999, in preparation
- Abraham, R. G., Ellis, R. S., Fabian, A. C., Tanvir, N. R., Glazebrook, K. 1999, MNRAS, 303, 641
- Abraham, R. G., Tanvir, N. R., Santiago, B. X., Ellis, R. S., Glazebrook, K., van den Bergh, S. 1996a, MNRAS, 279, L47
- Abraham, R. G., Valdes, F., Yee, H. K. C., van den Bergh, S. 1994, ApJ, 432, 75
- Abraham, R. G., van den Bergh, S., Ellis, R. S., and Basilio X. Santiago, K. G., Griffiths, R. E., Surma, P. 1996b, ApJS, 107, 1
- Alpher, R. A., Herman, R. 1948, Nature, 162, 774
- Avni, Y., Bahcall, J. N. 1980, ApJ, 235, 694
- Baade, W. 1956, PASP, 68, 5
- Babu, G. J., Feigelson, E. D. 1996, Astrostatistics, Chapman & Hall
- Babul, A., Ferguson, H. C. 1996, ApJ, 458, 100
- Babul, A., Rees, M. J. 1992, MNRAS, 255, 346
- Bahcall, N. A., Ostriker, J. P., Perlmutter, S., Steinhardt, P. J. 1999, Science, 284, 1481
- Barger, A. J., Aragon-Salamanca, A., Smail, I., Ellis, R. S., Couch, W. J., Dressler, A., Oemler, A., Poggianti, B. M., Sharples, R. M. 1998, ApJ, 501, 522
- Barger, A. J., Cowie, L. L., Trentham, N., Fulton, E., Hu, E. M., Songaila, A., Hall, D. 1999, AJ, 117, 102
- Barnes, J. E., Hernquist, L. 1992, ARA&A, 30, 705
- Barnes, J. E., Hernquist, L. 1996, ApJ, 471, 115
- Baugh, C. M., Benson, A. J., Cole, S., Frenk, C. S., Lacey, C. G. 1999, MNRAS, 305, L21

- Baugh, C. M., Cole, S., Frenk, C. S. 1996, MNRAS, 283, 1361
- Baugh, C. M., Cole, S., Frenk, C. S., Lacey, C. G. 1998, ApJ, 498, 504
- Beckett, M. G., Mackay, C. D., McMahon, R. G., Parry, I. R., Piche, F., Ellis, R. S. 1997, Proc. SPIE, 2871, 1152
- Benson, A. J., Cole, S., Frenk, C. S., Baugh, C. M., Lacey, C. G. 1999, astro-ph/9903343, submitted to MNRAS
- Bershady, M. A. 1995, AJ, 109, 87
- Bershady, M. A., Hereld, M., Kron, R. G., Koo, D. C., Munn, J. A., Majewski, S. R. 1994, AJ, 108, 870
- Bertin, E., Arnouts, S. 1996, Astronomy and Astrophysics Supplement Series, 117, 393
- Bertschinger, E. 1998, ARA&A, 36, 599
- Binggeli, B., Sandage, A., Tammann, G. A. 1988, ARA&A, 26, 509
- Binney, J. 1977, ApJ, 215, 483
- Binney, J., Merrifield, M. 1998, Galactic astronomy, Princeton Series in Astrophysics, Princeton University Press
- Blandford, R. D., Narayan, R. 1992, ARA&A, 30, 311
- Bloom, J. S., Kulkarni, S. R., Harrison, F., Prince, T., Phinney, E. S., Frail, D. A. 1998, ApJ, 506, L105
- Blumenthal, G. R., Faber, S. M., Primack, J. R., Rees, M. J. 1984, Nature, 311, 517
- Bouwens, R., Broadhurst, T., Silk, J. 1998a, ApJ, 506, 557
- Bouwens, R., Broadhurst, T., Silk, J. 1998b, ApJ, 506, 579
- Bouwens, R. J., Cayon, L., Silk, J. 1997, ApJ, 489, L21
- Branch, D. 1998, ARA&A, 36, 17
- Brinchmann, J., Abraham, R., Schade, D., Tresse, L., Ellis, R. S., Lilly, S., Le Fevre, O., Glazebrook, K., Hammer, F., Colless, M., Crampton, D., Broadhurst, T. 1998, ApJ, 499, 112
- Broadhurst, T. J., Ellis, R. S., Glazebrook, K. 1992, Nature, 355, 55
- Broadhurst, T. J., Ellis, R. S., Shanks, T. 1988, MNRAS, 235, 827
- Bromley, B. C., Press, W. H., Lin, H., Kirshner, R. P. 1998, ApJ, 505, 25

-
- Bruzual, A. G., Kron, R. G. 1980, ApJ, 241, 25
- Bruzual, G. 1983, ApJ, 273, 105
- Bruzual, G. A., Charlot, S. 1993, ApJ, 405, 538
- Bullock, J. S., Kolatt, T. S., Sigad, Y., Somerville, R. S., Kravtsov, A. V., Klypin, A. A., Primack, J. R., Dekel, A. 1999, astro-ph/9908159, submitted to MNRAS
- Burbidge, E. M., Burbidge, G. R., Fowler, W. A., Hoyle, F. 1957, Rev. Mod. Phys. 29, 547
- Byun, Y. I., Freeman, K. C. 1995, ApJ, 448, 563
- Calzetti, D. 1997, AJ, 113, 162
- Calzetti, D., Kinney, A. L., Storchi-Bergmann, T. 1994, ApJ, 429, 582
- Campos, A., Shanks, T. 1997, MNRAS, 291, 383
- Canal, R., Ruiz-Lapuente, P., Burkert, A. 1996, ApJ, 456, L101
- Carroll, S. M., Press, W. H., Turner, E. L. 1992, ARA&A, 30, 499
- Casali, M. M., Hawarden, T. G. 1992, JCMT-UKIRT Newsletter, 3, 33
- Chaboyer, B., Demarque, P., Kernan, P. J., Krauss, L. M. 1998, ApJ, 494, 96
- Charlot, S., Bruzual, A. G. 1991, ApJ, 367, 126
- Charlot, S., Worthey, G., Bressan, A. 1996, ApJ, 457, 625
- Cohen, J. G., Blandford, R., Hogg, D. W., Pahre, M. A., Shopbell, P. L. 1999a, ApJ, 512, 30
- Cohen, J. G., Hogg, D. W., Pahre, M. A., Blandford, R., Shopbell, P. L., Richberg, K. 1999b, ApJS, 120, 171
- Cole, S. 1991, ApJ, 367, 45
- Cole, S., Aragon-Salamanca, A., Frenk, C. S., Navarro, J. F., Zepf, S. E. 1994a, MNRAS, 271, 781
- Cole, S., Ellis, R. S., Broadhurst, T. J., Colless, M. M. 1994b, MNRAS, 267, 541
- Cole, S., Kaiser, N. 1988, MNRAS, 233, 637
- Cole, S., Lacey, C. 1996, MNRAS, 281, 716
- Cole, S., Treyer, M. A., Silk, J. 1992, ApJ, 385, 9

- Coleman, G. D., Wu, C.-C., Weedman, D. W. 1980, *ApJS*, 43, 393
- Colless, M., Ellis, R. S., Broadhurst, T. J., Taylor, K., Peterson, B. A. 1993, *MNRAS*, 261, 19
- Colless, M., Ellis, R. S., Shaw, G., Taylor, K. 1991, *MNRAS*, 253, 686
- Colless, M., Ellis, R. S., Taylor, K., Hook, R. N. 1990, *MNRAS*, 244, 408
- Connolly, A. J., Szalay, A. S., Bershad, M. A., Kinney, A. L., Calzetti, D. 1995, *AJ*, 110, 1071
- Connolly, A. J., Szalay, A. S., Dickinson, M., Subbarao, M. U., Brunner, R. J. 1997, *ApJ*, 486, L11
- Conselice, C. J., Bershad, M. A., Jangren, A. 1999, astro-hp/9907399, to be published in *ApJ*
- Cowie, L. L. 1988, in *Post-Recombination Universe*, p. 1
- Cowie, L. L., Hu, E. M., Songaila, A. 1995a, *Nature*, 377, 603
- Cowie, L. L., Hu, E. M., Songaila, A. 1995b, *AJ*, 110(4), 1576
- Cowie, L. L., Hu, E. M., Songaila, A., Egami, E. 1997, *ApJ*, 481, L9
- Cowie, L. L., Songaila, A., Barger, A. J. 1999, astro-ph/9904345, to be published in *ApJ*
- Cowie, L. L., Songaila, A., Hu, E. M. 1991, *Nature*, 354, 460
- Cowie, L. L., Songaila, A., Hu, E. M., Cohen, J. G. 1996, *AJ*, 112, 839
- Crampton, D., Le Fèvre, O., Lilly, S., Hammer, F. 1995, *ApJ*, 455
- Da Costa, L. N., Geller, M. J., Pellegrini, P. S., Latham, D. W., Fairall, A. P., Marzke, R. O., Willmer, C. N. A., Huchra, J. P., Calderon, J. H., Ramella, M., Kurtz, M. J. 1994, *ApJ*, 424, L1
- Dalcanton, J. J. 1998, *ApJ*, 495, 251
- Dalcanton, J. J., Spergel, D. N., Summers, F. J. 1997, *ApJ*, 482, 659
- Davis, M., Efstathiou, G., Frenk, C. S., White, S. D. M. 1985, *ApJ*, 292, 371
- Davison, A. C., Hinkley, D. V. 1997, *Bootstrap Methods and their Application*, Cambridge Series in Statistical and Probabilistic Mathematics, Cambridge University Press
- De Jong, R. S. 1996, *A&A*, 313, 45
- de Vaucouleurs, G. 1948, *Ann. Astrophys.*, 11, 247

-
- de Vaucouleurs, G. 1959, *Handbuch der Physik*, Vol. 53, 275, Berlin:Springer
- de Vaucouleurs, G., de Vaucouleurs, A., Corwin, Jr, H. G., Buta, R. J., Paturel, G., Fouqué, P. 1991, *Third Reference Catalogue of Bright Galaxies*, Springer-Verlag
- Djorgovski, S., Soifer, B. T., Pahre, M. A., Larkin, J. E., Smith, J. D., Neugebauer, G., Smail, I., Matthews, K., Hogg, D. W., Blandford, R. D., Cohen, J., Harrison, W., Nelson, J. 1995, *ApJ*, 438, L13
- Doi, M., Fukugita, M., Okamura, S. 1993, *MNRAS*, 264, 832
- Dressler, A., Smail, I., Poggianti, B. M., Butcher, H., Couch, W. J., Ellis, R. S., Oemler, A., J. 1999, *ApJS*, 122, 51
- Driver, S., Windhorst, R. A., Griffiths, R. E. 1996a, *IAU Symposia*, 171, 221
- Driver, S. P., Couch, W. J., Phillipps, S., Windhorst, R. A. 1996b, *ApJ*, 466, L5
- Driver, S. P., Fernandez-Soto, A., Couch, W. J., Odewahn, S. C., Windhorst, R. A., Phillips, S., Lanzetta, K., Yahil, A. 1998, *ApJ*, 496, L93
- Driver, S. P., Windhorst, R. A., Griffiths, R. E. 1995, *ApJ*, 453, 48
- Driver, S. P., Windhorst, R. A., Ostrander, E. J., Keel, W. C., Griffiths, R. E., Ratnatunga, K. U. 1995, *ApJ*, 449, L23
- Eales, S. 1993, *ApJ*, 404, 51
- Efstathiou, G., Bond, J. R. 1999, *MNRAS*, 304, 75
- Eggen, O. J., Lynden-Bell, D., Sandage, A. R. 1962, *ApJ*, 136, 748
- Einasto, J., Saar, E., Kaasik, A., Chernin, A. D. 1974, *Nature*, 252, 111
- Ellis, R. S. 1980, *Royal Society of London Philosophical Transactions Series*, 296, 355
- Ellis, R. S. 1995, *Contemporary Physics*, 36(6)
- Ellis, R. S. 1997, *ARA&A*, 35, 389
- Ellis, R. S., Colless, M., Broadhurst, T., Heyl, J., Glazebrook, K. 1996, *MNRAS*, 280, 235
- Faber, S. M., Gallagher, J. S. 1979, *ARA&A*, 17, 135
- Fall, S. M., Efstathiou, G. 1980, *MNRAS*, 193, 189
- Felten, J. E., Isaacman, R. 1986, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 58(3), 689
- Fernandez-Soto, A., Lanzetta, K. M., Yahil, A. 1998, To be published in *ApJ*

- Flores, H., Hammer, F., Désert, F. X., Césarsky, C., Thuan, T., Crampton, D., Eales, S., Le Fèvre, O., Lilly, S. J., Omont, A., Elbaz, D. 1999a, *A&A*, 343, 389
- Flores, H., Hammer, F., Thuan, T. X., Césarsky, C., Desert, F. X., Omont, A., Lilly, S. J., Eales, S., Crampton, D., Le Fèvre, O. 1999b, *ApJ*, 517, 148
- Folkes, S. R. et al. 1999, Accepted for *MNRAS*
- Folkes, S. R., Lahav, O., Maddox, S. J. 1996, *MNRAS*, 283, 651
- Freedman, W. L. 1999, in astro-ph/9909076, to be published in the David Schramm Memorial Volume of Physics Reports.
- Freeman, K. C. 1970, *ApJ*, 160, 811
- Frei, Z., Guhathakurta, P., Gunn, J. E. 1996, *AJ*, 111, 174
- Frenk, C. S., White, S. D. M., Efstathiou, G., Davis, M. 1985, *Nature*, 317, 595
- Fruchter, A. S., Hook, R. N., Busko, I. C., Mutchier, M. 1997, in *The 1997 HST Calibration Workshop with a new generation of instruments*, p. 518.
- Fukugita, M., Hogan, C. J., Peebles, P. J. E. 1998, *ApJ*, 503, 518
- Fukugita, M., Shimasaku, K., Ichikawa, T. 1995, *PASP*, 107, 945
- Gallego, J., Zamorano, J., Aragon-Salamanca, A., Rego, M. 1995, *ApJ*, 455, L1
- Gamow, G. 1948, *Nature*, 162, 680
- Gardner, J. P. 1996, *MNRAS*, 279, 1157
- Gardner, J. P. 1998, *PASP*, 110, 291
- Gardner, J. P., Cowie, L. L., Wainscoat, R. J. 1993, *ApJ*, 415, L9
- Gavazzi, G., Pierini, D., Boselli, A. 1996, *A&A*, 312, 397
- Gavazzi, G., Scodreggio, M. 1996, *A&A*, 312, L29
- Gehrels, N. 1986, *ApJ*, 303, 336
- Geller, M. J., Kurtz, M. J., Wegner, G., Thorstensen, J. R., Fabricant, D. G., Marzke, R. O., Huchra, J. P., Schild, R. E., Falco, E. E. 1997, *AJ*, 114, 2205
- Gilmore, G. 1989, Formation and evolution of the Galaxy, Chapt. 13, in [Gilmore et al. \(1989\)](#)
- Gilmore, G., King, I., van der Kruit, P. 1989, *The Milky Way as a galaxy*, Geneva Observatory

-
- Glazebrook, K., Abraham, R., Santiago, B., Ellis, R., Griffiths, R. 1998, MNRAS, 297, 885
- Glazebrook, K., Ellis, R., Santiago, B., Griffiths, R. 1995, MNRAS, 275, L19
- Glazebrook, K., Ellis, R. S., Colless, M., Broadhurst, T., Allington-Smith, J., Tanvir, N. 1995, MNRAS, 273, 157
- Glazebrook, K., Peacock, J. A., Miller, L., Collins, C. A. 1995, MNRAS, 275, 169
- Gnedin, N. I., Ostriker, J. P. 1992, ApJ, 400, 1
- Gott, J. R., I. 1977, ARA&A, 15, 235
- Gould, A., Bahcall, J. N., Flynn, C. 1996, ApJ, 465, 759
- Greisen, E. W., Calabretta, M. 1993, American Astronomical Society Meeting, 182, 0901
- Greisen, E. W., Calabretta, M. 1995, ASP Conf. Ser. 77: Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems IV, 4, 233
- Griffiths, R. E. et al. 1994, ApJ, 435, L19
- Grogin, N. A., Narayan, R. 1996a, ApJ, 464, 92
- Grogin, N. A., Narayan, R. 1996b, ApJ, 473, 570
- Groth, E. J., Kristian, J. A., Lynds, R., O'Neil, Earl J., J., Balsano, R., Rhodes, J., Idris, W.-. 1994, BAAS, 185, 5309
- Guiderdoni, B., Bouchet, F. R., Devriendt, J., Hivon, E., Puget, J. L. 1999, astro-ph/9902141
- Gunn, J. E. 1982, Vatican: Pontificia Academia Scientiarum
- Gunn, J. E., Gott, J. R., I. 1972, ApJ, 176, 1
- Guzman, R., Gallego, J., Koo, D. C., Phillips, A. C., Lowenthal, J. D., Faber, S. M., Illingworth, G. D., Vogt, N. P. 1997, ApJ, 489, 559
- Hall, P., Mackay, C. D. 1984, MNRAS, 210, 979
- Hammer, F., Flores, H., Lilly, S. J., Crampton, D., Le Fèvre, O., Rola, C., Mallen-Ornelas, G., Schade, D., Tresse, L. 1997, ApJ, 481, 49
- Hernquist, L. 1990, ApJ, 356, 359
- Heyl, J., Colless, M., Ellis, R. S., Broadhurst, T. 1997, MNRAS, 285, 613
- Hibbard, J., Vacca, W. 1997, AJ, 114, 1741

- Hodapp, K. W., Hora, J. L., Hall, D. N., Cowie, L. L., Metzger, M., Irwin, E. M., Keller, T. J., Vural, K., Kozlowski, L. J., Kleinhans, W. E. 1995, *Proc. SPIE*, 2475, 8
- Hogg, D. W. 1999, Distance measures in cosmology, astro-ph/9905116
- Hogg, D. W., Fruchter, A. S. 1999, *ApJ*, 520, 54
- Hogg, D. W., Pahre, M. A., McCarthy, J. K., Cohen, J. G., Blandford, R., Smail, I., Soifer, B. T. 1997, *MNRAS*, 288, 404
- Hook, R. N., Pirzkal, N., Fruchter, A. S. 1999, in *Astronomical Data Analysis Software and Systems VIII*, ASP Conference Series, Vol. 172, 337
- Hoskin, M. A. (ed.) 1998, *The Cambridge concise history of astronomy*, Cambridge University Press
- Hubble, E. 1926, *ApJ*, 64, 321
- Hubble, E. 1934, *ApJ*, 79, 8
- Hubble, E., Humason, M. L. 1931, *ApJ*, 74, 43
- Humason, M. L., Mayall, N. U., Sandage, A. R. 1956, *AJ*, 61, 97
- Im, M., Griffiths, R. E., Naim, A., Ratnatunga, K. U., Roche, N., Green, R. F., Sarajedini, V. L. 1999, *ApJ*, 510, 82
- Impey, C., Bothun, G. 1997, *ARA&A*, 35, 267
- Irwin, M. J. 1985, *MNRAS*, 214, 575
- Iverson, R., Smail, I., Blain, A., Kneib, J.-P., Frayer, D. 1999, astro-ph/9901361
- Jensen, J. B., Tonry, J. L., Luppino, G. A. 1998, *ApJ*, 505, 111
- Jimenez, R., Padoan, P., Matteucci, F., Heavens, A. F. 1998, *MNRAS*, 299, 123
- Jones, B. J. T., Wyse, R. F. G. 1985, *A&A*, 149, 144
- Jones, L. R., Fong, R., Shanks, T., Ellis, R. S., Peterson, B. A. 1991, *MNRAS*, 249, 481
- Kashlinsky, A. 1982, *MNRAS*, 200, 585
- Kauffmann, G. 1996a, *MNRAS*, 281, 487
- Kauffmann, G. 1996b, *MNRAS*, 281, 475
- Kauffmann, G., Charlot, S. 1998a, *MNRAS*, 294, 705
- Kauffmann, G., Charlot, S. 1998b, *MNRAS*, 297, L23

-
- Kauffmann, G., Charlot, S., White, S. D. M. 1996, MNRAS, 283, 117
- Kauffmann, G., Colberg, J. M., Diaferio, A., White, S. D. M. 1999, MNRAS, 303, 188
- Kauffmann, G., Guiderdoni, B., White, S. D. M. 1994, MNRAS, 267, 981
- Kauffmann, G., White, S. D. M. 1993, MNRAS, 261, 921
- Kauffmann, G., White, S. D. M., Guiderdoni, B. 1993, MNRAS, 264, 201
- Kennicutt, R. C., J. 1992a, ApJ, 388, 310
- Kennicutt, R. C., J. 1992b, ApJS, 79, 255
- Kennicutt, R. C., J. 1998a, ARA&A, 36, 189
- Kennicutt, J., R. C. 1998b, in ASP Conf. Ser. 142: The Stellar Initial Mass Function (38th Herstmonceux Conference), 1
- Kent, S. M. 1985, ApJS, 59, 115
- Kippen, R. M., Briggs, M. S., Kommers, J. M., Kouveliotou, C., Hurley, K., Robinson, C. R., Van Paradijs, J., Hartmann, D. H., Galama, T. J., Vreeswijk, P. M. 1998, ApJ, 506, L27
- Kippenhahn, R., Weigert, A. 1990, Stellar structure and evolution, Springer-Verlag
- Kodama, T., Bower, R. G., Bell, E. F. 1999, MNRAS, 306, 561
- Kolb, E. W., Turner, M. S. 1990, The early universe, Frontiers in Physics, Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley, 1988, 1990
- Koo, D. C., Kron, R. G. 1992, ARA&A, 30, 613
- Kron, R. 1980, ApJS, 43, 305
- Lacey, C., Cole, S. 1993, MNRAS, 262, 627
- Lacey, C., Cole, S. 1994, MNRAS, 271, 676
- Lacey, C., Silk, J. 1991, ApJ, 381, 14
- Larson, R. B., Tinsley, B. M. 1978, ApJ, 219, 46
- Lauberts, A., Valentijn, E. A. 1989, in The surface photometry catalogue of the ESO-Uppsala galaxies.
- Le Fèvre, O., Abraham, R., Lilly, S. J., Ellis, R. S., Brinchmann, J., Tresse, L., Colless, M., Crampton, D., Glazebrook, K., Hammer, F., Broadhurst, T. 1999, To be published in MNRAS

- Le Fèvre, O., Crampton, D., Lilly, S. J., Hammer, F., Tresse, L. 1995, ApJ, 455, 60
- Lifshitz, E. M. 1946, J. Phys, USSR, 10, 116
- Lilly, S., Le Fèvre, O., Hammer, F., Crampton, D. 1996, ApJ, 460, L1
- Lilly, S., Schade, D., Ellis, R., Le Fèvre, O., Brinchmann, J., Tresse, L., Abraham, R., Hammer, F., Crampton, D., Colless, M., Glazebrook, K., Mallen-Ornelas, G., Broadhurst, T. 1998, ApJ, 500, 75
- Lilly, S. J., Cowie, L. L., Gardner, J. P. 1991, ApJ, 369, 79
- Lilly, S. J., Le Fèvre, O., Crampton, D., Hammer, F., Tresse, L. 1995a, ApJ, 455, 50
- Lilly, S. J., Tresse, L., Hammer, F., Crampton, D., Le Fèvre, O. 1995b, ApJ, 455, 108
- Lin, H., Kirshner, R. P., Sheckman, S. A., Landy, S. D., Oemler, A., Tucker, D. L., Schechter, P. L. 1996, ApJ, 464, 60
- Longair, M. S. 1998, Galaxy Formation, Springer-Verlag
- Loveday, J. 1999, astro-ph/9907179, submitted to MNRAS
- Loveday, J., Peterson, B. A., Efstathiou, G., Maddox, S. J. 1992, ApJ, 390, 338
- Mac Low, M. M., Ferrara, A. 1999, ApJ, 513, 142
- Madau, P. 1995, ApJ, 441, 18
- Madau, P. 1999, astro-ph/9907268
- Madau, P., Della Valle, M., Panagia, N. 1998, MNRAS, 297, L17
- Madau, P., Ferguson, H. C., Dickinson, M. E., Giavalisco, M., Steidel, C. C., Fruchter, A. 1996, MNRAS, 283, 1388
- Madau, P., Pozzetti, L. 1999, astro-ph/9907315, subitted to MNRAS
- Maddox, S. J., Efstathiou, G., Sutherland, W. J., Loveday, J. 1990a, MNRAS, 243, 692
- Maddox, S. J., Sutherland, W. J., Efstathiou, G., Loveday, J., Peterson, B. A. 1990b, MNRAS, 247, 1P
- Mao, S., Mo, H. J., White, S. D. M. 1998, MNRAS, 297, L71
- Marleau, F. R., Simard, L. 1998, ApJ, 507, 585
- Marzke, R. O., Da Costa, L. N. 1997, AJ, 113, 185

-
- Marzke, R. O., Da Costa, L. N., Pellegrini, P. S., Willmer, C. N. A., Geller, M. J. 1998, ApJ, 503, 617
- Marzke, R. O., Geller, M. J., Huchra, J. P., Harold G. Corwin, J. 1994, AJ, 108(2), 437
- Mateo, M. L. 1998, ARA&A, 36, 435
- Mathewson, D. S., Ford, V. L. 1996, ApJS, 107, 97
- Matthews, K., Soifer, B. T. 1994, in I. S. McLean (ed.), *Infrared astronomy with arrays*, Vol. 190 of *Astrophysics and Space Science Library*, Kluwer
- Menanteau, F., Ellis, R. S., Abraham, R. G., Barger, A. J., Cowie, L. L. 1999, astro-ph/9811465, accepted for MNRAS
- Mestel, L. 1963, MNRAS, 126, 553
- Metcalf, N., Shanks, T., Fong, R., Roche, N. 1995, MNRAS, 273, 257
- Miller, G. E., Scalo, J. M. 1979, ApJS, 41, 513
- Mo, H. J., Mao, S., White, S. D. M. 1998, MNRAS, 295, 319
- Morgan, W. W. 1958, PASP, 70, 364
- Morgan, W. W. 1959, PASP, 71, 394
- Morgan, W. W., Mayall, N. U. 1957, PASP, 69, 291
- Moustakas, L. A., Davis, M., Graham, J. R., Silk, J., Peterson, B. A., Yoshii, Y. 1997, ApJ, 475, 445
- Naim, A., Lahav, O., Buta, R. J., Corwin, H. G., J., De Vaucouleurs, G., Dressler, A., Huchra, J. P., Van Den Bergh, S., Raychaudhury, S., Sodre, L., J., Storrie-Lombardi, M. C. 1995a, MNRAS, 274, 1107
- Naim, A., Lahav, O., Sodre, L., J., Storrie-Lombardi, M. C. 1995b, MNRAS, 275, 567
- Naim, A., Ratnatunga, K. U., Griffiths, R. E. 1997, ApJS, 111, 357
- Narlikar, J. V., Padmanabhan, T. 1991, ARA&A, 29, 325
- Navarro, J. F., Frenk, C. S., White, S. D. M. 1997, ApJ, 490, 493
- Odehahn, S. C., Windhorst, R. A., Driver, S. P., Keel, W. C. 1996, ApJ, 472, L13
- Oke, J. B. 1974, ApJS, 27, 21
- Oke, J. B., Gunn, J. E. 1983, ApJ, 266, 713

- Ostriker, J. P., Peebles, P. J. E. 1973, ApJ, 186, 467
- Ostriker, J. P., Peebles, P. J. E., Yahil, A. 1974, ApJ, 193, L1
- Paczynski, B. 1998, ApJ, 494, L45
- Padmanabhan, T. 1993, Structure formation in the universe, Cambridge University Press
- Parry, I., Sharples, R. M. 1988, in ASP Conf. Ser. 3: Fiber Optics in Astronomy, 93
- Partridge, R. B. 1995, 3K: The Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation, Cambridge University Press
- Partridge, R. B., Peebles, P. J. E. 1967, ApJ, 147, 868
- Peacock, J. 1999, Cosmological physics, Cambridge University Press
- Peebles, P. J. E. 1966, ApJ, 146, 542
- Peebles, P. J. E. 1969, ApJ, 155, 393
- Peebles, P. J. E. 1993, Principles of Physical Cosmology, Princeton University Press
- Penzias, A. A., Wilson, R. W. 1965, ApJ, 142, 419
- Perlmutter, S. et al. 1999, ApJ, 517, 565
- Persic, M., Salucci, P. 1992, MNRAS, 258, 14P
- Peterson, B. A., Ellis, R. S., Efstathiou, G., Shanks, T., Bean, A. J., Fong, R., Zen-Long, Z. 1986, MNRAS, 221, 233
- Phillipps, S., Driver, S. 1995, MNRAS, 274, 832
- Poggianti, B. M. 1997, A&AS, 122, 399
- Poggianti, B. M., Smail, I., Dressler, A., Couch, W. J., Barger, A. J., Butcher, H., Ellis, R. S., Oemler, A., J. 1999, ApJ, 518, 576
- Press, W. H., Schechter, P. 1974, ApJ, 187, 425
- Press, W. H., Teukolsky, S. A., Vetterling, W. T., Flannery, B. P. 1992, Numerical Recipes in Fortran, Cambridge University Press
- Rees, M. J., Ostriker, J. P. 1977, MNRAS, 179, 541
- Refsdal, S. 1964, MNRAS, 128, 307
- Riess, A. G., Press, W. H., Kirshner, R. P. 1996, ApJ, 473, 88

-
- Rix, H. W., Guhathakurta, P., Colless, M., Ing, K. 1997, MNRAS, 285, 779
- Roberts, M. S. 1975, IAU Symposia, 69, 331
- Rocca-Volmerange, B., Guiderdoni, B. 1990, MNRAS, 247, 166
- Rowan-Robinson, M. 1985, The cosmological distance ladder
- Rubin, V. C., Ford, W. K., J. 1970, ApJ, 159, 379
- Ruiz-Lapuente, P., Canal, R. 1998, ApJ, 497, L57
- Salpeter, E. E. 1955, ApJ, 121, 161
- Sandage, A. 1958, ApJ, 127, 513
- Sandage, A. 1961, The Hubble Atlas of Galaxies, Carnegie Institution of Washington
- Sandage, A. 1961a, ApJ, 133, 355
- Sandage, A. 1961b, ApJ, 134, 916
- Sandage, A. 1988, ARA&A, 26, 561
- Sandage, A., Bedke, J. 1994, The Carnegie Atlas of Galaxies, Carnegie Institution of Washington
- Sandage, A., Brucato, R. 1979, AJ, 84, 472
- Sandage, A. R. 1995, Saas-Fee Advanced Course 23, Springer, p. 1
- Scalo, J. 1998, in ASP Conf. Ser. 142: The Stellar Initial Mass Function (38th Herstmonceux Conference), 201
- Scalo, J. M. 1986, Fundamentals of Cosmic Physics, 11, 1
- Schade, D., Lilly, S. J., Crampton, D., Ellis, R. S., Fevre, O. L. H., F., . , F., Brinchmann, J., Abraham, R., Colless, M., Glazebrook, K., Tresse, L., Broadhurst, T. 1999, astro-ph/9906171, to be published in ApJ
- Schade, D. J., Lilly, S. J., Crampton, D., Hammer, F., Le Fèvre, O., Tresse, L. 1995, ApJ, 451, L1
- Schechter, P. 1976, ApJ, 203, 297
- Schmidt, M. 1968, ApJ, 151, 393
- Schweizer, F. 1982, ApJ, 252, 455
- Sellwood, J. A., Moore, E. M. 1999, ApJ, 510, 125

- Shectman, S. A., Landy, S. D., Oemler, A., Tucker, D. L., Lin, H., Kirshner, R. P., Schechter, P. L. 1996, *ApJ*, 470, 172
- Shimasaku, K., Fukugita, M. 1998, *ApJ*, 501, 578
- Silk, J. 1977, *ApJ*, 211, 638
- Silk, J. 1997, *ApJ*, 481, 703
- Simard, L., Pritchett, C. J. 1998, *ApJ*, 505, 96
- Simien, F. 1989, in H. G. Corwin, L. Bottinelli (eds.), *The World of Galaxies*
- Smail, I., Hogg, D. W., Yan, L., Cohen, J. G. 1995, *ApJ*, 449, L105
- Smail, I., Ivison, R., Blain, A., Kneib, J.-P. 1998, astro-ph/9810281
- Solheim, J. E., Tinsley, B. M. 1972, in *IAU Symposia*, Vol. 44, 397
- Somerville, R. S., Primack, J. R., Faber, S. M. 1998, astro-ph/9806228
- Sprayberry, D., Impey, C. D., Irwin, M. J., Bothun, G. D. 1997, *ApJ*, 482, 104
- Stabell, R., Refsdal, S. 1966, *MNRAS*, 132, 379
- Steidel, C. C., Adelberger, K. L., Giavalisco, M., Dickinson, M., Pettini, M. 1999, *ApJ*, 519, 1
- Steinmetz, M., Navarro, J. F. 1999, *ApJ*, 513, 555
- Storrie-Lombardi, M., Lahav, O., Sodre, L., J., Storrie-Lombardi, L. 1992, *MNRAS*, 259, 8P
- Syer, D., Mao, S., Mo, H. J. 1999, *MNRAS*, 305, 357
- Tayler, R. J. 1994, *The stars: their structure and evolution*, Cambridge University Press
- Thonnat, M. 1989, *The world of galaxies*, Chapt. Towards an automated classification of galaxies, 53, Springer, New York
- Tinsley, B. M. 1968, *ApJ*, 151, 547
- Tinsley, B. M. 1972a, *ApJ*, 173, L93
- Tinsley, B. M. 1972b, *A&A*, 20, 383
- Tinsley, B. M. 1977, *ApJ*, 211, 621
- Tinsley, B. M. 1980, *ApJ*, 241, 41

-
- Tolman, R. C. 1934, *Relativity thermodynamics and cosmology*, Oxford
- Treyer, M. A., Ellis, R. S., Milliard, B., Donas, J., Bridges, T. J. 1998, *MNRAS*, 300, 303
- Trimble, V. 1987, *ARA&A*, 25, 425
- Tully, R. B., Pierce, M. J., Huang, J. S., Saunders, W., Verheijen, M. A. W., Witchalls, P. L. 1998, *AJ*, 115, 2264
- Tyson, J. A. 1988, *AJ*, 96, 1
- van den Bergh, S. 1960a, *ApJ*, 131, 558
- van den Bergh, S. 1960b, *ApJ*, 131, 215
- van den Bergh, S. 1998, *Galaxy Morphology and Classification*, Cambridge University Press
- van der Kruit, P. 1989, Chemical evolution and disk-galaxy formation, Chapt. 14, in [Gilmore et al. \(1989\)](#)
- Van Der Kruit, P. C. 1987, *A&A*, 173, 59
- Van Dokkum, P. G., Franx, M., Kelson, D. D., Illingworth, G. D. 1998, *ApJ*, 504, L17
- van Kampen, E., Jimenez, R., Peacock, J. A. 1998, in *19th Texas Symposium on Relativistic Astrophysics and Cosmology*
- Vogt, N. P., Forbes, D. A., Phillips, A. C., Gronwall, C., Faber, S. M., Illingworth, G. D., Koo, D. C. 1996, *ApJ*, 465, L15
- Vogt, N. P., Phillips, A. C., Faber, S. M., Gallego, J., Gronwall, C., Guzman, R., Illingworth, G. D., Koo, D. C., Lowenthal, J. D. 1997, *ApJ*, 479, L121
- Wagoner, R. V., Fowler, W. A., Hoyle, F. 1967, *ApJ*, 148, 3
- Walker, T. P., Steigman, G., Kang, H., Schramm, D. M., Olive, K. A. 1991, *ApJ*, 376, 51
- Wang, L., Wheeler, J. C. 1998, *ApJ*, 504, L87
- White, S. D. M. 1996, astro-ph/9605035 to be published in proceedings of the ESO workshop on Large Millimeter Arrays ed. P. Shaver
- White, S. D. M., Frenk, C. S. 1991, *ApJ*, 379, 52
- White, S. D. M., Rees, M. J. 1978, *MNRAS*, 183, 341
- Williams, R. E. et al. 1996, *AJ*, 112, 1335
- Willmer, C. N. A. 1997, *AJ*, 114, 898

- Witt, A. N., Gordon, K. D. 1999, astro-ph/9907342, accepted for ApJ
- Worthey, G. 1994, ApJS, 95, 107
- Yee, H. K. C. 1998, in astro-ph/9809347. A review article to appear in the proceedings of the Xth Recontres de Blois: Birth of Galaxies; Blois, France, July 1998
- Yoshii, Y. 1993, ApJ, 403, 552
- Yoshii, Y., Takahara, F. 1988, ApJ, 326, 1
- Zaritsky, D., Zabludoff, A. I., Willick, J. A. 1995, AJ, 110, 1602
- Zepf, S. E. 1997, Nature, 390, 377
- Zucca, E. et al. 1997, A&A, 326, 477
- Zucca, E., Pozzetti, L., Zamorani, G. 1994, MNRAS, 269, 953
- Zwicky, F. 1937, ApJ, 86, 217

Appendix A

An astrophysical reference

Cosmologists are often wrong, but never in doubt.

LEV LANDAU

This appendix contains a set of basic equations of standard cosmology and astronomy that will be used throughout the thesis. The intention of this appendix is to act as a reference, no detailed derivations will be given for the relations. Further details can be found in any of the standard textbooks (e.g. [Peebles 1993](#); [Padmanabhan 1993](#); [Binney & Merrifield 1998](#); [Peacock 1999](#); [Longair 1998](#)). We will first summarise a few standard conventions in astronomy before giving a reference of basic cosmology.

A.1 An astronomical glossary

Throughout the thesis we will use some nomenclature that is standard in astronomy. Here we will just provide a quick reference for the reader, it is not intended to be exhaustive.

Measures of flux The standard way to report the flux of an object in astronomy is to quote it in *magnitudes*. These are related to the flux through

$$m = -2.5 \log \langle f \rangle + C, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where C is a constant offset, and where the angular brackets denote average over a response function which is composed of the response of the telescope, instrument and the filter in use,

$$\langle f \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_{\lambda} R(\lambda) d\lambda, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where f_{λ} is the flux per wavelength interval. The filter functions adopted give the *photometric system*; in addition it is necessary to give the normalisation of the magnitude system. The traditional approach has been to assign a magnitude of 0.0 to Vega, which is convenient for stellar photometry. This has the disadvantage of giving a complicated relation between

magnitude and flux. A thorough discussion of this and other aspects of synthetic photometry is given by Fukugita et al. (1995). An alternative normalisation is provided by AB magnitudes (Oke 1974; Oke & Gunn 1983) which are simply related to flux through

$$m_{\text{AB}} = -2.5 \log f_{\nu} + 48.60, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where f_{ν} is the flux in $\text{ergs cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{Hz}^{-1}$. We will use AB magnitudes in the first four chapters where we primarily use optical photometry and Vega magnitudes in the last two chapters where we include near-IR photometry.

The *apparent* magnitudes described above relates only to the received flux and are as such distance dependent. We define the *absolute magnitude*, M , to be the magnitude an object would have had at a distance of 10 parsecs so that

$$m - M = 5 \log d_L + 25, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where the *luminosity distance*, d_L , is given in mega parsec (Mpc).

Methods for magnitude measurements The definitions of magnitude above ignores the complications of noise and finite backgrounds on the measurement of magnitudes. These effects means that one only measures a certain fraction of the light coming from a galaxy (Yoshii 1993). Different methods for measuring galaxy photometry have therefore been proposed, and can for our purposes roughly be grouped in three groups

Aperture magnitudes are measured in a fixed size aperture. Most work is done using a fixed size in the observed plane, but it is probably more physical to measure with the same *physical* size (e.g. Glazebrook et al. 1995). This requires the photometry to be redone after the redshift of the galaxy is known. Large ($3''$ – $6''$) aperture magnitudes are usually good estimates of the total flux of a galaxy at high redshift, but less so at lower redshift. Their primary use in this thesis is to measure colours since they measure similar parts of the galaxies.

Isophotal magnitudes are measured by summing up the flux in all pixels down to a given isophote, or surface brightness level. This is extensively used for local galaxies and sizes of galaxies locally are often measured down to $\mu_B = 25$, where μ is the conventional symbol for surface brightness. The disadvantage of isophotal magnitudes is that surface brightness decreases with redshift¹ as $(1+z)^3$ and a given observed isophote corresponds to a very different physical size at high redshift. It is possible to get around this as a practical problem by going to extremely faint isophotal limits, which is the approach taken by the CFRS survey (Lilly et al. 1995a).

Corrected magnitudes is an amorphous class of magnitude measures that attempt to correct the measured flux to some estimate of the *total* flux of the object. For stellar

¹It is often stated that surface brightness decreases as $(1+z)^4$, but this is correct only for bolometric surface brightness.

sources this is fairly straightforward since these have well-defined intensity profiles. For galaxies the intensity profiles are *a priori* unknown and any correction is therefore uncertain. A full discussion of these methods is outside the scope of this summary, see [Dalcanton \(1998\)](#), and references therein). The most important measure for our discussion and the one adopted for most photometry in this thesis is the [Kron \(1980\)](#) “total” magnitude. This is defined as by taking the first moment of the light distribution

$$r_1 = \frac{\int_0^R rI(r)dr}{\int_0^R I(r)}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

and measure the flux within $r = kr_1$. This radius has been shown ([Kron 1980](#) see also [Bershady et al. 1994](#)) to encircle $\sim 90\%$ of the light for galaxies between $0.1 < z < 2$.

A.2 Cosmology

In expanding universe models we decompose distances into a time-independent *comoving* distance, l , and a time-dependent *scalefactor*, $R(t)$ so that lengths evolve as $l(t) = R(t)l(t_0)$. We normally set $R(t_0) = 1$ at the present. The redshift of an object observed at time t_{em} is defined through

$$\frac{\lambda_{\text{em}}}{\lambda_0} = \frac{R(t_{\text{em}})}{R(t_0)} = \frac{1}{1+z}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where λ_{em} is the wavelength of the light when it was emitted, the *rest wavelength* and λ_0 is the wavelength measured at $t = t_0$. The velocity of a test-particle is given as

$$v(t) = \frac{dl}{dt} = l(t_0)\dot{R}(t) = l(t)H(t), \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where $H(t) = \dot{R}/R$ is the expansion rate and its value at present, H_0 is called the Hubble constant. The relationship between redshift and time is given in [Table A.1](#).

The Friedman-Robertson-Walker universe The most general metric in a homogeneous and isotropic universe can be shown to be the Robertson-Walker metric

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + \frac{R(t)^2}{c^2} \left(\frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} + r^2 d\theta^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right), \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where c is the lightspeed, set to 1 in the following and where k can take the values $k = -1, 0, 1$, corresponding to a hyperbolic, flat and spherical geometry of the hypersurfaces, $t = \text{const}$.

The addition of matter in the Robertson-Walker universe gives rise to the Lemaître equations

$$\left(\frac{\dot{R}}{R}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G\rho}{3} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} - \frac{k}{R^2} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\frac{\ddot{R}}{R} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho + 3p) + \frac{\Lambda}{3}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

where c is set to unity, R is the scalefactor, ρ is the density, p is the pressure and Λ is the cosmological constant. We will throughout assume that $p = 0$, which gives the *Friedman equations*. The results are fairly insensitive to this approximation (Sandage 1961a). If we assume that $\Lambda > 0$, it is clear from the first equation that for $k = -1$, the universe will expand forever and for $k = 1$ it will reach a state of maximum expansion and then contract. Writing the first equation at $t = t_0$ we have

$$\frac{k}{R_0^2} = H_0^2(\Omega_0 + \lambda_0 - 1) = H_0^2\Omega_R, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where we define² $\Omega_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 8\pi G\rho_0/3H_0^2$ and $\lambda_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \Lambda/3H_0^2$. Thus we see that a universe with $\Omega_0 + \lambda_0 = 1$ will have that $\dot{R} \rightarrow 0$ at large times. We call these universe models *flat* and models with $\Omega_0 < 1$ or $\Omega_0 > 1$ for *open* and *closed* respectively (assuming $\lambda_0 = 0$). The flat universe with $\Omega_0 = 1$, $\lambda_0 = 0$ is called the Einstein-de Sitter universe model.

Number conservation of particles implies that $\rho \propto (1+z)^3$ which together with the fact that $R \propto (1+z)^{-1}$ leads to the following useful rewrite of Equation (A.9)

$$H(z) = H_0 \left(\Omega_0(1+z)^3 + \lambda_0 - \Omega_R(1+z)^2 \right)^{1/2} = H_0 E(z), \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where $H(z) = \dot{R}/R$ and we have used the definition of z from Equation (A.6). The rapid evolution of ρ with redshift also implies that at early times ($R \ll 1$), Equation (A.9) approaches the flat solution $\Omega = 1$. Reversing the argument one can immediately see that a solution that is close to $\Omega = 1$ at early time will deviate from by a large factor at late redshifts. If we write the density at redshift z as $\Omega(z)$, and set $\lambda_0 = 0$, we have the elegant equation

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{\Omega(z)}\right) = \frac{1}{1+z} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\Omega_0}\right), \quad (\text{A.13})$$

which shows that if $\Omega_0 = 0.3$ today, it would have been 0.998 at $z = 1000$ and much closer to 1 at earlier times. This need for such fine-tuning of the density parameter is often termed the *flatness* problem and has been used as an argument for inflation (e.g. Narlikar & Padmanabhan 1991). It is also known as one of the Dicke coincidences (Peebles 1993).

²Older works use $\sigma_0 = \Omega_0/2$ and $q_0 = \sigma_0 - \lambda_0$ (e.g. Stabell & Refsdal 1966)

The evolution of small density inhomogeneities in a Friedman universe can be treated with a perturbational analysis of the general relativistic equations (e.g. [Padmanabhan 1993](#)). The result is normally formulated in terms of the fractional overdensity, δ

$$\delta(x,t) = \frac{\rho(x,t) - \rho_b(t)}{\rho_b(t)}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where ρ_b is the smooth background density. The growing mode of these perturbations in the linear regime is given by

$$\delta \propto E(z) \int_z^\infty \frac{1+z}{E(z)^3} dz. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

In the case of an Einstein-de Sitter spacetime this simplifies considerably and we obtain $\delta \propto (1+z)^{-1} \propto t^{2/3}$.

Measures of distance Distances in an expanding non-Euclidean universe depend on the definitions used. The different distance measures have been well summarised by [Hogg \(1999\)](#), the most important measures for us can be summarised as follows:

Radial comoving distance This distance is found from the metric (Equation (A.8)) for light rays, i.e. $ds = 0$, and is

$$D_r(z) = \frac{c}{H_0} \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{E(z')} = \frac{c}{H_0} d_r(z) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Transverse comoving distance This is the coordinate distance at constant r and t and we denote it with $r(z)$,

$$r(z) = \frac{c}{H_0} S_k(d_r(z)) \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The function S_k (see [Peacock 1999](#)) depends on the curvature k and is given as

$$S_k(x) = \begin{cases} \Omega_R^{-1/2} \sinh(\sqrt{\Omega_R} x) & \text{for } \Omega_R > 0 \text{ (open)} \\ x & \text{for } \Omega_R = 0 \text{ (flat)} \\ \Omega_R^{-1/2} \sin(\sqrt{\Omega_R} x) & \text{for } \Omega_R < 0 \text{ (closed)} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Special values for $r(z)$ is given in Table A.1.

Angular diameter distance This is defined to be the ratio between the physical transverse size of an object to the observed angular size. It is related to the transverse comoving distance through

$$d_A(z) = \frac{r(z)}{1+z} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Luminosity distance This is the distance which makes the bolometric flux drop off proportionally to the square of the distance as in classical geometry, $f \propto L/d_L^2$. This is also related to $r(z)$ in a simple manner through

$$d_L(z) = (1+z)r(z) \tag{A.20}$$

We see that a knowledge of $E(z)$ and $r(z)$ makes it possible to calculate d_A and d_L in a simple way. This also extends to the comoving volume element per unit solid angle, $dV/d dz$, and we summarise these findings in Table [A.1](#).

TABLE A.1: *The basic equations of Friedman-Robertson-Walker spacetime*

General	
$H(z)/H_0 = E(z)$	$\sqrt{\Omega_0(1+z)^3 + (1 - \Omega_0 - \lambda_0)(1+z)^2 + \lambda_0}$
$H_0 t(z)$	$\int_z^\infty \frac{dz}{(1+z)E(z)}$
$H_0 r(z)$	$\frac{c}{H_0} S_k \left(\int_0^z \frac{dz}{E(z)} \right)$
$d_L(z)$	$\frac{c}{H_0} (1+z)r(z)$
$\frac{dV}{dzd}$	$cH_0^{-1} \frac{r(z)^2}{E(z)}$
Flat	
$H(z)/H_0 = E(z)$	$\sqrt{\Omega_0(1+z)^3 + \lambda_0}$
$H_0 r(z)$	$\int_0^z \frac{dz}{E(z)}$
Open	
$H(z)/H_0 = E(z)$	$(1+z)\sqrt{\Omega z + 1}$
$H_0 r(z)$	$\frac{2(2 - \Omega_0 + \Omega_0 z - (2 - \Omega_0)\sqrt{1 + \Omega_0 z})}{\Omega_0^2(1+z)}$
$\frac{dV}{dzd}$	$\frac{4c}{H_0 \Omega_0^4 (1+z)^3} \frac{(2 - \Omega_0 + \Omega_0 z - (2 - \Omega_0)\sqrt{1 + \Omega_0 z})^2}{\sqrt{1 + \Omega_0 z}}$
Einstein-de Sitter	
$H(z)/H_0 = E(z)^\dagger$	$(1+z)^{3/2}$
$H_0 t(z)$	$\frac{2}{3}(1+z)^{3/2}$
$H_0 r(z)^\ddagger$	$2 \left(1 - 1/\sqrt{1+z} \right)$
$\frac{dV}{dzd}$	$\frac{4c}{H_0 \Omega_0^4 (1+z)^2} \frac{(\sqrt{1+z} - 1)^2}{\sqrt{1+z}}$